

UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES AND VETERINARY MEDICINE OF CLUJ NAPOCA
FACULTY OF VETERINARY MEDICINE

CLUJ-NAPOCA, 2022

Ph.D. THESIS

Biology and ecology of the invasive mosquito species in Romania: distribution and molecular analysis of *Aedes albopictus* and *Aedes japonicus*

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Teză de doctorat

Biologia și ecologia speciilor de țânțari invazivi în România: distribuția și analiza moleculară a speciilor *Aedes albopictus* și *Aedes japonicus*

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UNIVERSITATEA DE ȘTIINȚE AGRICOLE ȘI MEDICINĂ VETERINARĂ DIN CLUJ-NAPOCA
FACULTATEA DE MEDICINĂ VETERINARĂ

PUBLICATION LIST

Papers published on the topic of the Ph.D. thesis

1. FĂLCUȚĂ, E., PRIOTEASA L., F., **HORVÁTH, C.**, PĂSTRAV, I., R., SCHAFFNER, F., **MIHALCA, A., D.** 2020. The invasive Asian tiger mosquito *Aedes albopictus* in Romania: towards a country-wide colonization? *Parasitology Research* 119, 841-845 (I. F. 2.20) (Chapter 2.1.1.)
2. **HORVÁTH, C.**, CAZAN, C., D., **MIHALCA, A., D.** 2021. Emergence of the invasive Asian bush mosquito, *Aedes (Finlaya) japonicus japonicus*, in an urban area, Romania. *Parasites & Vectors*, 14, 192 (I. F. 3.876) (Chapter 2.1.2.)
3. MIRANDA, M., Á., BARCELÓ, C., ARNOLDI, D., AUGSTEN, X., BAKRAN-LEBL, K., BALATSOS, G., BENGGOA, M., BINDLER, P., BORŠOVÁ, K., BOURQUIA, M., BRAVO-BARRIGA, D., ČABANOVÁ, V., CAPUTO, B., CHRISTOU, M., DELACOUR, S., ERITJA, R., FASSI-FIHRI, O., FERRAGUTI, M., FLACIO, E., FRONTERA, E., FUEHRER, H., P., GARCÍA-PÉREZ, A., L., GEORGIADIS, P., GEWEHR, S., GOIRI, F., GONZÁLEZ, M., A., GSCHWIND, M., GUTIÉRREZ-LÓPEZ, R., **HORVÁTH, C.**, IBÁÑEZ-JUSTICIA, A., JANI, V., KADRIAJ, P., KALAN, K., KAVRAN, M., KLOBUČAR, A., KURUCZ, K., LUCIENTES, J., LÜHKEN, R., MAGALLANES, S., MARINI, G., MARTINOU, A., F., MICHELUTTI, A., **MIHALCA, A., D.**, MONTALVO, T., MONTARSI, F., MOURELATOS, S., MUJA-BAJRAKTARI, N., MÜLLER, P., NOTARIDES, G., COSTA OSÓRIO, H., OTEO, J., A., OTER, K., PAJOVIĆ, I., PALMER, J., R., B., PETRINIC, S., RĂILEANU, C., RIES, C., ROGOZI, E., RUIZ-ARRONDO, I., SANPERA-CALBET, I., SEKULIĆ, N., SEVIM, K., SHERIFI, K., SILAGHI, C., SILVA, M., SOKOLOVSKA, N., SOLTÉSZ, Z., SULESCO, T., ŠUŠNJAR, J., TEEKEMA, S., VALSECCHI, A., VASQUEZ, M., I., VELO, E., MICHAELAKIS, A., WINT, W., PETRIĆ, D., SCHAFFNER, F., DELLA TORRE, A. 2022. AIMSurov: First Pan-European harmonized surveillance of *Aedes* invasive mosquito species of relevance for human vector-borne diseases. *Gigabyte*, 1-11 (DOAJ)
4. JUŽNIČ-ZONTA, Ž., SANPERA-CALBET, I., ERITJA, R., PALMER, J., R., B., ESCOBAR, A., GARRIGA, J., OLTRA, A., RICHTER-BOIX, A., SCHAFFNER, F., DELLA TORRE, A., MIRANDA, M., Á., KOOPMANS, M., BARZON, L., BARTUMEUS FERRE, F.,*Mosquito Alert Digital Entomology Network Collaborators: ALARCÓN-ELBAL, P., M., GONZÁLEZ, M., A., PUIG, M., A., BAKRAN-LEBL, K., BALATSOS, G., BARCELÓ, C., BENGGOA PAULIS, M., BISIA, M., BLANCO-SIERRA, L., BRAVO-BARRIGA, D., CAPUTO, B., COLLANTES, F., COSTA OSÓRIO, H., CURMAN POSAVEC, M., CVETKOVIKJ, A., DEBLAUWE, I., DELACOUR, S., ESCARTIN PEÑA, S., FERRAGUTI, M., FLACIO, E., FUEHRER,

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 6. VALADAS, V., PICHLER, V., **HORVÁTH, C.**, AKINER, M., CASTRO, A., CAPINHA, C., CAPUTO, B., DELLA TORRE, A., SCHAFFNER, F., PINTO, J. Molecular survey of the F1534C knockdown mutation in *Aedes albopictus* from Europe (in-prep)
 7. **HORVÁTH, C.**, VALADAS, V., **MIHALCA, A., D.**, PINTO, J. Genotyping of various microsatellite loci show multiple introduction events of *Aedes albopictus* (Diptera: Culicidae) in Romania (in-prep) (Chapter 2.2.1.)

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1. TOMAZATOS, A., JANSEN, S., PFISTER, S., TÖRÖK, E., MARANDA, I., **HORVÁTH, C.**, KERESZTES, L., SPÎNU, M., TANNICH, E., JÖST, H., SCHMIDT-CHANASIT, J., CADAR, D., LÜHKEN, R. 2019. Ecology of West Nile Virus in the Danube Delta, Romania: Phylogeography, Xenosurveillance and Mosquito Host-Feeding Patterns. *Viruses*, 11(12):1159. (I.F. 3.811)
2. CAZAN, C., D., PĂSTRAV, I., R., **HORVÁTH, C.** 2020. Seasonal dynamics of mosquitoes in a large urban area of Transylvania, Romania. *Sci Parasitol*, 21(3):86-93, ISSN 1582-1366
3. CAZAN, C., D., **HORVÁTH, C.**, PANAIT, L., C., POREA, D., MARINOV, M., ALEXE, V., **MIHALCA, A., D.** 2021. Seasonality of sand flies (Diptera: Psychodidae) in cave microhabitats and the rediscovery of *Sergentomyia minuta* (Rondani, 1843) after fifty years. *Parasites & Vectors*, 14, 476. (I. F. 3.876)
4. BALMOȘ, O., M., SUPEANU, A., TAMBA, P., **HORVÁTH, C.**, PANAIT, L., C., CAZAN, C., D., UNGUR, A., MOTIU, M., MANITA, F., A., ANCUCEANU, B., C., BĂRBUCEANU, F., DHOLLANDER, S., **MIHALCA, A., D.** 2022. African Swine Fever Virus load in hematophagous dipterans collected in outbreaks from Romania: risk factors and implications. *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases* (accepted for publication)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

First, I would like to thank my Ph.D. coordinator, Prof. Andrei Daniel Mihalca for accepting me as his Ph.D. student, and for the opportunities that he offered me over these years; Andi, without your help I would not have been able to pursue this work and to achieve all these results, thank you for being my supervisor and for advising me along the way!

I would like to thank all my collaborators over the years, special thanks to Prof. Dušan Petrić and his team from the University of Novi Sad, Prof. Romeo Bellini and his lab from CAA; Prof. João Pinto, and dr. Vera Valadas from IHMT; dr. Kornélia Kurucz from the University of Pécs - and last, but not least - to the whole AIM-COST community - to whom I am forever indebted for their help and support. Thank you!

I would also like to thank all my colleagues and members of the Department of Parasitology and Parasitic Diseases at USAMV Cluj-Napoca for their help and support, especially to Oana M. Balmoş and Silvia D. Borşan- who always offered me a helping hand when needed- thank you, girls, for your love and support!

I would like to thank my family, especially my parents who never stopped believing in me and supported me in pursuing my dreams! I dedicate this work to them, I want you to know that I love you and that I am forever grateful to you. I hope you are proud of me!

Last but not least, I would like to thank my friends for their emotional support, to Hajni and to Kata, who were there from the start, thank you for sharing this journey with me, for all the good memories, and thank you that you were always there for me, no matter what.

During my Ph.D. studies, I was supported by: the VectExel project “Multidisciplinary One Health excellence research platform for neglected and emerging vector-borne diseases”, project number 57 PCCDI/2018, grant agency The Executive Unit for Funding Higher Education and University Scientific Research (UEFISCDI) Romania and by the “Collegium Talentum” Programme of Hungary;

*“We inhabit a universe where atoms are made in the centres of stars; where each second a thousand suns are born; where life is sparked by sunlight and lightning in the airs and waters of youthful planets; where the raw material for biological evolution is sometimes made by the explosion of a star halfway across the Milky Way; where a thing as beautiful as a galaxy is formed a hundred billion times - a Cosmos of quasars and quarks, snowflakes and fireflies, where there may be black holes and other universe and extra-terrestrial civilizations whose radio messages are at this moment reaching the Earth. How pallid by comparison are the pretensions of superstition and pseudoscience; **how important it is for us to pursue and understand science, that characteristically human endeavour.**”*

Carl Sagan – Cosmos

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AIM	<i>Aedes</i> invasive mosquito
AIM-Cost	<i>Aedes</i> invasive mosquito COST Action
a.m.	ante meridiem
AMC	<i>Anopheles maculipennis</i> complex
AS-PCR	allele-specific polymerase chain reaction
BH	Bihor (county)
BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
bp	base pair
BTi	<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> subspecies <i>israelensis</i>
°C	degrees Celsius
CT	Constanța (county)
ca.	circa
CDC	Centers For Disease Control And Prevention
CDC-LT	CDC-Light Traps
CEV	California encephalitis virus
CHIKV	chikungunya virus
cm	centimetres
COI	cytochrome c oxidase subunit I
COST	European Cooperation in Science and Technology
coxI/COXI	Cytochrome c oxidase subunit I
CO ₂	carbon-dioxide
CTAB	Cetyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide
DDBR	Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve
DENV	dengue virus
DHF	dengue haemorrhagic fever
DF	dengue fever
DNA	deoxyribonucleic acid
dNTP	deoxyribonucleoside triphosphates
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Control
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
EEEV	Eastern equine encephalitis virus
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
e.g.	for example
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency (United States)
ET AL.	and others

EU	European Union
EU-WHO	World Health Organization Europe regional office
EWS	Early warning systems
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
Fis	inbreeding coefficient
F _{ST}	Fixation index
GG	mutated allele
GISD	Global Invasive Species Database
GR	Giurgiu (county)
GT	gravid traps
Hd	heterozygote deficit
He	expected heterozygosity
HLC	human landing catch
Ho	observed heterozygosity
HWE	Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
IBD	isolation by distance
i.e.	id Est
IL	Ilfov (county)
IMS	invasive mosquito species
ISSG	Invasive Species Specialist Group
IUCN	International Union for the Conservation of Nature
JCV	Jamestown canyon virus
JEV	Japanese encephalitis virus
kdr	knockdown resistance
L	litre
L1, L2, L3, L4	first, second, third and fourth stage larvae
LD	linkage disequilibrium
LEDV	Lednice virus
LACV	La Crosse encephalitis virus
MALDI-TOF MS spectrometry	matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization-time of flight mass spectrometry
MBD	mosquito-borne disease
m	meters
MgCl ₂	Magnesium chloride
MH	Mehedinți (county)
mm	millimetres
mM	milimole
mL	millilitre

NaCl	Sodium chloride
No allele	number of alleles
OHFV	Omsk haemorrhagic fever virus
ONNV	O’Nyong Nyong virus
PCR	polymerase chain reaction
pH	potential of hydrogen
PH	Prahova (county)
p.m.	post meridiem
r	estimated frequency of null alleles
RNA	ribonucleic acid
ROBU	Bucharest (population)
ROCO	Constanța (population)
RODE	Oradea (population)
ROPL	Ploșoru (population)
ROSM	Satu-Mare (population)
ROTI	Timișoara (population)
RRV	Ross River virus
Rs	allele richness
RVFV	Rift Valley fever virus
SB	Sibiu county
SIT	Sterile-Insect Technique
s	second
s.l.	sensu lato
sp/spp.	species
s.r.l.	limited liability company
s.s.	sensu stricto
syn	synonym
TAHV	Ťahyňa virus
TL	Tulcea (County)
UK	United Kingdom
USA	Unites States of America
US	Unites States
VEEV	Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus
VBD	Vector-borne disease
VG	heterozygote allele
VSSC	voltage-sensitive sodium channel
VV	wild-type allele
WEEV	Western equine encephalomyelitis virus
WHO	World Health Organization

WNV	West Nile virus
YFV	yellow fever virus
ZIKV	Zika virus
μl	microliter
μM	micromole

1. Introduction

1.1. General Introduction

Mosquitoes can be found throughout the world, except for those places that are continuously covered in ice and weather conditions are not favourable enough for them to complete their life cycle. Interestingly, mosquitoes are most abundant in the Arctic tundra, where during the short summer period thousands of mosquitoes emerge and swarm at the same time. However, three-quarters of all the mosquito species live in the humid tropical and subtropical regions, where the warm and moist climate is favourable for rapid development cycles and adult survival, having several generations per year (REITER, 2001). A warm and humid environment is perfect for maintaining mosquito populations and also the diversity of habitats permits the evolution of the species. The feeding habits of mosquitoes are the same as for other hematophagous (blood-feeding) insects: only the female takes blood meals (but they also feed on flower nectar and other sugary plant juices as well) while the males are solely nectar feeders (ELDRIDGE AND EDMAN, 2012). Mosquitoes often cause a nuisance around households or in open areas, but most importantly they have a negative impact on public health and on livestock or poultry production; economically important mosquitoes can trigger a reduction in real estate values, and also affect tourism. Mosquitoes are likely to adapt fast to new environments and the changing climate thanks to their ecological plasticity and resistance (BECKER ET AL., 2010; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). Some species have the ability to adapt to more severe climatic conditions and have developed special physiological and behavioural mechanisms, e.g. producing eggs that are resistant to cold and desiccation, some eggs could survive for at least 5 years in severe drought conditions (MOGI, 1996; BECKER ET AL., 2010). Most species are more active during the crepuscular period (early morning and late evening), but there are diurnal species like *Ae. albopictus*, whose host-seeking activity is not tied to a particular time of the day. Some species are active throughout the year; during winter the imago frequently takes shelter indoors, they even take blood meals from time to time, but usually do not lay eggs; in general, their activity and reproductive window are considered from late winter- early spring to late autumn in temperate climatic conditions. They are ectothermic insects, which means that they are active if the environment's temperature is 4°C at lowest (embryonic development and hatching) and 38°C at maximum, but even temperatures below the freezing point would not kill a diapausing egg or a hibernating larva (REINHOLD ET AL, 2018; BECKER ET AL, 2010).

Invasive mosquito species (IMS) are an increasing worldwide public health concern, as the climate crisis, globalization and human activities further facilitate their

spread. We refer to ‘invasive’ species as those introduced from different niches (non-native) - mostly via anthropogenic movements and activities, with great potential for establishment and to produce impacts on native mosquito populations, as well as on the local ecosystem (decline of biodiversity), on human activities (economic losses), or on human and animal welfare (LOUNIBOS, 2002; JULIANO AND LOUNIBOS, 2005). These IMS are often vectors of mosquito-borne diseases (MBD), causing serious epidemics mostly in tropical regions. These vectors are mainly associated with exotic pathogens, therefore their impact on human health remains a top priority when investigating MBDs.

Currently, in Europe five invasive *Aedes* mosquito species are of concern (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2013a): *Aedes aegypti*, *Ae. albopictus*, *Ae. atropalpus*, *Ae. japonicus*, and *Ae. koreicus*. These species are susceptible to transmit several arboviruses like Zika (ZIKV), dengue (DENV)-, chikungunya (CHIKV)-, yellow fever virus (YFV), Eastern Equine encephalitis (EEEV), Venezuelan Equine encephalitis (VEEV), Japanese encephalitis (JEV), La Crosse virus (LCV), West Nile Virus (WNV), and filariae such as *Dirofilaria immitis* and *D. repens* (PAUPY ET AL., 2009; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). The rapid expansion of these IMS raises awareness of the autochthonous spreading of exotic diseases as well as the elevated level of epidemics caused by MBDs. Constant monitoring of IMS and implementation of mosquito control (MC) activities could help us to prevent the further spread of MBD-related epidemics throughout Europe, as the rapid expansion of IMS together with the ever-growing globalization and the current climatic crisis puts considerable pressure on public health systems.

1.2. Taxonomy of mosquitoes

Mosquitoes are the most medically important arthropods, belonging to the family of nematocericid flies (Diptera, Nematocera: Culicidae, - MEIGEN, 1818) with approximately 3,611 species worldwide, classified in two subfamilies (Culicinae and Anophelinae) and 113 genera (HARBACH, 2021, <http://mosquito-taxonomic-inventory.info>). The family of Culicidae (derived from “*culex*”, the Latin name for “gnat”) is a large and abundant group which occurs throughout temperate and tropical regions of the world. They are one of the most primitive families of Diptera, resembling crane flies (family Tipulidae) and chironomid flies (non-biting midges, family Chironomidae). They are more closely related to Culicoides (biting midges), Sciaridae (gnats) and Tipulidae (crane flies) e.g. than to Muscidae (houseflies) or the Calliphoridae (blowflies) (HARBACH AND KITCHING, 2016; COURTNEY ET AL., 2017; HARBACH, 2021).

Classification of Culicidae (subfamily/ subgenus) after BECKER ET AL., (2010):

Subfamily Anophelinae

Genus *Anopheles* (*An.*)

Subgenera *Anopheles*, *Baimaia*, *Cellia*, *Kerteszia*,
Lophopodomyia, *Nyssorhynchus*, *Stethomyia*

Genus *Bironella* (*Bi.*)

Subgenera *Bironella*, *Brugella*, *Neobironella*

Genus *Chagasia* (*Ch.*)

Subfamily Culicinae

Tribus Aedeomyiini

Genus *Aedeomyia* (*Ad.*)

Subgenera: *Aedeomyia*, *Lepiothauma*

Tribus Aedini

Tribus Culicini

Genus *Culex* (*Cx.*)

Subgenera *Acalleoemyia*, *Acallyntrum*, *Aedinus*, *Afrocolex*,
Allimanta, *Anoedioporpa*, *Barraudius*, *Belkinomyia*,
Carrollia, *Culex*, *Culiciomyia*, *Eumelanomyia*,
Kitzmilleria, *Lasiosiphon*, *Lophoceraomyia*, *Maillotia*,
Melanoconion, *Micraedes*, *Microcolex*, *Neoculex*,
Nicaromyia, *Oculeomyia*, *Phenacomyia*,
Phytotelmatomyia, *Sirivanakarnius*, *Tinolestes*

Genus *Deinocerites* (*De.*)

Genus *Galindomyia* (*Ga.*)

Genus *Lutzia* (*Lt.*)

Subgenera *Insulalutzia*, *Lutzia*, *Metalutzia*

Tribus Culisetini

Genus *Culiseta* (*Cs.*)

Subgenera *Allotheobaldia*, *Austrotheobaldia*, *Climacura*,
Culicella, *Culiseta*, *Neotheobaldia*, *Theomyia*

Tribus Ficalbiini

Genus *Ficalbia* (*Fi.*)

Genus *Mimomyia* (*Mi.*)

Subgenera *Etorleptiomyia*, *Ingramia*, *Mimomyia*

Tribus Hodgesiini

Genus *Hodgesia* (*Ho.*)

Tribus Mansoniini**Genus** *Coquillettidia* (Cq.)**Subgenera** *Austromansonia*, *Coquillettidia*, *Rhynchoetaenia***Genus** *Mansonia* (Ma.)**Subgenera** *Mansonia*, *Mansonioides***Tribus** Orthopodomyiini**Genus** *Orthopodomyia* (Or.)**Tribus** Sabethini**Genus** *Isostomyia* (Is.)**Genus** *Johnbelkinia* (Jb.)**Genus** *Kimia* (Km.)**Genus** *Limatus* (Li.)**Genus** *Malaya* (Ml.)**Genus** *Maorigoeldia* (Mg.)**Genus** *Onirion* (On.)**Genus** *Runchomyia* (Ru.)**Subgenera** *Ctenogoeldia*, *Runchomyia***Genus** *Sabethes* (Sa.)**Subgenera** *Davismyia*, *Peytonulus*, *Sabethes*, *Sabethinus*,
*Sabethoides***Genus** *Shannoniana* (Sh.)**Genus** *Topomyia* (To.)**Subgenera** *Suaymyia*, *Topomyia***Genus** *Trichoprosopon* (Tr.)**Genus** *Tripteroides* (Tp.)**Subgenera** *Polylepidomyia*, *Rachionotomyia*, *Rachisoura*,
Tricholeptomyia, *Tripteroides***Genus** *Wyeomyia* (Wy.)**Subgenera** *Antunesmyia*, *Caenomyiella*, *Cruzmyia*, *Decamyia*,
Dendromyia, *Dodecamyia*, *Exallomyia*, *Hystatamyia*,
Menolepis, *Nunezia*, *Phoniomyia*, *Prosopolepis*,
Spilonympha, *Wyeomyia*, *Zinzala***Tribus** Toxorhynchitini**Genus** *Toxorhynchites* (Tx.)**Subgenera** *Afrorhynchus*, *Ankylorhynchus*, *Lynchiella*,
*Toxorhynchites***Tribus** Uranotaeniini**Genus** *Uranotaenia* (Ur.)**Subgenera** *Pseudoficalbia*, *Uranotaenia*

1. 3. Biology and ecology of the mosquitoes

1.3.1. Morphology of mosquitoes

Mosquitoes are a group of flies with a slender segmented body portioned to the head, thorax and abdomen with a pair of wings, and three pairs of legs (fore-, mid- and hind legs, one pair on each thoracic segment). The legs have six segments, the coxa, trochanter, femur, tibia, pretarsus and tarsus (with five tarsomeres) ending in little claws.

Mosquitoes can be easily distinguished from all other members of Nematocera because they have an elongated, scaled mouthpart called the proboscis. It is located on the head together with a pair of annulated (segmented) antennae-, maxillary palps (which are hairy and as long-, or longer than the proboscis in the case of male mosquitoes) and a pair of compound eyes. The proboscis is a tube-like mouthpart, made from the labium which holds together the piercing stylets (labroepipharynx, hypopharynx, and a pair of both maxillae and mandibles), and it is always longer than the thorax, about half as long as the mosquito's body. It is used to perforate the skin of the host and for bloodsucking (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

The head, thorax, and abdomen are extensively covered with distinct coloured and shaped scales and setae; the legs, wing margins, and wing veins are typically covered with scales, that can form patches and patterns. The portion of the coverage (patches) and the colour of the scales are genus-specific, as well as the presence or absence of the setae and spiracle at specific body parts, like the thorax or the scutum. The thorax consists of three segments: the prothorax, mesothorax and metathorax, from which only the mesothorax is fully developed. It consists of four main regions: the dorsal tergum, ventral sternum and the two lateral pleurae. The abdomen consists of eleven segments, in males, the ninth segment holds the reproductive apparatus, the hypopygium, meanwhile, the females have a short, modified structure, the cerci, attached to the eleventh segment, which has a role in ovipositing (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Only the female mosquito takes blood meals, which contain proteins that are needed to produce eggs. Only a few autogenous species such as *Cx. p. pipiens* biotype *molestus* or *Aedes atropalpus* can produce their first egg batch without a blood meal, as well as females from the Toxorhynchitinae genus, who only feed on plant juices (BEIER ET AL., 1983; CLEMENTS, 1992; BECKER ET AL., 2010). Thousands of mosquito species feed on the blood of various hosts ☐— vertebrates: including

mammals, birds, reptiles, amphibians, and some fish; or on other invertebrates (primarily other arthropods) (LYIMO AND FERGUSON, 2009; BECKER ET AL., 2010). Males feed on sugary plant juices and nectar as a source of energy. Like other Diptera, mosquitoes are holometabolous insects, they develop through complete metamorphosis. This means that the juvenile form passes through both larval and pupal stages before emerging into an adult. The larvae are anatomically different from the adults, live in aquatic habitats and feed on different types of food (mostly algae, decaying matter or other insect's larvae). Transformation into adult mosquito takes place during the non-feeding pupal stage (CLEMENTS, 1992).

1.3.2. Life cycle

Most species are multivoltine, having multiple generations per year, they exhibit complete metamorphosis and their life cycle consists of four stages: egg, larva, pupa, and adult (Figure 1). Eggs are laid on the water surface, or very close to the water surface in the moist surroundings; after the eggs hatch into larvae they start to feed on algae and organic material. Larvae pass through four instars (L1, L2, L3, L4) and transform into pupae, where the fully developed adult will emerge from the mature pupae and the transformation will be completed (CLEMENTS, 1992).

The first three developmental stages—egg, larva, and pupa—are largely aquatic, the larvae and the pupae develop strictly in the water. The larval stages typically last 5 to 14 days, depending on the species and the climatic conditions of the surroundings; when the temperature drops below freezing point, or there is not enough water for the eggs to hatch, the eggs will enter in diapause; under cold conditions, larvae will decrease their metabolism, development and activity and remain in a hibernating state; inside the egg, the embryo will delay its development, even for months until there is enough water or warmth for their needs (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

In some mosquito species, adult females can overwinter as well while hibernating. Usually, they seek shelter indoors and wait until climatic conditions are optimal for them to leave. Some species take occasionally blood meals to endure this period (for ex. *Anopheles Maculipennis* Complex -AMC) but in general, before entering hibernation, females will feed on plant juices to fill up their reserves (CLEMENTS, 1992).

The adult mosquito emerges from the mature pupa. Depending on species, sex, and weather conditions, their potential adult life span is ranging from a few days to several months (CLEMENTS, 1992; BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Figure 1: Life cycle of mosquitoes: a) egg stage, b) larval stage, c) pupal stage, d) adult stage (Source: ELDRIDGE AND EDMAN, 2012)

1.3.2.1. Adults

Newly emerged adult mosquitoes are ready to begin their life cycle again, which consists of mating, feeding and oviposition of the eggs. Just a few minutes after the emergence, adults are able to fly as soon as the soft cuticle has hardened and sclerotized. Mosquitoes that have just emerged from the pupal cuticle are not fully formed adults, they are still undergoing several maturation processes, where many of their organs continue to develop for a period of hours, even days, e.g., the salivary

glands grow in size during the first days of adult life, and in case of the male mosquitoes, the reproductive organs will rotate 180° to become fully functional, therefore, the males in the same population usually emerge 1–2 days before the females in order to achieve sexual maturity at the same time. Other dimorphisms are observable between sexes, e.g. in the structure of gonads, and their physical appearance- males have hairy antennae and maxillary palps, but they differ in body size as well- they are somewhat smaller than females (CLEMENTS, 1992; BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Usually, mating takes place soon after emergence. Following mating, the females will search for a host to obtain a blood meal. In almost every mosquito species, oogenesis can only be completed if the female mosquito feeds on blood since they need specific nutrients and proteins to create eggs, hence, females have developed a complex host-seeking behaviour to find potential hosts. The location of the host is based on a complex network of olfactory (kairomones, carbon dioxide, lactic acid, octenol, acetone, butanone and other phenolic compounds)-, visual- and thermal stimuli, which is realized with the help of the antennal receptors and the compound eyes that respond to these stimuli. After successfully locating the host, females would land on them and would pierce their skin with the help of the proboscis. While feeding, the female mosquito would inject its saliva into the host, which has an anaesthetic nature but also helps the blood to remain in a fluid state by preventing haemostasis and the aggregation of the red blood cells. The blood uptake can be 3 or 4 times the mosquito's weight. After ingesting the blood, the oocytes would start to develop into mature eggs within the ovarioles with the help of the freshly gained proteins; the process is completed when the female's search for a breeding site ends and the ovipositioning is done. Females can complete more than one gonotrophic cycle depending on how many times they fed and laid eggs (CLEMENTS, 1992; BECKER ET AL., 2010).

1.3.2.2. Eggs

Female mosquitoes usually lay between 50 - 500 eggs at one time after 2-4 days from ingesting the blood meal, depositing them on the water surface or on sites that later will be flooded. Mosquitoes lay their eggs singly or in egg rafts in many different habitats, such as swamps, marshes or pools, as well as in a great variety of small, natural, and artificial water collections, such as tree-holes, rock pools or man-made containers. Some females lay their eggs on the water surface, whereas others lay them on the moist soil surrounding the breeding site, on the edge of the water bodies or on the wall of containers, e.g., species of *Anopheles*, *Toxorhynchites*, *Sabethes* and *Wyeomyia* lay their eggs close to the water surface, while species from the genera

Culex, *Coquillettidia* and *Culiseta* lay egg batches on the water surface. Species from the genus *Aedes/Ochlerotatus* and *Psorophora* lay their eggs on the moist ground, in the vegetation and in substrates which later will be flooded (SILVER, 2007).

The eggs are nearly always elongated along the posterior-anterior axis and are covered with a protective layer called eggshell (chorion), which is differently sculpted by each species. Eggshells are always soft and white when laid, but they harden and darken within a few hours, at the same time it becomes less permeable to water. The embryonic development starts immediately after the eggs are deposited. Within one or two days to a week, or more- depending on the temperature, the embryo develops into fully formed larvae. The length of time required is dependent almost entirely on temperature, e.g. at a temperature of 30°C the *Cx. p. pipiens* larvae hatch after 1 day as the eggs are deposited, at 20°C it takes 3 days-, while at 10°C it takes approximately 10 days for the egg to hatch. At 4°C, the embryonic development of the *Cx. p. pipiens* is completely inhibited (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Mosquitoes of the *Aedes*, *Psorophora*, *Opifex* and *Haemagogus* genera have desiccation-resistant eggs, fully-formed but unhatched larvae can survive inside the eggshells for months, or even years without free water. The diapause is induced therefore when the climatic and hydrological conditions are unfavourable for the larval development. Several species have evolved to produce diapausing eggs, mostly from *Aedes/Ochlerotatus* genera. If the conditions are suitable for their needs, the dormant eggs will start to develop embryos and soon the first instar larvae will hatch. For them to hatch several stimuli are required, e.g., if previously eggs were dried, they have to submerge once again in water, the temperature of the water is also an important factor, as well as the organic compounds found in water; oxygen levels and the water movement can also stimulate the egg hatching. Freshly hatched larvae can survive in moist surroundings without being submerged in water for several days (CLEMENTS, 1992; BECKER AT AL., 2010).

1.3.2.3. Larvae

Mosquito larvae can be easily distinguished from other aquatic insects/ larvae because they lack legs, their head is ornamented with a pair of mouth brushes and antennae; behind the head is the thorax which is wider than the head and the abdomen. They have a segmented abdomen, which usually ends in a terminal syphon (subfamily Culicinae), or in a pair of modified respiratory openings allowing them to stay attached to aquatic plants, totally submerged (genus *Mansonia* and *Coquillettidia*) while gaining oxygen from the plant's aerenchyma. The abdomen is composed of ten segments, of which seven are almost identical and the last three are modified posterior segments. The abdomen is ornamented with setae, whose

placement and structure are very important from a taxonomic point of view (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

The larval habitats usually differ from species to species, they can be small, shallow or large water bodies, permanent or temporary flooded areas, with little or no water movement – typically shallow pools, river stream edges with vegetation coverage, marshes and swamps, rock pools, phytotelmata like water-filled tree holes or leaf axils; man-made containers, plant pots, cemetery vases, tyres and rainwater drains. Most species live in freshwater, but some species are adapted to live in saline or brackish water, or in saline marshes (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Mosquito larvae are omnivores, their mixed diet provides the proteins necessary for growth and also the vitamins, nucleotides and sterol, that are essential for metabolism and development. The characteristic food resource of mosquito larvae is the organic matter, this includes aquatic microorganisms, such as bacteria, protozoa, diatoms and algae, particles of detritus from decayed plant tissues and small invertebrates. Depending on their feeding style, larvae can be filter feeders, browsers or predators. Filter feeder larvae can move slowly in the water column while filtering the water, browsers would spend more time submerged skimming the bottom of the breeding sites. Anophelinae larvae usually feed close to the water surface, just below the surface membrane in the particle-rich layer, meanwhile, Culicinae larvae mostly feed on particles suspended in the water column, but there are predators like larvae from the Toxorhynchitinae genus, that are preying on smaller invertebrates or on other mosquito species' larvae (BECKER ET AL., 2010). Mosquito larvae pass through four instars (L1, L2, L3 and L4), they moult four times at each stage of their development. Identification of the larvae is best at fully grown fourth instar larvae. The length of their development is influenced by several factors: environmental conditions such as the water temperature and day/night routine (photoperiodic sensitivity); the nutrition of the larvae, but it can differ from species to species (BENEDICT ET AL., 1996).

Some mosquitoes are known to overwinter in the larval stage and can even survive for days in breeding sites with a frozen surface. During the cold season, their metabolism is reduced and larval development is delayed (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

1.3.2.4. Pupae

The pupa is strictly an aquatic organism, the last developmental stage of the mosquito before it reaches the fully-grown adult form.

The body of the pupa resembles a sphere with an elongated abdominal part to which two paddles are attached; the body consists of the cephalothorax, which is the head and the thorax combined, and a much narrow segmented abdomen with nine segments where the paddles are attached, which helps the larvae to make quick

manoeuvres in the water and to swim. The pupa usually floats on the water surface, the top of its thorax in contact with the surface membrane of the water, where two respiratory tubes- syphons are connected to the air in order to help the pupae breathe (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

The pupal stage of the two sexes is more or less about the same length, but there is a difference in sizes between male and female pupae, usually, females are somewhat bigger (BECKER ET AL., 2010). From a taxonomic point of view, it is easier to rear the pupae into adults to identify the species.

During the pupal stage, the body of the adult mosquito is formed, some larval organs will disappear and are replaced with adult organs. This final stage of the metamorphosis can be completed within one or two days. Unlike larvae, pupae do not feed. When the adult is fully formed, the pupae will start to swallow air, which will increase the internal pressure of the cuticle, allowing the membrane to hatch open, and the adult mosquito will start to slowly expand out of the pupal skin and step on the water's surface. The emergence from pupae to adults depends on the mosquito species and environmental conditions (BENEDICT ET AL., 1996; CLEMENTS, 1992).

1.4. Mosquito species in Europe

1.4.1 Native species

1.4.1.1. General overview

Mosquitoes are inhabiting several types of biomes, from the Arctic tundra to the humid tropics, with more than 3,600 species worldwide, from which more than 100 species can be found in Europe. They can adapt fast to changing conditions, therefore they occupy different kinds of niches, swampy woodlands, salty marshes, freshwater, canals, lagoons, or more urbanistic areas where they use man-made containers as breeding habitats. They cause nuisance along these sites which mostly are in close proximity to human settlements. The most widely distributed and most common mosquito, the *Culex pipiens pipiens*, known as the "house mosquito" is causing a nuisance in the temperate zones, while the closely related *Cx. p. quinquefasciatus* occurs mainly in the tropics; the floodwater mosquitoes, like *Aedes vexans*, or *Ochlerotatus sticticus* are a common nuisance along river streams worldwide. Snow-melt mosquitoes, such as the *Oc. cantans*, *Oc. communis*, *Oc.*

punctor and *Oc. cataphylla*, breed in swampy woodlands and tundra areas. In brackish or salt water habitats are breeding species such as *Oc. caspius* and *Oc. detritus*; *Oc. geniculatus*, *Ae. cretinus*, *Anopheles plumbeus* and *Orthopodomyia pulcripalpis* often inhabit tree holes and other phytotelmata.

Different species' larvae often can be found in the same breeding habitat living together (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

1.4.1.1.1. Species in Romania

In Romania, there are 61 mosquito species, divided into 7 genera: *Aedes* (29 species), *Anopheles* (10 species), *Coquillettidia* (2 species), *Culex* (10 species), *Culiseta* (8 species), *Orthopodomyia* (1 species) and *Uranotaenia* (1 species) (TÖRÖK ET AL., 2018; HORVÁTH ET AL., 2021).

Systematics of the Romanian mosquito fauna:

Subfamily Anophelinae, GRASSI, 1900

Genus *Anopheles*, MEIGEN, 1818

Subgenus *Anopheles*, MEIGEN, 1818

- *algeriensis* (THEOBALD, 1903)
- *atroparvus* (VAN THIEL, 1927)
- *claviger* (MEIGEN, 1804)
- *daciae* (LINTON, NICOLESCU AND HARBACH, 2004)
- *hyrcanus* (PALLAS, 1771)
- *maculipennis* (MEIGEN, 1818)
- *melanoon* (HACKETT, 1934)
- *messeae* (FALLERONI, 1926)
- *plumbeus* (STEPHENS, 1828)
- *sacharovi* (FAVRE, 1903)

Subfamily Culicinae, MEIGEN, 1818

Tribe Aedini, NEVEU-LEMAIRE, 1902

Genus *Aedes*, MEIGEN, 1818

Subgenus *Acartomyia*, THEOBALD, 1903

- *zammitii* (THEOBALD, 1903)

Subgenus *Aedes*, MEIGEN, 1818

- *cinereus* (MEIGEN, 1818)
- *geminus* (PEUS, 1970)
- *rossicus* (DOLBESKIN, GORICKAJA AND MITROFANOVA, 1930)

Subgenus *Stegomyia*, THEOBALD, 1901

- *albopictus* (SKUSE, 1895)

Subgenus *Finlaya*, THEOBALD, 1901

- *japonicus japonicus* (THEOBALD, 1901), [s.s *Hulecoeteomyia japonica*] (REINERT ET AL., 2006)

Subgenus *Aedimorphus*, THEOBALD, 1903

- *vexans* (MEIGEN, 1830)

Subgenus *Dahlia*, REINERT, HARBACH AND KITCHING, 2006

- *geniculatus* (OLIVIER, 1791)

Genus *Ochlerotatus*, LYNCH ARRIBÁLZAGA, 1891

Subgenus *Woodius*, REINERT, HARBACH AND KITCHING, 2009

- *intrudens* (DYAR, 1919)

Subgenus *Ochlerotatus*, LYNCH ARRIBÁLZAGA, 1891

- *annulipes* (MEIGEN, 1830)
- *behningi* (MARTINI, 1926)
- *cantans* (MEIGEN, 1818)
- *caspicus* (PALLAS, 1771)
- *cataphylla* (DYAR, 1916)
- *communis* (DE GEER, 1776)
- *detritus* (HALIDAY, 1833)
- *dorsalis* (MEIGEN, 1830)

- *duplex** (MARTINI, 1926)
- *excrucians* (WALKER, 1856)
- *flavescens* (MULLER, 1764)
- *hungaricus* (MIHÁLYI, 1955)
- *leucomelas* (MEIGEN, 1804)
- *nigrinus* (ECKSTEIN, 1918)
- *pulcritarsis* (RONDANI, 1872)
- *pullatus* (COQUILLET, 1904)
- *punctor* (KIRBY, 1837)
- *riparius* (DYAR AND KNAB, 1907)
- *sticticus* (MEIGEN, 1838)

Subgenus *Rusticooidus*, SHEVCHENKO AND PRUDKINA, 1973

- *refiki* (MEDSCHID, 1928)

Tribe Culicini, MEIGEN, 1818

Genus *Culex*, LINNAEUS, 1758

Subgenus *Barraudius*, EDWARDS, 1921

- *modestus* (FICALBI, 1890)

Subgenus *Culex*, LINNAEUS, 1758

- *impudicus* (FICALBI, 1890)
- *laticinctus* (EDWARDS, 1913)
- *mimeticus* (NOE, 1899)
- *pipiens* (LINNAEUS, 1758)
- *theileri* (THEOBALD, 1903)
- *torrentium* (MARTINI, 1925)

Subgenus *Neoculex*, DYAR, 1905

- *martinii* (MEDSCHID, 1930)

- *territans* (WALKER, 1856)

Subgenus *Maillotia*, THEOBALD, 1907

- *hortensis* (FICALBI, 1889)

Tribe Culisetini, BELKIN, 1962

Genus *Culiseta*, FELT, 1904

Subgenus *Allotheobaldia*, BROLEMANN, 1919

- *longiareolata* (MACQUART, 1938)

Subgenus *Culiseta*, FELT, 1904

- *alaskaensis* (LUDLOW, 1906)
- *annulata* (SCHRANK, 1776)
- *fumipennis* (STEPHENS, 1825)
- *glaphyroptera* (SCHINER, 1864)
- *morsitans* (THEOBALD, 1901)
- *subochrea* (EDWARDS, 1921)

Subgenus *Culicella*, FELT, 1904

- *ochroptera* (PEUS, 1935)

Tribe Mansoniini, BELKIN, 1962

Genus *Coquillettidia*, DYAR, 1905

- *buxtoni* (EDWARDS, 1923)
- *richiardii* (FICALBI, 1889)

Tribus Orthopodomyiini, BELKIN, HEINEMANN AND PAGE, 1970

Genus *Orthopodomyia*, THEOBALD, 1904

- *pulcripalpis* (RONDANI, 1872)

Tribus Uranotaeniini, LAHILLE, 1904

Genus *Uranotaenia*, LYNCH ARRIBÁLZAGA, 1891

- *unguiculata* (EDWARDS, 1913)

1.4.1.1.2. Short presentation of the mosquito species of Romania

The rich mosquito fauna of Romania is not equally divided per region. In the DDBR for example, 31 species can be found, due to the climatic conditions and the nature of habitats, since nearly 30 types of ecosystems can be found there (PRIOTEASA AND FĂLCUȚĂ, 2010). The Carpathian arc with its moderate temperature and the lack of suitable habitats for mosquitoes can be a strict breeding site for many species, but the high land species like mosquitoes from *Aedes* and *Ochlerotatus* genera are present in many areas. The low land areas with its suitable habitats and climate conditions are also used by mosquitoes.

The genus *Anopheles* is represented by 10 species in Romania.

Anopheles algeriensis (THEOBALD, 1903) was collected in Algeria for the first time, now it has a large distribution through Europe (mostly in the Mediterranean), Middle-East and North Africa. It closely resembles *An. claviger* (MEIGEN, 1804). Larvae can be found in freshwater, but also shows tolerance towards salty- brackish water; it overwinters mainly in larval form (BECKER ET AL., 2010; TIPPELT ET AL., 2018).

Its vectorial capacity is high and it is considered a secondary vector of malaria; It feeds both on animals and humans, but it is characterized as strongly exophilic (BECKER ET AL., 2010). This species was recorded in Romania for the first time in the DDBR, close to Sulina (TÖRÖK ET AL., 2016).

Anopheles atroparvus (VAN THIEL, 1927) is a widespread species in Europe, it prefers coastal habitats but also it can be found in freshwater. Females can be hardly distinguished from other species in the *Anopheles maculipennis* complex (AMC), therefore molecular identification is advised; their eggs seem to be morphologically distinct from other species, as they have specifically patterned surfaces. They overwinter as adult females, but they are gonoactive all year round in Portugal (SOUSA, 2008). Females show a zoophilic feeding behaviour, but they bite humans as well (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

It causes a biting nuisance, and it is known to be involved in malaria-, WNV- and *Dirofilaria* sp. transmission in Europe (FILIPÉ, 1972; RAMOS ET AL., 1993; BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Anopheles claviger s.s. was first described by MEIGEN in 1804 as *Culex bifurcates*, and adult females can be easily confused with *An. plumbeus*. It is a member of the *Anopheles claviger* complex, together with its sibling species, the *Anopheles petragnani*. It is widely distributed in the Palearctic region, from Scandinavia to St. Petersburg, but it is found throughout of Europe, the Middle East and North Africa.

Larvae prefer clean water bodies, and it overwinters as L3-L4 stage larva, and it can form autogenous populations (RIOUX ET AL., 1975). It shows a zoophilic behaviour, with a preference mainly towards domestic animals, but will feed on humans as well.

It is well known as a principal malaria vector in the eastern Mediterranean region but also can transmit BATV and TAHV, although, its medical importance is negligible as it has a low abundance (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Anopheles daciae (LINTON, NICOLESCU AND HARBACH, 2004) belongs to the AMC. First, it was described by NICOLESCU in 2004, and it is an endemic species to Romania, but was reported in several European countries: Germany, Great Britain, Poland, Serbia, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Croatia, Russia, Finland, Sweden, Belgium and The Netherlands (WEITZEL ET AL., 2012; KRONEFELD ET AL., 2012; DANABALAN ET AL., 2014; RYDZANICZ ET AL., 2017; KAVRAN ET AL., 2018; BLAŽEJOVÁ ET AL., 2018; MERDIĆ ET AL., 2020; NAUMENKO ET AL., 2020; CULVERWELL ET AL., 2020; LILJA ET AL., 2020; SMITZ ET AL., 2021; IBÁÑEZ-JUSTICIA ET AL., 2022). In Romania, it was collected in the Black Sea's coastal region and plains adjacent to the Danube River in the southern part of the country. *An. daciae* is most similar to-, and sympatric with *An. messeae* but genetic studies confirmed the species' distinctiveness (NICOLESCU ET AL., 2004; NAUMENKO ET AL., 2020; LILJA ET AL., 2020).

Larvae can be found widespread in diverse breeding sites, and the adult feeds on various hosts. The species could be involved in malaria transmission (NICOLESCU ET AL., 2004)

Anopheles hyrcanus (PALLAS, 1771) is one of the most widespread and common species of the genus *Anopheles*; in Europe, it is widely distributed throughout the northern Mediterranean countries, from Spain, southern France, Italy, and Greece to Turkey. Together with closely related species from the *Anopheles hyrcanus* group, it is common in south-east Asia and its eastern distribution range includes China, Japan and Korea. Larvae can be found in stagnant or slowly moving, clean water bodies with dense vegetation It is considered to have an exophilic feeding habit, therefore it is not accorded with medical importance, although it might have the potential to transmit malaria (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Anopheles maculipennis s.s. (MEIGEN, 1818) is part of the AMC species complex, comprising various sibling species (*An. sacharovi*, *An. melanoon*, *An. atroparvus*, *An. subalpinus*, *An. labranchiae*, *An. messeae*, *An. beklemishevi*). There can be found morphological differences between these species (larvae, adults, eggs) but

differentiation on the species level is done using mostly molecular methods, as the morphological identification is still based largely on characteristics of the egg (markings of the dorsal exochorion, presence of floats and their size, position and texture). Members of this species group breed in different habitats, and are also differentiated in mating habits. The complex species are important vectors of malaria and MBDs like BATV, TAHV and WNV, *An. maculipennis* s.s. being a major vector for malaria (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Anopheles melanoon (HACKETT, 1934) belongs to the AMC; it can be found in south-western and southern Europe, but it is considered to have a limited distribution range compared to other members of the group. They may occur in marshes, edges of rivers and lakes, ponds, ground pools, rice fields, streams and water collections. Just like the other members of this complex, *An. melanoon* shows a zoophilic biting behaviour and has a preference towards cattle (BECKER ET AL., 2010). It is believed to have the potential to transmit malaria when it has a high abundance. In Romania, it was first found in 2003, near the Black Sea, in Herghelia Mangalia (NICOLESCU ET AL., 2004).

Anopheles messeae (FALLERONI, 1926) is the most widespread member of the *An. maculipennis* complex. It can be found in the northern Palearctic region and across northern and central Europe, as far as Asia.

The larvae are breeding in large, stagnant freshwater bodies and along river courses. Adult females hibernate throughout the winter. They show a zoophilic feeding preference, but are often found resting inside human buildings. It is not considered to be an important vector of MBDs (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Anopheles plumbeus (STEPHENS, 1828) appearance resembles to *An. claviger*, but it is smaller in size. It is known to be a persistent biter of humans. This species has been found in nearly all European countries, including Scandinavia and also in the western Himalayas. Larvae usually develop in water filled tree holes, but they may occur in artificial containers as well, due to their habitat preference they can be found in forests, or rural settlements; overwintering takes place in the egg or larval stage (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

It is suspected of having contributed to malaria transmission in the past and has been demonstrated to be a competent vector for both tropical and Eurasian strains of malaria, but it has minor medical importance (BLACKLOCK ET AL., 1920)

Anopheles sacharovi (FAVRE, 1903) is another member of the AMC. The species distribution is limited to south-eastern Europe, mainly in the coastal region of the

eastern Mediterranean. It uses coastal brackish habitats, river margins, swamps and irrigated land for rice as breeding sites. Overwinters in form of adult females, and they may take occasionally blood meals in this stage.

It is highly anthropophilic, and it is the third most important vector of the AMC of malaria across Europe and in Turkey (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

In the genus *Aedes/Ochlerotatus* 29 species are present in Romania:

Ochlerotatus zammitii (THEOBALD, 1903) syn. *Acartomyia zammiti* is a species from the *Mariae* complex together with *Oc. mariae* and *Oc. phoenicidae*. Closely resembles to *Oc. mariae* in all stages. Endemic to the Mediterranean basin, it has distribution in the Adriatic coasts, the eastern coast of Sicily, the whole Island of Malta, and the Ionian and Aegean coasts. Larvae usually can be found in rock pools alongside coastal regions, as larvae breed in saline water (BECKER ET AL., 2010). In Romania, it was first observed in 2006, in the DDBR (PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2010). It is not known to have vector potential.

Aedes cinereus (MEIGEN, 1818) is morphologically similar to *Ae. rossicus*, is widely distributed in the northern Holarctic region and in Europe. Larvae occur in a large range of habitats, from woodland to flood plains and marshes. Females principally feed on mammals and birds, but would readily feed on humans as well, therefore are considered bridge vector (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

It is known to be a vector for Ockelbo – (SINV subtype), TAHV, WNV and SINV (FRANCY ET AL., 1989; HUBÁLEK ET AL., 1999; ANDERSON ET AL., 2006; LUNDSTRÖM ET AL., 2019).

Aedes geminus (PEUS, 1970) is a less known species and its vector potential is unknown. Morphologically very similar to *Ae. cinereus* but it's smaller in size and lighter in colouration. It shares the habitats with *Ae. cinereus*. It was found in England, north-western France, Germany, Poland, Czech Republic, the southern Sweden, and southern and eastern shores of the Baltic Sea (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2001; BECKER ET AL., 2010). Like any other floodwater mosquito, larvae can be found in marshes and ponds (MEDLOCK AND VAUX, 2009).

Aedes rossicus (DOLBESKIN, GORICKAJA AND MITROFANOVA, 1930) is another floodwater mosquito, females are aggressive daytime bitters and readily attack humans. It occurs in western Europe as far as the Atlantic Ocean; it was recorded in Sweden, Norway, France, Germany, Hungary, the Czech Republic, territory of the former Yugoslavia, Ukraine, the northern part of the Caucasus and in the Ural. Overwinters in form of eggs (BECKER ET AL., 2010). Like its closely related sibling

species *Ae. cinereus*, *Ae. rossicus* also acts as a bridge vector. It is susceptible to WNV and SINV (HUBÁLEK ET AL., 2010; LUNDSTRÖM ET AL., 2019).

Aedes (Stegomyia) albopictus (SKUSE, 1895) syn. *Stegomyia albopicta* (see more at the invasive species - Chapter 1.4.2.1.);

Aedes japonicus japonicus (THEOBALD, 1901), [s.s. *Hulecoeteomyia japonica*] (REINERT ET AL., 2006) (see more at the invasive species - Chapter 1.4.2.4.);

Aedes (Aedimorphus) vexans (MEIGEN, 1830) syn. *Aedimorphus vexans*, is a common floodwater mosquito species in Romania. It breeds in inundated areas, temporary water bodies and lakes. It is a multivoltine species with several generations per year. It is a very aggressive species, causing a great nuisance, feeding mostly on human blood; it can transmit LACV, WEE, EEE, CE, RVFV, TAHV and WNV, and potential vector for ZIKV, *D. immitis* and *D. repens* (BURKOT ET AL., 1982; HUBÁLEK, 2008; BECKER ET AL., 2010; YILDIRIM ET AL., 2011; RUDOLF ET AL., 2014; O'DONNELL ET AL., 2017; BIRNBERG ET AL., 2019).

Ochlerotatus (Finlaya) geniculatus (OLIVIER, 1791) syn. *Dahlia geniculata* has a Palearctic distribution range, widely dispersed in most European countries, in the Mediterranean region, North Africa and in Asia Minor. They prefer tree holes as breeding sites. Females are daytime and crepuscular feeders and they aggressively bite humans (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

They can transmit CHIKV, and susceptible for *D. immitis* and *D. repens* infection (SILAGHI ET AL., 2017; PRUDHOMME ET AL., 2019)

Ochlerotatus intrudens s.s. (DYAR, 1919) belongs to a species group, together with *Oc. diantaeus* and *Oc. pullatus*. It has a Holarctic distribution range, occurring from the central part of Europe to the northern, from the steppe to the taiga. It is a monocyclic species; it overwinters in form of eggs. Larvae breed in temporary water bodies and can be found right after snow melt. It is not known to have vector potential (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Ochlerotatus annulipes s.s. (MEIGEN, 1830) is a species from the Annulipes group together with *Oc. behningi*, *Oc. cantans*, *Oc. cyprius*, *Oc. euedes*, *Oc. excrucians*, *Oc. flavescens*, *Oc. mercurator*, *Oc. riparius*, *Oc. surcoufi*.

It is a widespread mosquito being most abundant in central Europe. Just like *Oc. intrudens*, it is a monocyclic species occurring during springtime. Larvae breed in a sylvatic environment in semi-permanent water bodies and are often found together with *Oc. cantans* larvae. Females are day-time biters but also show crepuscular

activity (BECKER ET AL., 2010). It is known to be a vector for TAHV (LUNDSTRÖM, 1999), and susceptible to transmit malaria (experimental) (ROBERTS, 1943).

Ochlerotatus behningi (MARTINI, 1926) belongs to the Annulipes group (species included in the group are: *Oc. annulipes*, *Oc. cantans*, *Oc. cyprius*, *Oc. euedes*, *Oc. excrucians*, *Oc. flavescens*, *Oc. mercurator*, *Oc. riparius*, *Oc. surcoufi*). It is an early summer species and it is considered to be monocyclic. Knowledge is scarce about its general biology, vector potential and distribution. It was reported to occur in eastern Europe (Ukraine, Russia, Slovakia, Poland) (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Ochlerotatus cantans (MEIGEN, 1818) is another species from the Annulipes group, and it has a western Palearctic distribution. Larvae can be found from early spring until late spring/ early summer, but it is predominantly univoltine, and it has diapausing eggs. Day-time biter, it feeds on humans and other mammals, therefore it has medical importance, due to Flaviviruses (WNV) and Bunya virus (TAHV) have been isolated from them (LABUDA ET AL., 1974; LUNDSTRÖM, 1994; LUNDSTRÖM, 1999; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2005; BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Ochlerotatus caspius (PALLAS, 1771) syn. *Ae. caspius*, is a species from another complex called the Caspius group together with *Oc. berlandi*, *Oc. dorsalis*, *Oc. mariae*, *Oc. pulcritarsis* and *Oc. zammitii*.

Both the larval and adult form of this species is very similar to *Oc. dorsalis*. It is a polycyclic mosquito, with distribution in the Palearctic region, from Europe to Mongolia, China, Africa and Asia. It is a halophilous species (preferring brackish- or saltwater habitats) and larvae breed in shallow lagoons along coastal areas. The species is an aggressive biter and can transmit WNV, TAHV and *Francisella tularensis* which is the causative agent of tularaemia; it is susceptible to transmit RVFV (TURELL ET AL., 1996; BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Ochlerotatus cataphylla (DYAR, 1916) syn. *Ae. cataphylla* is univoltine species, with breeding sites in the swampy woodlands. It has a Holarctic origin with distribution in Eurasia, North America and from northern (tundra) to southern Europe. It is a daytime biter and can cause a nuisance in sylvatic areas (BECKER ET AL., 2010). It is known to be susceptible to JCV (HARDY ET AL., 1993).

Ochlerotatus communis (DE GEER, 1776) is part of the *Ochlerotatus communis* complex, with three sibling species: *Oc. nevadensis*, *Oc. tahoensis*, and *Oc. churchillensis* (KIRIK ET AL., 2020). *Oc. Communis* is a snow-melt mosquito, it has activity in the early spring. It produces one generation per year, with breeding sites

in the swampy forests. The species is found from northern Europe to the Mediterranean area, in the Holarctic region, North America, and Eurasia (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

It is known to carry SINV, BATV, *F. tularensis*, *D. repens*, TAHV and CEV (MCLEAN ET AL., 1973; L'VOV ET AL., 1985; FRANCY ET AL., 1989; LUNDSTRÖM ET AL., 2011; TINGSTRÖM ET AL., 2016; SHAIKEVICH ET AL., 2019).

Ochlerotatus detritus (HALIDAY, 1833) forms a species group together with *Oc. coluzzi* (RIOUX, 1998). It is a Palearctic species, with distribution along most of the European coastlines, around the Mediterranean basin, and the Northern and Baltic Sea, in Africa and Asia. It is a multivoltine species; hibernation takes place in form of eggs and larvae. It is a halophile species with crepuscular activity (BECKER ET AL., 2010). It mostly feeds on birds and cattle, but would readily bite humans as well, acting as a potential bridge vector for zoonotic arboviruses. It is known to have a vector capacity toward arboviruses like JEV and WNV (MACKENZIE-IMPOINVIL ET AL., 2015; BLAGROVE ET AL., 2016).

Ochlerotatus dorsalis (MEIGEN, 1830) syn. *Oc. melanimon* it is a widespread Holarctic halophilic species in Europe from Scandinavia to Greece, with a distribution range to central Asia, China, northern Russia, and North America. It has multiple generations per year. It breeds in temporarily flooded areas, and swamps. Females are aggressive biters, rarely they are capable of autogeny. It is known to transmit WEE, SLE, CE, JEV, and *F. tularensis* (MILANKOV ET AL., 2009; BECKER ET AL., 2010).

*Ochlerotatus duplex** syn. *Ae. duplex*, *Oc. caspius* is a highly discussed species because it was described based on only two male specimens captured in Russia by MARTINI in 1926, and since then there were no records of them. It is a member of the *Ochlerotatus caspius* complex; In Romania, the species was recorded from the North-western- and South-eastern Romanian Plain (NICOLESCU ET AL., 2003). Probably their presence was established upon an identification mistake made on damaged specimens. Many suggest that this species should not be considered as a distinct member of the *Ochlerotatus caspius* complex, but as a synonym for *Ochlerotatus caspius* (GOMOSTAEVA, 2000; KHALIN, 2008; BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Ochlerotatus excrucians (WALKER, 1856) is a Holarctic species, with distribution in Europe, North America, Canada and Alaska. It is part of the *Ochlerotatus excrucians* complex, together with *Oc. euedes*, *Oc. aloponotum* and *Oc. surcoufi*. The females are aggressive day biters. Their activity starts early in the spring, larvae can be found

in snowmelt pools, temporary water bodies and woodland ponds, and they are considered univoltine species. The species does not have medical importance, but it is believed to play a role in heartworm (*D. scapiceps*) transmission in rabbits in the US and was demonstrated to be susceptible to *D. immitis* infection, as well as to transmit Ockelbo virus (YEN, 1938; HIGHBY, 1943; TURELL ET AL., 1990; BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Ochlerotatus flavescens (MULLER, 1764) is a Holarctic species, occurring in Eurasia and North America. In Europe, it is widely distributed except for some countries in the Mediterranean region. It is considered to be univoltine species, producing only one generation per year; hibernates in form of eggs. Larvae are frequently found in brackish marshes along coasts, as they show high tolerance towards saline waters; females are active at crepuscular hours, and it feeds on livestock and humans. Little is known about its vector status, but it can be involved in WE transmission (SHELTLANCHUK, 1969; BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Ochlerotatus hungaricus (MIHÁLYI, 1955) has been reported from Austria, Slovakia, Hungary and Romania, and it is considered endemic to Hungary. Larvae are typically found in the floodplains of larger river systems like the Danube river. It is considered to be a multivoltine species. Females are aggressive biters and would feed during the day, but there is little known about this species' biology and their vector competence (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Ochlerotatus leucomelas (MEIGEN, 1804) has a distribution mainly throughout eastern and central Europe. It prefers woodland and flooded areas for breeding sites after snowmelt, but also occurs in saline water; it is considered to be a monocyclic species. Knowledge about its vector status is scarce (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Ochlerotatus nigrinus (ECKSTEIN, 1918) has a Holarctic distribution range (Southern Scandinavia, Finland, Denmark, Germany, France, Poland, Estonia, the northern Urals western Siberia and England) and it is closely related and very similar in appearance to *Oc. sticticus*. Preferably breeds in open areas, flooded meadows, and swamps along river courses (BECKER ET AL., 2010; HARBACH ET AL., 2017).

Ochlerotatus pulcritarsis (RONDANI, 1872) has a Western Palearctic, Mediterranean distribution, but it can be found in many countries from central Europe as well; it is a multivoltine species. It uses tree holes and other phytotelmata as breeding sites. Females prefer an antropophilic environment, they feed on humans but presumably

on animals as well and will bite during daytime. So far there is no information about its vector status (BECKER ET AL., 2010; BAKRAN-LEBL ET AL., 2022).

Ochlerotatus pullatus (COQUILLET, 1904) is a northern Holarctic species, it prefers mountainous areas (up to 2000 m elevation), and arctic tundra. It is a monocylic species, it breeds in snow-melt pools, mountain streams and lakes, it hibernates in form of eggs; the females are aggressive biters any time of the day. It is not known to be a vector for MBDs (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Ochlerotatus punctor (KIRBY, 1837) is a species from a species group called *Ochlerotatus punctor* group, the species included in this complex are: *Oc. hexodontus*, *Oc. nigripes*, *Oc. punctor* and *Oc. punctodes*. It is a Holarctic species and it is widely distributed throughout North America and Eurasia. In Europe, it can be found from Scandinavia to the Mediterranean region (BECKER ET AL., 2010). It is a snow-melt mosquito, which prefers swampy forested areas and higher elevations, adult females show crepuscular activity. Hibernates in the egg stage, it is considered to be univoltine species. No vector role has been attributed so far to this species (PACKER AND CORBET, 1989).

Ochlerotatus riparius (DYAR AND KNAB, 1907) has a Nearctic and northern Palearctic distribution range, rarely reported from northern and central Europe. It belongs to the *Aedes annulipes* group. Its biology is less known, it overwinters in form of eggs, and most probably has a single generation per year. It prefers to breed in forested areas, where it breeds in temporary water bodies and swampy bogs. No vector status is known of the species (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Ochlerotatus sticticus (MEIGEN, 1838) is a widespread Holarctic species, its distribution ranges from Siberia to the Mediterranean region. It is a floodwater mosquito, it breeds in temporary water bodies and it prefers shaded terrains. Adult females mainly show crepuscular activity, but would bite aggressively during the day-time as well; it feeds on both humans and animals causing severe nuisance (BECKER ET AL., 2010). Due to its feeding habits could be considered as a potential zoonotic vector; it was proven to transmit TAHV and was found to be infected with *F. tularensis* but plays a minor role in MBD transmission (DANIELOVÁ AND HOLUBOVA, 1977; LUNDSTRÖM ET AL., 2011).

Ochlerotatus (Rusticoides) refiki (MEDSCHID, 1928) is widely distributed throughout Europe, it can be found in Scandinavia and in Asia Minor as well. It is very similar to *Oc. rusticus* as morphologically as biologically. It is a rare species. It

shows monocyclic behaviour and hibernates in egg stage at winter. The typical breeding sites for this species are semi-permanent water bodies in swampy woodlands and flooded meadows. Females would feed on humans and other mammals at dusk, but prefer to stay close to their breeding sites. No vector status has been proven to this species yet (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

In the genus *Culex*, *Culex (Barradius) modestus* (FICALBI, 1890) is considered a common species in Europe, occurring mainly in the southern and central part of the continent, but it can be found in middle and southwest Asia, northern India, and northern Africa (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

It has medical importance because this species is a proven arbovirus vector; it can transmit Bunya virus (TAHV and LEDV), or Flavivirus (WNV) and bacteria (e.g. tularaemia) (RIBEIRO ET AL., 1988; LUNDSTRÖM, 1994; BALENGHIEN ET AL., 2008; BECKER ET AL., 2010). It was the principal WNV bridge vector in France (PONÇON ET AL., 2007).

Culex (Neoculex) impudicus (FICALBI, 1890) is a common species in the Mediterranean region. In northern Africa, it was reported from Algeria, Tunisia and Iran. It breeds in freshwater, in small ponds, rock pools, marshes or along the edges of streams, occasionally in rice fields. It overwinters in form of adult females. It is mainly feeding on amphibians and it was not observed so far to feed on humans, therefore it has no medical importance, although, it is considered to feed on birds occasionally, which makes the species a potential bridge vector for WNV (BECKER ET AL., 2010; ROMI ET AL., 2004).

Culex laticinctus (EDWARDS, 1913) it is a widely distributed species, with records from Canary Islands, Africa, Asia and Europe- mostly from the Mediterranean region. Larvae are often found in fresh water, in rock pools, stream edges, and swamps, but it breeds in artificial containers (flower pot, buckets) as well in urban areas. Adult females avoid biting humans, it is considered strictly a zoophilic species, but up to date its vector competence for pathogens is unknown (BECKER ET AL., 2010; TOMA ET AL., 2020).

Culex mimeticus (NOE, 1899) distribution ranges from southern parts of the Palearctic to Oriental regions. In Europe, it ranges from the Mediterranean region to Russia. It is a polycyclic, orophilic (associated with mountainous regions) mosquito. Larvae breeds in fresh, clear water, usually in small, shallow pools. Females are considered zoophilic but would feed on humans occasionally. No vector status is known for this species (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Culex pipiens has two biotypes, *Culex pipiens pipiens* (LINNAEUS, 1758) and *Culex pipiens molestus* (FORSKÅL, 1775). The biotype *pipiens* is a widespread mosquito species in the Holarctic region and is commonly found throughout Europe. It uses as breeding sites mostly any type of semi-permanent to permanent water bodies, from larger pools with vegetation to man-made artificial containers, or flooded cellars. The females are anautogenous, and ornitophilic; they will overwinter in form of adult females, however, they usually lay eggs during this period (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

It is a medically important species due to its involvement in WNV transmission (GODDARD ET AL., 2002; REISEN ET AL., 2005; TURELL ET AL., 2000, 2001; FONSECA ET AL., 2004; HAMER ET AL., 2008; BECKER ET AL., 2010; LUTOMIAH ET AL., 2011; TURELL, 2012), as it was involved too in Romania, in the 1996 WNV epidemics (SAVAGE ET AL., 1999).

It is a competent laboratory vector for SLEV (MITCHELL ET AL., 1979, 1980; SARDELIS ET AL., 2003), susceptible to SINV (BERGMAN ET AL., 2020) RVFV (MEEGAN ET AL., 1980; GARGAN ET AL., 1983; TURELL ET AL., 1984, 1996, 2007, 2010; IRANPOUR ET AL., 2011; TURELL, 2012), and *Cx. pipiens* s.l. was tested positive for USUV and BATV (SCHEUCH ET AL., 2018).

The biotype *molestus* occurs in all Europe and in temperate regions of the world, it is more frequently in anthropogenic environments than *Cx. p. pipiens*. It cannot be morphologically differentiated from *Cx. p. pipiens*, but they exhibit ecological and physiological differences, e.g. *Cx. p. molestus* is known to be autogenous, and highly anthropophilic, they can mate in confined places (stenogamy), and diapausing is optional, they can reproduce throughout the winter in urban habitats, man-made shelters like cellars (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

It is one of the major bridge-vectors of WNV worldwide (TURELL ET AL., 2006; BECKER ET AL., 2010), competent to transmit JEV (WENG ET AL., 2000) USUV (HOLICKI ET AL., 2020).

Culex theileri (THEOBALD, 1903) is found in the Palearctic region, Middle East and in the Oriental region. It has more generations per year. The larvae can be found in flooded meadows, stagnant or slowly moving streams, rock pools, swamps, and rice fields but can occur in man-made containers or in strongly polluted waters. Adult females are zoophilic, but would feed on human hosts as well (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

It is known to be a carrier of RVFV and *D. repens* in North Africa and Portugal, as well as SINV and WNV were isolated from wild populations (JUPP ET AL., 1966;

MCINTOSH ET AL., 1967; SMITH, 1973; RIBEIRO ET AL., 1983, 1988; HARBACH, 1988; STORM ET AL., 2013).

Culex torrentium (MARTINI, 1925) is a species from the *Culex pipiens* complex. It has a wide distribution range in the temperate Palearctic region. It is very similar to *Cx. p. pipiens*, making their morphological differentiation difficult. Larvae occur in a variety of semi-permanent water bodies, river stream edges, marshes, and artificial containers. Females are strictly ornitophilic and so far it has never been reported to bite humans in the wild, nor in laboratory colonies (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

It is involved in SINV transmission (LUNDSTRÖM ET AL., 1990a, 1990b; HESSON ET AL., 2015; LWANDE ET AL., 2019), competent to transmit USUV (HOLICKI ET AL., 2020), WNV (JANSEN ET AL., 2019).

Culex (Neoculex) martinii (MEDSCHID, 1930) is not a very common species, it's a thermophilic species, and its distribution ranges from the Mediterranean region to middle Asia, but occurs in Africa too (Morocco). It breeds in a wide variety of habitats. Little is known about its biology but is assumed that it does not feed on humans, but instead prefers to bite amphibians and/or birds, like the other members of its subgenus. As its host preference is not known, no medical importance has been given to this species (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Culex (Neoculex) territans (WALKER, 1856) is widely distributed throughout Europe, ranging from central Asia to northern Africa. In the northern parts of its distribution, it is univoltine but in the southern parts, it has more than one generation per year. Preferred breeding sites are water bodies such as ponds, stream pools, swamps, lake and river edges, or channels. It overwinters in form of adult females. The adult females are known to feed mostly on amphibians, reptiles and birds, but avoid humans as potential hosts; it is not known to be a vector to MBDs (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Culex (Maillotia) hortensis (FICALBI, 1889) is widely distributed throughout the Mediterranean region, and it occurs in Africa, Middle Asia and India as well. Larvae occur in clear water, in rice fields, in small ponds or in artificial containers. Hibernation takes place in the adult stage, and females usually avoid feeding on humans, they are thought to be herpetophilic (ROIZ ET AL., 2012), therefore the species has no medical importance in transmitting MBDs (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

In the genus *Culiseta* there are 8 species present in Romania.

Culiseta (Allothobaldia) longiareolata (MACQUART, 1938) is widely distributed in Europe mostly in the Mediterranean region, but it ranges in southwest Asia, India and middle Africa. The larvae occur in rock pools, but in any kind of artificial container as well. It overwinters in larval stage. The females prefer avian hosts, and rarely bite humans (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

It is considered to be a vector of avian malaria (HUFF ET AL., 1965; SCHOENER ET AL., 2017), tularaemia (MASLOV ET AL., 1989), and WNV (HUBÁLEK ET AL., 1999; MEDLOCK, 2007; BISANZIO ET AL., 2011).

Culiseta alaskaensis (LUDLOW, 1906) is a Holarctic species with a distribution in the boreal and tundra regions, it occurs in the mountainous areas of the Middle East and northern India. Larvae can be found in a variety of habitats, from small snow-melt pools to swamps. It is a univoltine species in the north, and multivoltine in the south, hibernating takes place in form of adult females, it frequently feeds on humans, but it is not known to be involved in pathogen transmission (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Culiseta annulata (SCHRANK, 1776) is a widely distributed mosquito species in Europe, its range extends into northern Africa, Asia Minor, and southwest Asia. It is a multivoltine species, and may have 1–3 generations per year. They breed in a wide variety of natural and artificial habitats, permanent and semi-permanent water bodies, and fresh and brackish water. Adult females hibernate over winter, but so do larvae. Adult females would feed on humans, birds and various mammals during the day (BECKER ET AL., 2010). The species is known to be a potential vector of TAHV, (RIBEIRO ET AL., 1988), WNV (SCHÖNENBERGER ET AL., 2016), USUV (MANCINI ET AL., 2017).

Culiseta (Culicella) fumipennis (STEPHENS, 1825) is a widely distributed Holarctic species throughout Europe, ranging from Scandinavia to northern Africa. It is a multivoltine species. They prefer open water bodies as breeding habitats. They are considered ornitophilic species. Little is known about their vector capacity (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Culiseta glaphyoptera (SCHINER, 1864) can only be found in mountainous regions of central and south-eastern Europe. They choose partly shaded, cool breeding sites, along small mountain river streams. They most likely feed on birds or small mammals which inhabit mountainous forests (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Culiseta (Culicella) morsitans (THEOBALD, 1901) is widely distributed throughout the Palearctic region, it ranges from Scandinavia to northern Africa, common

species. It is very similar to *Cs. fumipennis*, is a monocyclic species. The larvae can be found in a variety of breeding from swampy woodlands and temporary water bodies to slowly moving waters, in fresh and saline water. It rarely attacks humans, they prefer avian hosts, small mammals or reptiles. The species was found to be a carrier of SINV (FRANCY ET AL., 1989; HESSON ET AL., 2015), EEEV (ANDREADIS ET AL., 1998; CDC, 2006) and could serve as a potential bridge vector for WNV (MEDLOCK ET AL., 2005).

Culiseta subochrea (EDWARDS, 1921) is a Palearctic species, not very common but it can be found in nearly all European countries. Its range stretches into north Africa and to middle Asia. It is closely related to *Cs. annulata*, they resemble a lot in all stages (adult, larva, pupa), even in their biology. It uses freshwater habitats, like ditches, ponds or garden tanks, but larvae have tolerance toward salinity. Overwintering takes place in adult form; Females usually feed on domestic animals and on humans, it has no significant medical or veterinary importance (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Culiseta (Culicella) ochroptera (PEUS, 1935) is a very rare mosquito, it has distribution in the Palearctic region. Females are often confused with *Cs. morsitans*, but they are smaller in size. Larvae occur in large shallow marshes, forest ponds and ditches. It is a multivoltine species, larvae and egg diapause in the winter. Females are considered ornitophilic, but would feed on amphibians, rarely on humans and have no known medical importance (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

The genus *Coquillettidia* is present in Romania with 2 species, *Coquillettidia buxtoni* and *Cq. richiardii*.

Coquillettidia buxtoni (EDWARDS, 1923) is a rarity, with a distribution in the Mediterranean basin up to Ukraine. Little is known about its biology or medical importance, but larvae are often found attached to aquatic plants' roots. Females readily attack humans in open areas (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Coquillettidia richiardii (FICALBI, 1889) is a common, widely distributed species throughout all Europe. It uses various types of permanent water bodies to breed, larvae and pupae stay submerged and connected to aquatic plants' roots. It has multiple generations per year. Females usually feed on mammals, domestic animals and humans, but it also bites birds or amphibians, causing a severe nuisance. Females are capable of autogeny (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Their medical importance can't be neglected, as they act as possible bridge-vectors for zoonotic diseases, in wild populations females were detected to be infected/

potentially transmit WNV, OHF, SINV, BATV, TAHV (HUBÁLEK ET AL., 1999; HUBÁLEK, 2008; BECKER ET AL., 2010; SZENTPÁLI-GAVALLÉRT ET AL., 2014; LEBL ET AL., 2015).

The genus *Orthopodomyia* is present in Romania with one species, the *Orthopodomyia pulcripalpis* (RONDANI, 1872), which is mainly distributed in the Mediterranean basin, the Black Sea coastal region, and in Transcaucasia. It is a tree-hole breeding mosquito with a preference toward highly alkaline waters, with multiple generations per year; ornitophilic species, rarely bite humans. Hibernation takes place in larval form during the winter. Its vector capacity is unknown, although considering its feeding habits it could be involved in arbovirus transmission like WNV, or in avian blood parasites transmission cycles (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

The genus *Uranotaenia* is also present in Romania with one species, *Uranotaenia (Pseudoficalbia) unguiculata* (EDWARDS, 1913), which is a frequent species throughout central Europe and in the Mediterranean region. Outside Europe, it occurs in Middle and southwest Asia to Iran and Pakistan. Their favoured breeding sites are floodplain forests and marshes, ditches, pools or canals with stagnant water, with rich coverage of aquatic plants. Hibernation takes place in the adult stage, females usually avoid feeding on mammals, as other species of the genus show preference towards amphibians (BECKER ET AL., 2010). WNV was detected in Austrian populations and it can have importance in other zoonotic virus transmissions (PACHLER ET AL., 2014; KEMENESI ET AL., 2014; CAMP ET AL., 2018).

1.4.2. Invasive species

The rapid globalization of trade in agricultural products and increasing tourism have dramatically increased the spread of harmful invasive organisms (KLASSEN ET AL., 2002). Currently, five invasive *Aedes* mosquito species are of concern in Europe: *Aedes aegypti*, *Ae. albopictus*, *Ae. atropalpus*, *Ae. japonicus* and *Ae. koreicus* (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2013a). Their dispersal throughout Europe is alarmingly rapid, causing a major public health concern due to their ability to transmit exotic pathogens. Invasive species play an important role in the dissemination of MBDs, they can act as bridge-vectors in the transmission of zoonotic diseases, arboviruses and other disease agents. Urbanization and the movement of the infected hosts together with the presence of the invasive species can cause epidemic outbreaks. Global warming and the ever-growing globalization sub serve these species' colonization of new territories. Usually, they have high vectorial- and rapid adaptive capacity. Their ecological plasticity allows them to evolve rapidly, e.g. they can easily

adapt to lower temperatures/ draught- by producing cold- and desiccation-resistant eggs-; they easily conform to new habitats, by finding suitable breeding sites for oviposition. They pose a threat to local mosquito fauna as well, as invasive species are superseding them by being highly competitive. Aedini species have multivoltine gonocycles, which allows them to produce multiple generations per year, becoming abundant at given breeding sites. Their host preference is wide, more or less preferring to bite humans, usually exploiting all the available blood hosts, which enhances the possibility of transmitting zoonoses from one host to another. The degree of domesticity varies between the species, some of them are showing highly anthropophilic behaviour, feeding and resting indoors, also some species prefer to bite humans (MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012).

Ae. albopictus, the Asian tiger mosquito is native to tropical regions of Asia. In the course of a climate-related evolutionary adaption, it has developed specific biological and ecological traits, such as photoperiodic sensitivity, which reflects in their breeding habits- once the days are starting to get shorter, the females would lay eggs that are different from the ones that they lay when the days are longer. These eggs, which were laid during the shorter photoperiod have the ability to enter in diapause, they are dormant and do not hatch until the following season, or until the conditions in the environment are suitable for them to hatch. This grants the species survival throughout the cold season. Moreover, they have adapted their breeding habitats to artificial breeding sites (such as tires and flower pots, man-made containers, vases, and even garbage). The ability to quickly adapt to a new environment and to new climatic conditions, their cold- and desiccation-resistant eggs and the fact that embryos inside the eggs are able to survive for more than a year makes invasive species like *Ae. albopictus* or *Ae. j. japonicus* are highly successful species. This has contributed and facilitated their global expansion and colonization of new terrains, which was accomplished mainly via international trade, the blooming shipping industry of ornamental plants like *Dracaena spp.* (lucky bamboo) and the trade of used tires. They can “travel” from one country- or continent to another by cars, aircraft or cargo containers within a matter of days or even just a few hours (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Among the five invasive Aedine species so far *Ae. albopictus* (PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015) and *Ae. japonicus* (HORVÁTH ET AL., 2021) have been reported in Romania. Neighbouring countries like Hungary and Serbia have also reported the presence of these species, moreover the presence of another invasive species, the *Ae. koreicus*, which is present in Hungary (KURUCZ ET AL., 2016; SEIDEL ET AL., 2016a; KAVRAN ET AL., 2019)

These invasive *Aedes* species should be kept under close observation in order to dynamically monitor their invasion. Not only the monitoring of these species would

be essential but also applying appropriate control methods in order to reduce the possibility of MBD transmission and to reduce the biting nuisance. MC methods (pesticide application, e.g. Pyrethroids) are usually combined with different approaches, like door-to-door campaigns for educating the public, or with biological control methods - to obtain the most effective source reduction. Assessments can be done as simple faunistic monitoring or active coordinated surveillance in suitable habitats and sites at risk for introduction and spread, such as trade routes, highways, airports, harbours, cemeteries, or highly frequented tourist destinations (SCHOLTE AND SCHAFFNER 2007; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013; COLLANTES ET AL., 2015). Mosquito management is also important to keep invasive species under control. There are numerous ways to reduce mosquito populations, some of the control methods are targeting larval populations, like bacterial insecticides (BTi), insect growth inhibitors, organophosphate insecticides, mineral oils or monomolecular films (EPA- United States Environmental Protection Agency), while others target adult populations, like the SIT (Sterile Insect Technique), which is an autocidal control method used to reduce the population numbers using laboratory breed sterile males. This method involves rearing large numbers of males of the target species, which further on will be exposed to gamma- or X-rays, which induces sexual sterility. Later the sterile males will be released into the wild, where they mate with wild females, breaking the pest's reproductive cycle (IAEA, 2022).

1.4.2.1. *Aedes (Stegomyia) albopictus* syn. *Stegomyia albopicta*

Invasive mosquitoes cause new public health concerns, posing a great threat to human well-being and to human and animal health as they are efficient vectors of numerous pathogens. Moreover, they can have also environmental impacts by being highly competitive with local mosquito species, due to their ecological plasticity (PAUPY ET AL., 2009; ANDREADIS AND WOLFE, 2010).

Aedes albopictus (SKUSE, 1895) is a mosquito species endemic to Southeast Asia (PAUPY ET AL., 2009; PETRIĆ ET AL., 2017) but in the past decades, it has been extending its range. It made it into the top “100 of the World’s Worst Invasive Alien Species” list of ISSG (GISD, 2022). Originally, it used natural habitats like tree holes as breeding sites, but due to its rapid adaptive capacity, it acquired the ability to breed in urban and suburban environments, using artificial containers (e.g. flower pots, tires, water storage containers, barrels) for oviposition. For example, suburban environments like cemeteries usually show large populations of this species, because it is a perfect breeding habitat, as it contains numerous flower vases creating yearlong optimal breeding spots (CAPUTO ET AL., 2012; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013). The species was dispersed worldwide mainly via the international trade

of used tires and ornamental plants such as lucky bamboo and has conquered every continent except Antarctica (ADHAMI AND REITER, 1998; BENEDICT ET AL., 2007; PAUPY ET AL., 2009; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013, AKINER ET AL., 2016). The intracontinental spread is mostly attributed to the passive transportation in vehicles from infested areas (SCHOLTE ET AL., 2008).

Ae. albopictus has proved efficient acclimation, by producing diapausing desiccation- and cold-resistant eggs, through which they can overwinter (HANSON AND CRAIG, 1994). Its behaviour in terms of feeding activity has shown that not only cold acclimation, but nutrition also plays a key role in the successful colonization of different ecological niches (PAUPY ET AL., 2009; DELATTE ET AL., 2010; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013).

Aedes albopictus feeds on a large spectrum of hosts, including humans, and it can act as a vector of pathogens. Since very few mosquito species that are native to Europe are capable to transmit CHIKV (PRUDHOMME ET AL., 2019), DENV, or ZIKV; the establishment of this species or other competent invasive mosquito species makes Europe vulnerable to these arboviruses. Moreover, unlike most native mosquitoes, *Ae. albopictus* has aggressive daytime biting behaviour, generating a nuisance to humans. *Ae. albopictus* shows an aggressive exophilic blood feeding behaviour and has been involved in mosquito-borne pathogen transmission throughout Europe, mainly in the Mediterranean region where this species is known to be a vector for several arboviruses, such as CHIKV, ZIKV, DENV and it is susceptible to transmit EEEV, LCV, VEEV, JEV and WNV. It is a vector for *Dirofilaria immitis* and *D. repens* (PAUPY ET AL., 2009; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). The tiger mosquito was responsible for an epidemic of chikungunya fever with 217 confirmed cases in northern Italy in 2007 (ANGELINI ET AL., 2007; BONILAURI ET AL., 2008), and 2 chikungunya fever cases locally transmitted from an imported case in France in 2010 (DELATTE ET AL., 2010; GRANDADAM ET AL., 2011), and autochthonous dengue outbreaks in France in 2010 (LA RUCHE ET AL., 2010; MARCHAND ET AL., 2013; SUCCO ET AL., 2016), as well as in Croatia in 2010 (GJENERO-MARGAN ET AL., 2011; GOSSNER ET AL., 2018a) and in Spain (ECDC, 2018a; ECDC, 2019a). Autochthonous cases of chikungunya fever were reported in Montpellier, France (DELISLE ET AL., 2015). Additionally, imported human cases of Zika (FLORESCU ET AL., 2017) and dengue (DINU ET AL., 2015a) in Romania have been recently reported.

In Europe its first observation was reported from Albania, in August 1979 (ADHAMI AND MURATI, 1987), possibly imported with cargo shipments from China; later on from Italy (SABATINI ET AL., 1990). Subsequently, the species has rapidly invaded new territories, including most of the Mediterranean region (SCHOLTE AND SCHAFFNER, 2007; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). Since its first finding it has been reported from Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Romania, Croatia, Czech

Republic, North Macedonia, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Slovakia, Liechtenstein, Malta, Monaco, Montenegro, the Netherlands, Portugal, southern Russia, San Marino, Serbia, Slovenia, Spain, United Kingdom, Switzerland, Turkey, Vatican City, Republic of Moldova, Kosovo (SCHOLTE ET AL., 2008; GANUSHKINA ET AL., 2012; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012; PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015; ŠEBESTA ET AL., 2012; BOCKOVÁ ET AL., 2013; SEIDEL ET AL., 2016a; SEIDEL ET AL., 2016b; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2017; GOSSNER ET AL., 2018a; CVETKOVIKJ, 2020; FĂLCUȚĂ ET AL., 2020; SULESCO ET AL., 2021; MUJA-BAJRAKTARI ET AL., 2022).

In Romania, this species was first found in 2012. Between August 26 and October 5, an entomological survey for WNW vectors was carried out in Bucharest and its suburban area, with 14 collection sites. During the survey, three types of mosquito traps were used: CDC gravid traps, CDC light traps, and BG Sentinel traps with BG-lure. Between September 4 and October 3, a total of 45 *Ae. albopictus* (38 females and 7 males) were captured at 7 locations in the south of Bucharest. Most of them were collected using CDC gravid traps.

In 2013, from July to October, another surveillance was performed in the same locations, where *Aedes albopictus* was sampled again. Larvae were found present too at the sampled locations: in rain catch basins like water barrels and in other man-made household containers.

In 2014 another aggressive *Ae. albopictus* population was found in a household in Bucharest, following a nuisance complaint of an inhabitant. Following an entomological investigation adults and larvae were found present at the property. During this period, surveillance of *Ae. albopictus* outside of the capital city was not performed, but the data showed maintenance of the species for over 2 winter seasons. The presence of *Ae. albopictus* has been reported every year since 2012 and has become established in Bucharest with a permanent breeding population (PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015).

Today, this mosquito is spread inside the Carpathian Mountains arch (the historical region of Transylvania, in Sibiu county), and the distribution data shows that the lowland southeast and western regions of the country host several well-established populations as well (FĂLCUȚĂ ET AL., 2020). During this short period since its first detection, the species become established in 19 counties. Romania does not have an active mosquito surveillance program; hence, all the data originate from research-related sampling. These new records from Romania show the continuous spreading tendency of the tiger mosquito. They also highlight the need for surveillance, not only to further assess the species distribution and abundance but also to assess the pathogen transmission risk related to this vector species.

1.4.2.4. *Aedes (Finlaya) japonicus japonicus* syn. *Hulecoeteomyia japonica*, *Ochlerotatus japonicus japonicus*

Aedes japonicus (THEOBALD, 1901), the Asian bush- or rock pool mosquito, is also originating from East Asia, but nowadays is widely distributed throughout central Europe (TANAKA ET AL., 1979). Its occurrence in Europe was firstly reported in France, in 2020 (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2003), then in Belgium, in 2002 (VERSTEIRT ET AL., 2009), in Switzerland and Germany in 2008 (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2009), in Austria and Slovenia in 2011 (SEIDEL ET AL., 2012); in 2012 it was reported from the Netherlands and Hungary (IBÁÑEZ-JUSTICIA ET AL. 2014; SEIDEL ET AL., 2016a), later from Croatia, in 2013 (KLOBUČAR ET AL. 2019), from Lichtenstein and Italy in 2015 (SEIDEL ET AL., 2016b; MONTARSI ET AL., 2019), from Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2017 (JANSSEN ET AL., 2020), from Spain, Luxembourg and Serbia in 2018 (ERITJA ET AL., 2019; SCHAFFNER AND RIES, 2019; JANSSEN ET AL., 2020), from Slovakia in 2020 (ČABANOVÁ ET AL., 2021) and from Romania in 2020 (HORVÁTH ET AL., 2021).

It is a container breeding species, which means that it has adapted to urban areas where it uses artificial containers for breeding, like cemetery vases, stone vessels, fountains and catch basins (TANAKA ET AL., 1979; SOTA ET AL., 1994; MONTARSI ET AL., 2015). In its native range, it colonises tree-hole habitats in forested areas, rock pools or bamboo stumps (KAUFMAN AND FONSECA, 2014). In the urban areas it is a nuisance biting pest, and is active during the daytime and in evening hours; it takes blood meals mostly from mammals, although feeding on birds has also been observed (APPERSON ET AL., 2004). It is an aggressive biter. This species is multivoltine and overwintering, which suggests that it could be more widely established in Europe (ANDREADIS ET AL., 2001). It is a highly competitive species, it has higher overwintering survival rates and hatches earlier compared to *Ae. albopictus* (CUNZE ET AL., 2016), besides it is able to exploit larval habitats before *Ae. albopictus* and is outcompeting *Ae. atropalpus* in some areas of the United States due to shorter larval development periods (ARMISTEAD ET AL., 2014).

In its native range *Ae. japonicus* is not considered an important disease vector, however, its relevance cannot be neglected. Evidence shows that it can transmit ZIKV (JANSEN ET AL., 2018; ABBO ET AL., 2020; GLAVINIC ET AL., 2020) and it is an efficient vector for WNV (SARDELIS AND TURELL, 2001; ANDREADIS ET AL., 2001; TURELL ET AL., 2005), DENV and CHIKV (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2011). Susceptible to both *D. immitis* and *D. repens* (SILAGHI ET AL., 2017) and was involved in JEV transmission in Asia (TAKASHIMA AND ROSEN, 1989) and LACV transmission in the US (SARDELIS ET AL., 2002a; WESTBY ET AL., 2011). Competent vector for EEEV (SARDELIS ET AL., 2002b), SLEV (SARDELIS ET AL., 2003) and RVFV (TURELL ET AL., 2013) under laboratory conditions.

In Romania, the species was first found during an entomological survey conducted at the International Airport of Cluj-Napoca, with the aim to investigate the presence/absence of invasive *Aedes* mosquito species. The study was carried out between 30 June and 29 September 2020. During the survey 1 BG-Sentinel trap and 5 ovitraps were operating. On the 24th of August, 26 eggs were collected in one of the ovitraps placed at the airport. The eggs were hatched and the adults were later identified to be *Ae. japonicus*. Since its first report the species has been detected in 2021 in Cluj-Napoca, and in Târgu Mureş with the help of a citizen science application (Mosquito Alert). Further investigation is needed to assess the species distribution and status in Romania.

1.4.2.3. *Aedes (Finlaya) koreicus* syn. *Hulecoeteomyia koreica*, *Ochlerotatus koreicus*

Aedes koreicus (EDWARDS, 1917), or the “Korean bush mosquito” is a species endemic to Japan, north-eastern China, South Korea and some parts of Russia (TANAKA ET AL., 1979). Outside its natural range it was first reported in Belgium, in 2008 (VERSTEIRT ET AL., 2012, 2014), in Italy, in 2011 (CAPELLI ET AL., 2011; MARCANTONIO ET AL., 2016; BALLARDINI ET AL., 2019; NEGRI ET AL., 2021), and quickly colonized the Swiss-Italian border and Switzerland (SUTER ET AL., 2015); it was reported from Russia (BEZZHONOVA ET AL., 2014; GANUSHKINA ET AL., 2016), Germany (WERNER ET AL., 2016; PFITZNER ET AL., 2018; ZOTZMANN ET AL., 2019; HOHMEISTER ET AL., 2021), Hungary (KURUCZ ET AL., 2016), Slovenia (KALAN ET AL., 2017), Crimea (KOVALENKO AND TIKHONOV, 2019; GANUSHKINA ET AL., 2020), Austria (FUEHRER ET AL., 2020), Republic of Kazakhstan (ANDREEVA ET AL., 2021), and from the Netherlands (TEEKEMA ET AL., 2022).

Its morphology and biology are very similar to *Ae. j. japonicus*; they originate from the same region, they are highly adapted to human habitations offered breeding sites (e.g. artificial containers) (TANAKA ET AL., 1979; MONTARSI ET AL., 2013). Much like *Ae. albopictus* and *Ae. j. japonicus*, this species can also survive long human-aided transport routes and low temperatures. It has the ability to overwinter by producing freeze- and desiccation-resistant dormant eggs and has a higher tolerance to cold climates compared to *Ae. albopictus* (MONTARSI ET AL., 2013; KAUFMAN AND FONSECA, 2014; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2015).

Ae. koreicus is known to bite cattle, domestic animals and humans during daytime (TANAKA ET AL., 1979; KIM ET AL., 2004; CAPELLI ET AL., 2011). As for its vector competence, field evidence revealed *D. repens* infection in wild-caught females (KURUCZ ET AL., 2018). Laboratory experiments demonstrated that *Ae. koreicus* is susceptible to *D. immitis* infection (MONTARSI ET AL., 2015), same as for CHIKV (CIOCCHETTA ET AL., 2018; JANSEN ET AL., 2021). Vector potential has been

demonstrated for *Brugia malayi* in Korea (KCDC, 2007). Laboratory experiments have revealed susceptibility to experimental virus transmission for JEV in Russia, in 1970 (GUTSEVICH ET AL., 1974), and ZIKV (JANSEN ET AL., 2021). Regarding its vector competence towards WNV, studies could not prove its involvement in virus transmission (JANSEN ET AL., 2021).

We have to consider its possible future expansion towards Romania, considering its strong ecological plasticity and resistance to colder climates.

1.4.2.2. *Aedes (Stegomyia) aegypti*

Aedes aegypti (LINNAEUS, 1762), often called the “yellow fever mosquito”, is endemic to north Africa and it is one of the most widespread invasive mosquito species globally; currently, it is dispersed throughout the tropics including Africa and in subtropical regions such as the Pacific and Indian Islands, south-eastern United States, the Middle East, Southeast Asia and Northern Australia (PAUPY ET AL., 2009; SOUMAHORO ET AL., 2010). In Europe, its presence dates back to the late 18th century. It is present in Madeira (ALMEIDA ET AL., 2007; SEIXAS ET AL., 2013), Russia and Georgia (YUNICHEVA ET AL., 2008; AKINER ET AL., 2016), Turkey (AKINER ET AL., 2016), the Netherlands (IBAÑEZ-JUSTICIA ET AL., 2017).

It is adapted to urban environments thanks to its ecological plasticity; it is a highly anthropophilic, aggressive day-time biter preferring to bite humans. It uses a variety of artificial containers and natural habitats like dwellings, water tanks, uncovered cisterns, rain-filled empty cans, flower pots, tree holes or leaf axils (OTERO ET AL., 2006; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012; BECKER ET AL., 2010). This species' biology is the same as the development of other Aedini species. It is known to be a multivoltine species, mammophilic, highly anthropophilic, with a daytime- and crepuscular activity (TURELL ET AL., 2005; SAIFUR ET AL., 2012).

Unlike *Ae. albopictus*, the dispersal of *Ae. aegypti* towards the temperate regions is currently restricted due to its intolerance to temperate winters. It produces desiccation-resistant eggs, but the mortality of eggs is high when they are exposed to frost, although they can resist low temperatures for up to one year (OTERO ET AL., 2006).

Ae. aegypti is an important vector for CHKV (DE LAMBALLERIE ET AL., 2008), DENV (PAUPY ET AL., 2003; RAMCHURN ET AL., 2009), ZIKV (MUSSO AND GUBLER, 2016) - and YFV (AITKEN ET AL., 1979; FONTENILLE ET AL., 1997), its establishment in Europe raises concerns about autochthonous arbovirus transmission (TOMASELLO AND SCHLAGENHAUF, 2013; SCHAFFNER AND MATHIS, 2014). It is a competent vector for VEEV- and WNV as well (LARSEN ET AL., 1971; TURELL ET AL., 2005).

1.4.2.5. *Aedes (Coquilett) atropalpus* syn. *Georgecraigius atropalpus*, *Ochlerotatus atropalpus*

Aedes atropalpus (COQUILLET, 1902) is a North American invasive species. It has been reported from several countries in central Europe, in Italy (ROMI ET AL., 1997), France and The Netherlands (SCHOLTE ET AL., 2009; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2015), although up to date it has no established populations. This species was likely introduced in Europe due to commercial trade and transport (MEDLOCK ET AL., 2005). It is known that this species is autogenous which means that can produce its first eggs without taking blood meal (BEIER ET AL., 1983). Normally breeds in rock pools and has more than one generation per year. It occurs early in the spring and prefers mammalian hosts (MEDLOCK ET AL., 2005).

Ae. atropalpus feeds on numerous hosts, and it has a great vector capacity; WNV was isolated from field-caught mosquitoes (TURELL ET AL., 2005), and experimental transmission has been proven for WNV, LACV, JEV, SLEV and EEEV (FREIER AND BEIER, 1984; HARDY ET AL., 1984; SCHOLTE ET AL., 2009), which means that once it gets established, it could have a potential impact on public health in Europe (MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012).

1.4.2.6. Other invasive species

Aedes (Ochlerotatus) triseriatus (SAY, 1823), the American tree-hole mosquito, is originating from North America. So far it has been found in France back in 2004, arriving with some shipment of used tires, which later were treated with insecticide. There is no evidence, that the species became established (CHOUIN AND SCHAFFNER, unpublished data; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012).

It is considered primarily zoophilic, but also feeds on humans (FREIER AND GRIMSTAD, 1983; MOLAEI ET AL., 2008). It has multiple generations per year; it breeds in tree holes, discarded tires and other artificial containers, often in urban areas. *Ae. triseriatus* is able to exploit larval habitats before *Ae. albopictus*, but when competing for food resources the larvae of *Ae. albopictus* exceeds the larvae of *Ae. triseriatus* (LEISNHAM AND JULIANO, 2012).

Ae. triseriatus is a medically important species which is known to be a vector for the WNV (STYER ET AL., 2007; UNLU ET AL., 2010), LACV (PANTUWATANA ET AL., 1972; THOMPSON ET AL., 1972; WATTS ET AL., 1974; BEIER ET AL., 1983), and SLEV (SHOPE, 1980). It has been demonstrated to be susceptible to other arboviruses such as VEEV (DAVIS ET AL., 1966), EEEV, WEEV, DENV and YFV (MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). It is considered to be a vector for JCV (WALKER ET AL., 1993).

Culex vishnui (THEOBALD, 1901) is a mosquito from Asia as well, in the Oriental areas is considered a major vector for the JEV (VYTHILINGAM ET AL., 1995), but also specimens from the wild were sampled to be infected with WNV (MISHRA AND MOURYA, 2001).

In Europe it was sampled in Albania, although this species can be confused with *Culex tritaeniorhynchus*, which also occurs in parts of the Balkans; so far this report is needed to be confirmed (MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012).

It is considered to be an exophilic and zoophilic species, it feeds on cattle, farm animals and humans (BHATTACHARYYA ET AL., 1994).

1.4.3. Spreading mechanisms of invasive mosquito species

The ever-growing globalization together with the climate crisis, anthropogenic movements and activities- in particular the international trade of used tires, facilitated invasive mosquitoes to colonize new territories in Europe (GENCHI ET AL., 2009; OTRANTO ET AL., 2013). These mosquitoes are well adapted to survive human-induced transport over long distances, can tolerate low winter temperatures, and can exploit artificial containers as breeding sites (MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). Invasive mosquitoes cause new public health threats, as they can transmit MBDs that affect human and animal wellbeing (BENEDICT ET AL., 2007; PAUPY ET AL., 2009). The introduction of these alien species can also have a huge impact on ecosystems, their expansion can lead to the disappearance of native species since they can drive back native species' abundance by exploiting the same food and breeding site resources (CROWL ET AL., 2008; PAUPY ET AL., 2009).

Importation pathways of the invasive mosquitoes are believed to be partly due to commercial transport such as the used tire trade or the ornamental flower trade. The global transportation of the used tires toward European countries facilitated the spread of invasive mosquito species, such as the *Aedes albopictus*. Besides used tires, importing ornamental flowers, such as the lucky bamboo has made an impact on the dispersion of this species, e.g. the water- and gel-based plant importation ensures necessary space for larval development (SCHOLTE ET AL., 2008).

Road-, aerial- and sea traffic could also facilitate the further spread of the mosquitoes, harbours and airports serve as important entry points of the species. The increased travel movement of tourists and goods facilitates the transmission of exotic diseases and the dispersal of alien species (TATEM ET AL., 2006; CROWL ET AL., 2008; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). The expansion of the global transport network together with ongoing epidemics in different parts of the world and the spread of

vectors facilitates vector-borne pathogen-associated disease transmission (TATEM ET AL., 2006).

1.4.4. Mosquitoes importance in public health

Mosquitoes can transmit several medically important pathogens and parasites that raise public health concerns among human and animal communities, such as bacteria, protozoans, arboviruses, and nematodes, which can cause serious diseases like malaria, dengue, yellow- and Chikungunya fever, encephalitis or filariasis (ELDRIDGE AND EDMAN, 2012). If we take a closer look at the mortality caused by vector-borne diseases among the world's human population, it is out of the question that mosquitoes are the most medically important arthropod-vector group, as more than three billion people are affected worldwide every year by MBDs. Due to their feeding habits, mosquitoes are able to transfer pathogens or parasites from one host to another during their blood meal. They become infected by ingesting blood from an infected host, and after proliferation in the vector, the virus can be transmitted to another vertebrate host (horizontal transmission). This transmission mechanism in arthropods is known under the term of arthropod-borne-virus transmission, and the term "arbovirus" is defined as viruses that replicate in arthropods and are transmitted by arthropods to vertebrates. During a transovarial transmission (vertical transmission) cycle, arboviruses are transferred from one arthropod generation to their offspring (BECKER ET AL., 2010). Approximately 100 arboviruses impact humans and 40 infect livestock. The most important arboviruses that cause an impact on public health come from three families: Togaviridae family with the genus Alphavirus (e.g. CHIKV, SINV, EEEV, and RRV), Flaviviridae family with the genus Flavivirus (e.g. YFV, DENV 1-4, WNV, JEV and SLEV) and the Bunyaviridae family with the genera Bunyavirus (e.g. the California group), and Phlebovirus (RVFV) (ELDRIDGE AND EDMAN, 2012). In the past few decades, globalisation, anthropogenic movements and increased transportation of goods have facilitated the dispersion of invasive mosquito species in Europe. The public health concern of these species have increased as well as the circulation of mosquito-borne pathogens, putting pressure on the public health system and economy. The establishment of alien species in combination with the favourable environmental and climatic conditions, together with the importation of travel-related viral infections of MBDs, has resulted in autochthonous transmission of exotic arboviruses throughout Europe. Several imported or autochthonous cases of ZIKV, CHIKV and DENV were reported from Europe, among these countries is Romania with imported cases of ZIKV (FLORESCU ET AL., 2017), DENV (DINU ET AL., 2015a) and CHIKV (JAVELLE ET AL., 2019); worth to mention that EEEV, WEEV

and SINV were also detected with low seroprevalence in human samples (DRĂGĂNESCU ET AL., 1975).

1.4.4.1. Mosquito-borne diseases relevant to public health in Europe

1.4.4.1.1. Arboviruses with public health importance in Romania

West Nile virus (WNV) is the causative agent of West Nile fever, it first was isolated from the blood of a woman in the West Nile province of Uganda in 1937 (HUGHES ET AL., 1940). The virus is a positive-stranded RNA virus, belonging to the Japanese encephalitis serocomplex (Flaviviridae) (MUKHOPADHYAY ET AL., 2003). There have been 8 WNV strains described (FALL ET AL., 2017) of which only lineage 1 and 2 are affecting humans. Usually, individuals remain asymptomatic (about 80% of the cases) (KRAMER ET AL., 2007), but when it manifests, it is causing fever, nonspecific influenza-like symptoms or in severe cases neurological affections -infectious encephalitis, meningitis and even fatalities (MUKHOPADHYAY ET AL., 2003; PAZ, 2015).

WNV is a mosquito-borne Flavivirus, the virus transmission is maintained through a bird-mosquito-bird (or accidentally human) cycle. Humans are considered dead-end hosts, due to only developing low-level serum viremia and cannot re-infect mosquitoes (BOWEN AND NEMETH, 2007; KRAMER ET AL., 2007).

The most important hosts of this virus are wild birds, hooded crows and house sparrows appear to be important amplification hosts (PÉREZ-RAMÍREZ ET AL., 2014). The primary vector species are belonging to the *Culex* genera, members of the *Cx. pipiens* complex (*Cx. pipiens*, *Cx. molestus*, *Cx. modestus*) are proven to be competent laboratory vectors of WNV (TURELL ET AL. 2000, 2005; SARDELIS ET AL. 2001; GODDARD ET AL. 2002; LUTOMIAH ET AL. 2011), but also *Ae. albopictus*, *Ae. vexans*, *Oc. dorsalis*, *Oc. caspius*, *Oc. detritus*, *Oc. sticticus*, *Oc. punctor*, *Oc. cantans*, *An. plumbeus*, mosquitoes from the AMC (*An. messeae*, *An. atroparvus*), *Cq. richiardii*, *Cs. annulata*, *Cs. morsitans*, *Ae. japonicus*, *Ae. cinereus* and *Ae. triseriatus* are potent vectors (MEDLOCK ET AL., 2005, TURELL ET AL., 2005). Vertical transmission of the virus was proven in *Cx. pipiens* (DINU ET AL., 2015b).

In Romania, the epidemic activity was quite intense, first in the 1960's then in 1996 with at least 352 serologically confirmed cases and 17 deaths (TSAI ET AL., 1996; CAMPBELL ET AL., 2001). The strain belonged to the genetic lineage 1 (SAVAGE ET AL., 1999). Between 1997-2000, there were only 39 clinical cases recorded including 5 deaths. In 2010, another major outbreak caused by WNV lineage 2 with 54 cases were reported (SIRBU ET AL., 2011). In all outbreaks *Culex pipiens* was identified as the main vector in the disease transmission (SAVAGE ET AL., 1999;

SIRBU ET AL., 2011). In 2016 another significant outbreak occurred in Romania, with 93 neurological cases (ECDC, 2016), screening of the mosquito population has revealed three vector species involved in the outbreak *Cx. pipiens*, *Cx. modestus*, and *Cq. richiardii* (COTAR ET AL., 2018).

Today WNV associated infections affect southern-, western- and eastern European countries, and it has become a major public health and veterinary concern.

Dengue virus (DENV) is a rapidly spreading arbovirus, it has 4 serotypes (DENV 1-4) which cause severe illness among humans, dengue fever (DF) and dengue haemorrhagic fever (DHF). Nearly 75% of the global population is exposed to dengue, mostly habitants in the Asia-Pacific region, Africa and the eastern Mediterranean (GUZMÁN AND KOURI, 2002).

The virus is a positive single-stranded RNA virus, belonging to the family of Flaviviridae, the Flavivirus genus. The infection with the virus can cause acute febrile symptoms, in severe cases DHF or dengue shock syndrome with fatalities, but up to 80% of dengue infections have no symptoms at all (GUZMÁN AND KOURI, 2002).

The virus transmission is maintained in a human-mosquito-human cycle, humans are the main hosts of the virus and mosquitoes from *Aedes* genus serve as primary vectors, *Ae. aegypti* and *Ae. albopictus* being the most important species (SCHAFFNER AND MATHIS, 2014). Many autochthonous cases were reported from Europe e.g. from France, Croatia, Greece and from Madeira (TOMASELLO AND SCHLAGENHAUF, 2013). In Romania, imported cases of DENV were reported between 2008 and 2013 (DINU ET AL., 2015a).

Zika virus (ZIKV) is another virus from the Flaviviridae family, Flavivirus genus. It was first isolated from a rhesus monkey in 1947 and from *Ae. africanus* in 1948 (DICK ET AL., 1952).

The virus is a positive-stranded RNA-virus, from the Flaviviridae family, Flavivirus genus, with two lineages: African and Asian lineage. Infection with the virus can led to mild febrile illness with maculopapular rash; ZIKV infections were associated with foetal losses, congenital microcephaly and Guillain–Barré syndrome (WEAVER ET AL., 2016; AGUMADU AND RAMPHUL, 2018). The main vectors are mosquitoes from *Aedes* genus, *Ae. aegypti* and *Ae. albopictus* being the most competitive vectors (BENELLI ET AL., 2017).

The virus transmission is maintained in a sylvatic cycle involving non-human primates and mosquitoes from *Aedes* genus. In urban/suburban environments a mosquito-human-mosquito cycle is occurring, *Aedes aegypti* and *Ae. albopictus* are

considered the most important vectors for Zika virus transmission (ELDRIDGE AND EDMAN, 2012).

In Romania, imported cases of ZIKV were reported in 2016 (FLORESCU ET AL., 2017).

Chikungunya virus (CHIKV) caused viral infections can be confused with dengue. Unlike dengue, which is a member of the family Flaviviridae, CHIKV belongs to the family of Togaviridae. Phylogenetic analysis has identified three different genotypes of the virus: West African, Asian and East Central South African (POWERS ET AL., 2000). Symptoms are influenza-like, with maculopapular rash (HUBÁLEK, 2008). The principal mosquito vector is *Ae. aegypti*, which maintains human-to-human transmission cycles. In Europe the primary vector is *Ae. albopictus*, but *Ae. koreicus* and *Ae. japonicus* also has the potential to transmit this virus (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2011; CIOCCHETTA ET AL., 2018). There have been reported autochthonous cases of chikungunya fever in Europe from Italy, La Réunion Island and France (TOMASELLO AND SCHLAGENHAUF, 2013; CIOCCHETTA ET AL., 2018). Imported cases of CHIKV have been reported in Romania in 2018 (JAVELLE ET AL., 2019).

Ťahyňa virus (TAHV) is a virus from the Bunyaviridae family, common throughout central Europe and Asia.

First, it was isolated from *Ae. vexans* and *Oc. caspius* in 1958 (BÁRDOŠ AND DANIELOVÁ, 1959). The virus has a three-segmented negative-stranded RNA genome, and it causes mild influenza-like illness, in severe cases meningitis, but no fatal cases have been reported (KALLIO-KOKKO ET AL., 2005).

The main vectors included in the transmission are from the genus *Aedes*: *Ae. vexans*, *Oc. caspius*, *Oc. cantans* and *Ae. cinereus*, but there have been a few isolations from mosquitoes in other genera like *Culex*, *Anopheles*, *Culiseta* and *Mansonia* as well (e.g. *Cs. annulata*, *Cx. modestus*, *Cx. pipiens* and *An. hyrcanus*). Other important species are *Oc. punctator*, *Oc. communis*, *Oc. flavescens*, and *Oc. excrucians* (HUBÁLEK, 2008). In Romania, it was isolated from *Culex pipiens* (ARCAN ET AL., 1974; DRĂGĂNESCU ET AL., 1979).

Yellow fever virus (YFV) is a member of the Flaviviridae family, with a positive single-stranded RNA, first, it was isolated in humans in 1927, but in general, primates are susceptible to this infection. It is endemic in the South American and African tropics. Mosquitoes from the genus *Aedes* and *Haemagogus* are the primary vectors of this virus and the sylvatic cycle is maintained between mosquitoes and monkeys, in Europe *Ae. aegypti* and *Ae. albopictus* are the major vectors (HUBÁLEK, 2008; GIANCHECCHI ET AL., 2022). Symptoms are influenza-like with mild fever, in

severe cases haemorrhagic fever, organ malfunction and fatalities. The transmission of yellow fever virus has been reported from countries across sub-Saharan Africa and in tropical areas across South and Central America, and in Europe (GIANCHECCHI ET AL., 2022). One imported case of YFV has been reported from Romania in 2018 (GOSSNER ET AL., 2018b).

1.4.4.1.2. Other medically important mosquito-borne viruses

Western equine encephalomyelitis virus (WEEV) is a member of the Togaviridae family, comprised of 6 serotypes. The virus is transmitted by ornitophilic *Cx. tarsalis* among passeriform birds in agroecosystems, but *Aedes spp.* (*Aedes melanimon* and *Ae. dorsalis*), *Culex (Melanoconion) ocosa* and *Culex (Melanoconion) portesi* and small mammals or birds can be involved in WEEV transmission cycle (HUBÁLEK, 2008).

Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus (VEEV) has numerous serotypes and varieties, all of which can cause illness in humans. Vectors are in the genus *Culex*, subgenus *Melanoconion*, *Aedes*, *Ochlerotatus*, *Anopheles*, *Mansonia* and *Psorophora*. Small rodents are the principal vertebrate hosts; but also birds may be involved in transmission cycles (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

O' nyong-nyong virus (ONNV) is classified as a serotype of CHIK virus and occurs only in tropical Africa, *Anopheles funestus* and *An. gambiae* are the most important vectors of this disease. It is considered a neglected MBD with similar symptoms to chikungunya fever. ONNV was first isolated in Uganda in 1959 and has caused several major outbreaks in eastern and western Africa. Humans are the only known reservoirs of the virus (SAXTON-SHAW ET AL., 2013; REZZA ET AL., 2017).

Sindbis virus (SINV) is an alphavirus. It was first isolated in 1952 from *Culex* mosquitoes collected in the Egyptian village of Sindbis. It is present in Europe, Africa, Asia and Australia. The primary vectors of this virus are ornitophilic mosquitoes from the genus *Culex*, *Aedes* and *Culiseta* (e.g. *Culex pipiens*, *Culex torrentium*, *Culiseta morsitans*, *Coquillettidia richiardii*, *Ochlerotatus communis*, *Ochlerotatus excrucians*, *Aedes cinereus*, and *Anopheles hyrcanus*) (HUBÁLEK, 2008).

St. Louis encephalitis virus (SLEV) is an important mosquito-borne virus, the transmission cycles are maintained between *Culex* mosquitoes and passeriform-, columbiform- and other bird species, humans and domestic animals are considered dead-end hosts. It is a single-stranded RNA virus, most cases remain asymptomatic, or with mild flu-like symptoms, only severe cases result in encephalitis. The main

mosquito vectors are *Cx. pipiens*, *Cx. quinquefasciatus*, *Cx. tarsalis* and *Cx. nigripalpus* (SIMON ET AL., 2022).

Japanese encephalitis virus (JEV) is widespread in the temperate and tropical parts of eastern and southern Asia; it is a virus from the Flaviviridae family, it was first isolated in 1934 from a deceased patient's brain and later, in 1938 from *Cx. tritaeniorhynchus*, which has been identified as the major vector of the virus (VAN DEN HURK ET AL., 2009). Probably the most important vector species are from the genus *Culex* and *Aedes* (*Ae. albopictus*, *Ae. vexans*, *Ae. japonicus*, *Ae. koreicus*), but it has been isolated from a large number of mosquito species, while the hosts are mostly mammals (equines, humans and pigs- latter serving as the major amplifying host) but wild and domestic birds also serve as important reservoirs (ROSEN, 1986). The clinical manifestation of the infection is often asymptomatic, or mild- non-specific influenza-like illness, only in severe cases appears to be acute meningitis which can result in the death of the patient (VAN DEN HURK ET AL., 2009).

Jamestown Canyon virus (JCV) is a virus from the Bunyaviridae family, which occurs throughout most of North America; mosquitoes of the genus *Aedes/Ochlerotatus* are the primary vectors (*Ae. albopictus*, *Ae. vexans*, *Ae. cinereus*, *Oc. communis*, *Oc. dorsalis*) while the major amplifying hosts is the White-tailed deer, *Odocoileus virginianus*. In humans the virus causes mild febrile illness or in acute form meningitis and encephalitis (ANDREADIS ET AL., 2008).

La Crosse virus (LACV) is probably the second most important mosquito-borne arbovirus in North America (behind SLEV). It is a bunyavirus from the California serogroup, first, it was isolated in 1964 (THOMPSON ET AL., 1965). The mosquito vectors are from the *Aedes* genus (*Ae. triseriatus*, *Aedes hendersoni*; *Ae. albopictus* and *Ae. japonicus* vector capacity has been proven in laboratory conditions). Hosts are small mammals (squirrels) or accidentally humans. The disease's symptoms are fever, headache, muscle pain, and general discomfort- in severe cases encephalitis but rarely causes death (HARDING ET AL., 2019).

Batai virus (BATV) is a pathogen from *Bunyaviridae*. First time it was isolated from *Culex* mosquitoes in 1955. Principal vectors in Europe are zoophilic mosquitoes like *Anopheles maculipennis*, *Anopheles claviger*, *Coquillettidia richiardii*, *Ochlerotatus punctor* and *Ochlerotatus communis*. The main hosts are pigs, horses and ruminants, but birds are efficient reservoirs. The clinical manifestation of the disease is influenza-like symptoms with fever (HUBÁLEK, 2008).

Usutu virus (USUV) is a Flavivirus, it was isolated first time in 1959 from *Culex* mosquitoes. Primary hosts are wild birds (predominantly blackbirds *Turdus merula*). The vectors are largely ornitophilic mosquitoes from the *Culex* genus (for ex. *Culex univittatus*, *Culex perfuscus*, *Culex pipiens*, *Culex hortensis* and *Culex territans*), other important species are *Coquillettidia aurites*, *Mansonia africana*, *Culiseta annulata*, *Aedes vexans*, and *Aedes rossicus* (HUBÁLEK, 2008). It is a neglected MBD as it has never been associated with severe illness or death.

Rift Valley fever virus (RVFV) is a Phlebovirus from the family Bunyaviridae, with great veterinary importance, it is considered to cause severe disease in livestock, especially in sheep and cattle, but it can cause serious infections in humans as well- clinical manifestation can lead to severe encephalitis, hepatitis, haemorrhagic symptoms. The mosquito vectors are species from the *Aedes* genus and from the *Culex pipiens* complex, besides mosquitoes Simuliidae and Culicoides can also transmit the virus (BIRD ET AL., 2009).

1.4.4.1.3. MOSQUITO-BORNE DISEASES WITH AN IMPACT ON PUBLIC HEALTH

There are numerous nematode species transmitted by mosquitoes that are causing public health concerns in tropical areas, e.g. the lymphatic **filariasis**, caused by *Wuchereria bancrofti* (COBBOLD, 1877) and *Brugia malayi* (BRUG, 1927) that affects millions of people worldwide; *W. Bancrofti* is endemic to the Sub-Saharan Africa, Madagascar, western Pacific region, southeast Asia, India and South America, while *B. malayi* occurs in southeast Asia. The principal vector for this disease is *Culex quinquefasciatus* but other mosquitoes e.g. Anophelinae, *Aedes spp.* (*Ae. koreicus*) or species from the *Culex pipiens* complex can transmit *W. bancrofti* in the subtropics (EDESON AND WILSON, 1964).

Heartworm disease and subcutaneous dirofilariasis are generally of concern in subtropical region, but lately countries with moderate climate in Europe have to deal with this public health burden. The most affected areas are Italy, Spain, Portugal, Greece and France (GENCHI ET AL., 2009; CAPELLI ET AL., 2013; ONTARO ET AL., 2013; VIEIRA ET AL., 2015). The causative agents are nematodes, *Dirofilaria immitis* and *D. repens*, it mostly affects dogs, but can parasitize other domestic or wild animals such as foxes, jackals, wolves, wildcat and weasel (IONICĂ ET AL., 2017). Most vectors for this disease belong to the genus *Aedes*, *Anopheles* and *Culex* (MORCHÓN ET AL., 2012).

Malaria is caused by single-celled microorganisms, called protozoans from the *Plasmodium spp.* and is one of the most severe public health problems worldwide. Nearly half of the world's population lives in areas affected by malaria transmission,

and approximately 85 countries are at risk, as it is estimated by the WHO (WHO, 2021). It is transmitted in the first place by mosquitoes from the genus *Anopheles*. Africa is the most affected area, the principal vectors of the disease being mosquitoes from the *Anopheles gambiae* complex. The predominant parasite species are *Plasmodium falciparum* and *P. vivax* which causes severe illness and death in humans. The transmission cycle is maintained in a mosquito-human-mosquito contact.

The *P. vivax* has the widest geographical range, provoking illness in temperate and tropical areas (ELDRIDGE AND EDMAN, 2012).

In Romania, malaria was common in the 20th century, with its peak in 1942, the eradication campaign started in 1947 and by 1962 the country became malaria-free (NEGHINA ET AL., 2011). Ever since, a few sporadic imported cases were reported, but the presence of vector species, climate crisis and tourism might lead to the re-emergence of malaria in Romania (IVANESCU ET AL., 2016).

Not only humans are threatened by malaria, but other species like reptiles, rodents or birds as well (ELDRIDGE AND EDMAN, 2012). Avian malaria affects several bird species worldwide and is mostly transmitted by the mosquitoes from the genus *Culex*; the involved agents are *Plasmodium gallinaceum*, *P. hermansi*, *P. relictum*, *P. lophurae*, *P. cathemerium*, *P. circumflexum*, and *P. elongatum* (VALKIUNAS, 2004).

Mosquitoes can transmit bacteria as well, like *Francisella tularensis* which is the causative agent of **tularaemia**. *F. tularensis* is a gram-negative coccobacillus, it can be transmitted by ingestion of contaminated food or water, arthropod bites (including mosquitoes, fleas, lice, midge, ticks or flies) or aerial ways. *Ae. cinereus* and *Oc. excrucians* are proven vectors of this pathogen (PETERSEN ET AL., 2009).

The presence of alien species in combination with the favourable climatic and environmental conditions together with the importation of arboviruses related to travel has resulted in autochthonous transmission of exotic viruses throughout Europe. The establishment of invasive mosquitoes in Europe led to raising concerns about the public health status of arboviruses such as dengue and chikungunya, since there were examples for autochthonous transmission of these pathogens (MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012).

2. Original research

2.1. Invasive mosquito species distribution and ecology in Romania

2.1.1. The invasive Asian tiger mosquito *Aedes albopictus* in Romania: towards a country-wide colonization?

2.1.1.1. Introduction

The ever-growing globalization together with environmental and climate changes facilitates mosquitoes to colonize new territories. Their introductions have been mediated mostly by human activities, in particular the international trade of used tires (BENEDICT ET AL., 2007). Invasive mosquitoes cause new public health concerns, posing a great threat to human well-being and to human and animal health as they are efficient vectors of numerous pathogens. Moreover, they can have also environmental impacts by being highly competitive with local mosquito species, due to their ecological plasticity (PAUPY ET AL., 2009; ANDREADIS AND WOLFE 2010). Currently, five invasive *Aedes* mosquito species are of concern in Europe (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2013a): *Aedes aegypti*, *Ae. albopictus*, *Ae. atropalpus*, *Ae. japonicus*, and *Ae. koreicus*. *Aedes albopictus*, also known as the Asian tiger mosquito, is a rapidly, globally spreading invasive species, originating from Southeast Asia (PETRIĆ ET AL., 2017). *Aedes albopictus* was dispersed worldwide mainly via the trade of used tires and ornamental plants as lucky bamboo and has conquered every continent except Antarctica (PAUPY ET AL., 2009; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013; AKINER ET AL., 2016). *Aedes albopictus* feeds on a large spectrum of hosts, including humans, and it can act as vector of pathogens to both humans and animals. Since very few mosquito species that are native to Europe are capable to transmit chikungunya (PRUDHOMME ET AL., 2019), dengue, or Zika viruses, the establishment of this species or of *Ae. aegypti* makes Europe vulnerable to these arboviruses. Moreover, unlike most native mosquitoes, *Ae. albopictus* has an aggressive daytime biting behaviour, generating a nuisance to humans. In Europe, *Ae. albopictus* has been reported in most countries, with well-established populations mainly in the Mediterranean region (ECDC AND EFSA, 2018). In Romania, the only reported invasive mosquito species is *Ae. albopictus*. Up till now, there was only one established population reported from Bucharest (PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015). Constant monitoring of the mosquito populations is essential, as early detection of new species and potential vectors can prevent serious epidemics, if control

measures are implemented. Assessments can be done as simple faunistic monitoring or active coordinated surveillance in suitable habitats and sites at risk for introduction and spread, such as trade routes, high-ways, airports, harbours, cemeteries, or highly frequented tourist destinations (SCHOLTE AND SCHAFFNER 2007; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013; COLLANTES ET AL., 2015). Romania does not have an active mosquito surveillance program; hence, all the data originate from research-related sampling. Additionally, imported human cases of Zika (FLORESCU ET AL., 2017) and dengue (DINU ET AL., 2015a) in Romania have recently been reported. The aim of our study was to update the knowledge of the distribution of this invasive mosquito species in Romania by investigating new potential locations. This study was supported by VectorNet, the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

2.1.1.2. Materials and methods

To monitor the presence of *Ae. albopictus*, traps were placed in 3–4 different locations in 53 localities in 13 counties (Additional file 1: Table S1.). All traps were placed at sites suitable for container-breeding mosquitoes (ECDC AND EFSA 2018). Between May 2017 and October 2018, CDC-Gravid Traps (GT) model 1712 (John W. Hock Company, Gainesville, Florida, USA), baited with a grass and hay infusion were set up continuously in Bucharest (over a 2-year period) and only for three consecutive days in nine localities in six counties (Ilfov—IL, Giurgiu—GR, Prahova—PH, Constanța—CT, Mehedinți—MH, Tulcea—TL). These traps were operating for 48–72 consecutive hours at every site, along main transport and trade routes, used tire dumps, and residential areas with gardens, urban parks, and playgrounds. In the Danube Delta, we investigated four sites (two in Sulina and two in Sfântu Gheorghe). CDC miniature Light Traps (CDC-LT) (Model512; John W. Hock Company, Gainesville, Florida, USA) baited with CO₂ (dry ice) were set up from dusk to dawn. GT were placed on the ground in partially shaded areas. CDC-LT were hung on trees approximately 1–1.5 m off the ground. Collected adult mosquitoes were counted and identified according to morphological criteria using the key by BECKER ET AL., (2003) and SCHAFFNER ET AL., (2001). Additionally, between 11 and 28 August 2017, 75 ovitraps were placed in various locations in five counties in Transylvania region (Cluj, Alba, Hunedoara, Brașov, and Sibiu) in order to collect mosquito eggs. The ovitraps were placed along main transport routes, abandoned cars, car parking sites, nearby bushes, buildings, channels, and under small bridges. The traps were made out of black plastic buckets (1 l) and pieces (ca. 10 cm × 5 cm × 2 cm) of polystyrene as an oviposition substrate. The buckets were filled with hay infusion and the polystyrene pieces were placed in the buckets. After 17 days, the polystyrene pieces were collected and examined for the presence of mosquito eggs.

The samples were stored in plastic bags at room temperature for over a month and submitted for identification by the MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2014b) to Mabritec AG (Riehen, Switzerland). Furthermore, between 8 and 9 October 2018, four CDC-LT baited with CO₂ (dry ice) were installed in Oradea (Bihar County—BH) at four different sites. The traps were operating from early afternoon to next day's late afternoon. During trap placement, mouth aspirators were used for collecting adult mosquitoes which landed on the trap operators (human landing catches—HLC) approximately 5 min at each site.

2.1.1.3. Results

Aedes albopictus adults and eggs were collected in 10 localities from eight counties across Romania (Figure 2).

Adults

Aedes albopictus adults were collected in nine localities: Bucharest (IF), Petru Rareș (GR), Jilava (IF), Bragadiru (IF), Giurgiu (GR), Ploiești (PH), Constanța (CT), Dubova (MH), and Oradea (BH) (Figure 2). In total, 3559 adult *Ae. albopictus* were captured, of which 2556 were females and 1003 males. In Tulcea (TL) county, *Ae. albopictus* was absent at all eight sites of the three sampled localities (Sulina, Tulcea, and Sfântu Gheorghe).

Eggs

Five *Ae. albopictus* eggs were found only in one location (gas station in Colonia Tâlmaci, Sibiu (SB) county) out of 75 locations where traps were set.

Figure 2. Updated distribution map of *Aedes albopictus* in Romania (2018), dashed line: Romania's counties with abbreviated names; circle, triangular, diamond shapes: trapping sites

2.1.1.4. Discussion

Aedes albopictus is a mosquito species that originates from the Southeast of Asia. Originally, it used natural habitats like tree holes as breeding sites, but due to its rapid adaptive capacity, it acquired the ability to breed in urban and suburban environments, using artificial containers (flower pots, tires, water storage containers, barrels) for oviposition. For example, suburban environments like cemeteries show usually large populations of this species, because they contain numerous flower vases creating yearlong optimal breeding spots (CAPUTO ET AL., 2012; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013). *Aedes albopictus* has proved efficient acclimation, by producing diapausing desiccation- and cold-resistant eggs, as an adaptation to overwintering (HANSON AND CRAIG, 1994). Its behaviour in terms of feeding activity has shown that not only the cold acclimation, but nutrition also plays a key role for the successful colonization of different ecological niches (PAUPY ET AL., 2009; DELATTE ET AL., 2010; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013). *Aedes albopictus* has been involved in mosquito-borne pathogen transmission throughout Europe, mainly in the Mediterranean region where this species is known to transmit arboviruses (chikungunya, dengue) and filariae (*Dirofilaria immitis*, *D. repens*) (PAUPY ET AL., 2009). The tiger mosquito caused chikungunya outbreaks in Italy and France (BONILAUDI ET AL., 2008; DELATTE ET AL., 2010; GRANDADAM ET AL., 2011; DELISLE ET AL., 2015) and autochthonous dengue outbreaks in France (SUCCO ET AL., 2016), Croatia (GOSSNER ET AL., 2018a), and Spain (ECDC, 2018a). In Europe, the first record of *Ae. albopictus* was reported from Albania in August 1979 (ADHAMI AND REITER, 1998) and later on from Italy (SABATINI ET AL., 1990). Subsequently, the species has rapidly invaded new territories, including most of the Mediterranean region (SCHOLTE AND SCHAFFNER, 2007; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). In Romania, this species was first found in 2012 in a neighbourhood of southwest Bucharest, during an entomological investigation, when a total of 45 adult *Ae. albopictus* were collected. In the following years, *Ae. albopictus* became established in Bucharest with a permanent breeding population (PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015). Our study confirms the establishment of *Ae. albopictus* in seven other counties by 2018. Our updated distribution data shows that the lowland southeast and western regions of the country host several established populations of *Ae. albopictus*. We also report for the first time the presence of *Ae. albopictus* inside the Carpathian Mountains arch (the historical region of Transylvania, in Sibiu county). New sampling sites should be kept under observation in order to monitor the invasion of *Ae. albopictus* and potentially other invasive *Aedes* species, which are known to be present in neighbouring countries like *Ae. koreicus* and *Ae. japonicus* in Hungary (KURUCZ ET AL., 2016; SEIDEL ET AL., 2016a) and *Ae. japonicus* in Serbia (KAVRAN ET AL., 2019). These new records from Romania show the continuous spreading

tendency of the tiger mosquito. They also highlight the need for surveillance, not only to further assess the species' distribution and abundance but also to assess pathogen transmission risk related to that vector species.

2.1.2. Emergence of the invasive Asian bush mosquito, *Aedes (Finlaya) japonicus japonicus*, in an urban area, Romania

2.1.2.1. Introduction

The Asian bush mosquito, *Aedes (Finlaya) japonicus japonicus* (TEOBALD, 1901) (Diptera: *Culicidae*), is naturally occurring in Southeast Asia (Palaeartic Japan, Korea, parts of China, Taiwan and Russia) (TANAKA ET AL., 1979). In the past 3 decades, it has become invasive in various parts of the world, including Central Europe. Its invasion was mostly mediated by anthropogenic movements. Like the related species, *Aedes albopictus*, it has travelled throughout the continents mainly via the trade of used tires, which is considered the most important introduction means of these container breeding species (REITER AND SPERGER, 1987; SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2003). The first report of *Ae. japonicus* occurring outside its endemic area came from New Zealand (LAIRD ET AL., 1994), where during an entomological survey, in 1993, the species was found in a shipment of used tires together with *Ae. albopictus*. Later on, in 1998, it was reported in the USA (New York and New Jersey) (PEYTON ET AL., 1999) and Canada (SAVIGNAC ET AL., 2002). The first record of the species in Europe dates back to 2000, when two larvae were collected in used tires in a storage yard from a metropolitan area of France (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2003). Later, the species was eradicated, just to return and establish a decade later (KREBS ET AL., 2014). *Ae. japonicus* is showing rapid expansion throughout Europe, and in less than 2 decades it has managed to become established in 13 countries (Table 1).

Table1.
Status of *Aedes japonicus* in Europe

Year of first observation	Country	Current status	References
2000	France	Established	SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2003
2002	Belgium	Established	VERSTEIRT ET AL., 2009
2008	Switzerland	Established	SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2009
2008	Germany	Established	SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2009
2011	Austria	Established	SEIDEL ET AL., 2012
2011	Slovenia	Established	SEIDEL ET AL., 2012
2012	The Netherlands	Established	IBÁÑEZ-JUSTICIA ET AL. 2014
2012	Hungary	Established	SEIDEL ET AL., 2016
2013	Croatia	Established	KLOBUČAR ET AL. 2019
2015	Lichtenstein	Established	SEIDEL ET AL., 2016
2015	Italy	Established	MONTARSI ET AL. 2019
2017	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Introduced	JANSSEN ET AL., 2020
2018	Serbia	Introduced	JANSSEN ET AL., 2020
2018	Spain	Established	ERITJA ET AL., 2019
2018	Luxembourg	Established	SCHAFFNER AND RIES, 2019
2020	Romania	Introduced	Current study

Its success lays in the species' ecological flexibility, its ability to adapt to new climatic conditions and larval habitats, and its capacity to overwinter (KAUFMAN AND FONSECA, 2014). Its tolerance to lower temperatures is responsible for a wider distribution range compared to other invasive species, indicating a bigger colonizing potential in the future (MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). Its invasion is supported by globalization; the excessive trade of used tires and increasing tourism both play a considerable role in the colonization process (CUNZE ET AL., 2016). However, *Ae. japonicus* seems to prefer rural habitats over urban sites (BARTLETT-HEALY ET AL., 2012). It uses different types of natural and artificial larval habitats: tree-holes, rock pools, ponds, ditches, rain water pools, tires, cans, bird baths, water barrels, buckets, etc. The larvae usually feed on decaying organic matter and algae (KAUFMAN AND FONSECA, 2014). It is often found together and competes for the breeding sites with other container-breeding mosquitoes (ARMISTEAD ET AL., 2014). Therefore, *Ae. japonicus* can be a challenge for local mosquito populations. Although *Ae. japonicus* is not considered a major disease vector, it is known to transmit several flaviviruses (i.e. West Nile, Japanese encephalitis, chikungunya, dengue, La Crosse, Eastern equine encephalitis, St. Louis encephalitis, Rift Valley fever, Zika and Usutu viruses) and nematodes such as *Dirofilaria repens* and *D. immitis* (TAKASHIMA AND ROSEN, 1989; SARDELIS AND TURELL, 2001; SARDELIS AND TURELL, 2002; SARDELIS ET AL., 2002a; SARDELIS ET AL., 2002b; SARDELIS ET AL., 2003; SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2011; TURELL ET AL., 2013; HUBER ET AL., 2014; WAGNER ET AL., 2018; SILAGHI ET AL., 2017; ABBO ET AL., 2020). According to the ECDC's Annual Epidemiological Report for 2018 (ECDC, 2019b), Romania has a significant number of cases of West

Nile encephalitis, with the highest numbers in 2018 (267 confirmed cases with 43 deaths). Recently, imported cases of dengue (DINU ET AL., 2015a), Zika (FLORESCU ET AL., 2017), yellow fever (ECDC, 2018b) and chikungunya (JAVELLE ET AL., 2019) were reported in Romania. With the generally increased tourism (with the exception of 2020 COVID-19-related travel bans and restrictions), the emergence of exotic diseases is an ever-present risk. This, in connection to the spread of invasive mosquitoes (FĂLCUȚĂ ET AL., 2020), is causing a permanent epidemiological concern. The airports and harbours seem to be particularly sensitive regions for the introduction and establishment of exotic mosquito species like *Ae. japonicus*; therefore, they need careful observation (IBAÑEZ-JUSTICIA ET AL., 2017; REASER ET AL., 2020). For this reason, we conducted a targeted surveillance study to detect adult and immature stages of invasive mosquitoes at an international airport in Romania as part of harmonized mosquito monitoring (www.aedescost.eu/aimsurv). This article is the first report of *Ae. japonicus* in Romania.

2.1.2.2. Materials and methods

Study area and design

An entomological survey was conducted for 3 months (between 30 June and 29 September 2020) at the 'Avram Iancu' International Airport in Cluj-Napoca, Romania, to detect invasive *Aedes* species (Figure 3). The study was part of a coordinated Pan-European initiative within the framework of *Aedes* Invasive Mosquitoes COST Action (www.aedescost.eu/aimsurv). One BG-Sentinel trap baited with BG-Lure (Biogents AG, Regensburg, Germany) and dry ice was set at the airport. The dry ice was placed in a special storage unit inside the trap, which allowed it to sublimate gradually, releasing gaseous carbon dioxide (CO₂) while the trap was operating. Additionally, five ovitraps were also set up at the investigated area and positioned approximately 50 m apart to increase the sensitivity of detection.

**Figure 3. Location of the study area in Cluj-Napoca, Romania.
Red triangles indicate the sampling locations**

The ovitraps were represented by 1-l black plastic recipients filled with tap water (approximately 700 ml) and a piece of polystyrene (ca. 10 cm×5 cm×2 cm) as an oviposition substrate. The traps were set in the airport apron areas where aircraft were parked while on land and by selecting areas where vegetation was present. Each week, the BG- Sentinel trap was operating for 1 night (approximately 15 h), usually from Monday evening (7 p.m.) until Tuesday morning (10 a.m.) when mosquitoes were collected. Ovitrap were permanently in place, and the oviposition substrate was checked for the presence of eggs and replaced every second week. The eggs were later hatched at the University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Cluj-Napoca's insectary by submerging the polystyrene pieces in tap water in a controlled environment, where the room temperature was set at 30 °C and the humidity at 55%. Larvae were fed with TetraMin Mini Granules (Tetra GmbH, Germany). Moreover, another female mosquito resembling an invasive species was accidentally caught inside a building in Cluj-Napoca's central area, spontaneously and unrelated to the study design.

Morphological identification

Adult mosquitoes were collected and identified using the morphological key by BECKER ET AL. (2010). The adult mosquitoes which emerged from eggs were identified using the key in the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control's

guidelines for the surveillance of the invasive mosquitoes in Europe (ECDC, 2012). The mosquitoes were cooled to 4 °C in a refrigerator and identified.

Molecular assessment

For the adult mosquitoes for which the morphological examination to the species level was impossible because of incomplete body parts, a molecular identification protocol was applied. The DNA was extracted individually from each female mosquito specimen using ISOLATE II Genomic DNA Kit (Bioline Meridian Bioscience, Luckenwalde Germany), according to the manufacturer's instructions and stored at -20 °C. PCR amplification of the cytochrome c oxidase subunit 1 (COI) gene region (~660 bp) was performed in 25 µl reaction volume, containing 12.5 µl Red PCR Master- mix (Rovalab GmbH, Teltow, Germany), 6.5 µl of ultra- pure water, 1 µl (10 pmol/µl) of each of the two primers LCO1490 (5'-GGTCAACAAATCATAAAGATATTG G-3') and HCO2198 (5'-TAAACTTCAGGGTGACCA AAAATCA-3') (FOLMER ET AL., 1994) and 4 µl aliquot of isolated DNA. One negative control (ultra-pure water) was included. The PCR was performed using the T1000TM Thermal Cycler (Bio-Rad, London, UK) with the following conditions: initial denaturation at 95 °C for 5 min, followed by 40 cycles of denaturation at 95 °C for 45 s, annealing at 47 °C for 45 s and extension at 72 °C for 45 s, with a final extension at 72 °C for 5 min. Amplification products were visualized by electrophoresis on 1.5% agarose gel stained with ECO Safe 20,000× Nucleic Acid Staining Solution (Pacific Image Electronics, New Taipei, Taiwan), and their molecular weight was assessed by comparison to a molecular marker (O'GeneRulerTM 100 bp DNA Ladder, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, MA, USA). PCR products were purified using the ISOLATE II PCR and Gel Kit (Bioline Meridian Bio-science, Luckenwalde Germany) and sent for sequencing (Macrogen Europe, Amsterdam, The Netherlands). The sequences were compared with those available in GenBankTM using Basic Local Alignments Tool (BLAST) analyses. All sequences were analysed and edited using Geneious® 4.85 software (KEARSE ET AL., 2012).

Mapping

The maps were generated using QGIS 3.6.2 software (<http://www.qgis.org>).

2.1.2.3. Results

Mosquito eggs were found only on 24 August 2020 when 26 eggs were collected from one of the five traps (46.782228° N, 23.686877° E). The rearing procedure resulted in seven adult mosquitoes, two males and five females (Figure 4). The COI sequence analysis showed a similarity of 100% with other *Ae. japonicus* specimens from Germany (accession numbers KF211480.1, KP076236.1, KP076252.1).

Figure 4. Specimen of *Aedes japonicus* collected at the airport in 2020: a lateral view; b Scutum

No adult *Ae. japonicus* were sampled in the BG-Sentinel trap, but females and males of *Culex pipiens* and *Ochlerotatus caspius* were collected (results not shown). On 15 October, another female of *Ae. japonicus* was caught accidentally inside a building in Cluj-Napoca's central area (46.776425° N, 23.593782° E). For this specimen the morphological examination to species level was impossible because of incomplete body parts; therefore, molecular analysis was performed to identify the species. The specimen showed a 100% match with specimens from Austria (accession number MN103386.1), the USA (accession number GQ254794.1), Japan (accession number LC341253.1), Germany (accession number KP076233.1, KP076256.1, KX260924.1, KX260920.1), Canada (accession number MN058628.1) and Italy (accession number MK265686.1, MK265689.1, MK265688.1). All sequences were submitted to the Gen-Bank database under the accession numbers MW509625 and MW509626.

2.1.2.4. Discussion

Over the past few decades, five mosquito species have become invasive in Europe (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2013a). Among these, three species in particular are of concern and seem to be rapidly expanding their range: *Ae. japonicus*, *Ae. albopictus* and *Ae. koreicus*. Such invasive mosquitoes represent a significant ecological and epidemiological threat generating one of the most challenging public health issues nowadays. To date, in Romania only *Ae. albopictus* has been found and is considered established (FĂLCUȚĂ ET AL., 2020; PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015). Mostly because these invasive mosquitoes share similar niches (KAUFMAN AND FONSECA, 2014), the establishment of other invasive species is expected. A climatic model by CUNZE ET AL. (2016) predicted that *Ae. japonicus* could also occur in the inner part of the

Carpathian Basin under similar conditions as other established populations in Europe. These predictions match with our findings as well, although we cannot yet confirm this species' establishment. As *Ae. japonicus* is assumed to be adapted to temperate climatic conditions (KAUFMAN AND FONSECA, 2014), further surveillance should be continued to establish the species status in Romania. Compared to other invasive species, *Ae. japonicus* has an advantage because it has a longer activity period over the year, its life-cycle is multivoltine and it overwinters as eggs (KAUFMAN AND FONSECA, 2014; BOVA ET AL., 2019). Blood meal analysis in wild-caught females showed that they prefer feeding on humans and other mammalian hosts (such as horses, deer, opossums, chipmunks), but also on birds. Females are not considered aggressive biters; however, they readily feed on hosts and they show crepuscular activity (KAMPEN AND WERNER, 2014). *Aedes japonicus* is part of a species group with four allopatric subspecies, *Ae. j. japonicus*, *Ae. j. shintienensis*, *Ae. j. yaeyamensis* and *Ae. j. amamiensis* (TANAKA ET AL., 1979; KAUFMAN AND FONSECA, 2014). They share similar biology and morphology, but only *Ae. j. japonicus* has become invasive. *Aedes koreicus*, a closely related sibling species invasive in Europe, is naturally endemic to East Asia (TANAKA ET AL., 1979). The present study reports for the first time the presence of *Ae. japonicus* in Romania (Figure 5). Moreover, it represents the first invasive species of mosquito detected in Cluj-Napoca, the second most populous city of Romania (CAZAN ET AL., 2020). Due to the study design, adult and egg trappings were limited to suitable habitats inside the airport. Further studies and long-term surveillance are required for clarifying the introduced or established status of this mosquito species. Due to its climatic and environmental conditions, Romania has a high probability of being invaded by *Ae. japonicus* in the future. Distribution data show that attention should be paid also to the possible presence of another invasive species, *Ae. koreicus*, which is present in Hungary (KURUCZ ET AL., 2016). Like the closely related *Ae. japonicus*, *Ae. koreicus* is also a container-breeding mosquito species that is well adapted to temperate climates. A more accurate picture of the threats that these invasive species pose could be the fact that *Ae. albopictus*, after only 8 years from its first finding in Bucharest (PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015), has now become established in eight counties in Romania (FĂLCUȚĂ ET AL., 2020).

Figure 5. Current known distribution of *Aedes japonicus* in Romania (counties shown in green with confirmed absence according to the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control and European Food Safety Authority. Mosquito maps [internet]. Stockholm: ECDC; 2020. Available from: <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/aedes-japonicus-current-known-distribution-may-2020>)

These new findings highlight the need for control measures to be implemented in the affected areas, and further surveillance should be carried out. A first step in the management of invasive species in Romania could be the implementation of regular entomological surveillance to keep these species under control and educating citizens about the reduction of potential breeding sites and involving them into surveillance programmes.

2.1.2.5. Conclusions

We are reporting for the first time to our knowledge the presence of *Ae. japonicus* in Romania. This study was designed to be part of a harmonized Pan-European surveillance coordinated by the AIM-Cost program. Our findings draw attention to the dissemination of invasive mosquito species, which, together with increased global travel and trade, as well as climate change, presents a significant risk to the public health system and economy. Invasive species expand their geographic range steadily, increasing the circulation of vector-borne diseases globally. We

recommend that future investigations should be carried out in Romania and elsewhere to assess the distribution of invasive mosquito species and make local authorities aware of the situation so they can carry out regular surveillance and mosquito control in the affected areas.

2.2. Molecular phylogeny based on microsatellite markers and insecticide resistance in *Aedes albopictus*

2.2.1. Genotyping of various microsatellite loci shows multiple introduction events of *Aedes albopictus* (Diptera: Culicidae) in Romania

2.2.1.1. Introduction

Globalization and modern transportation methods have facilitated the transcontinental dispersal of invasive *Aedes* mosquito species (TATEM ET AL., 2006; PAUPY ET AL., 2009; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013). Anthropogenic movements and the transportation of goods became the most common mechanism of invasion of the medically important mosquito vectors, such as *Aedes albopictus* (REITER AND SPRENGER 1987, TATEM ET AL., 2006; BENEDICT ET AL., 2007). Naturally occurring in tropical and subtropical regions of Southeast Asia and the Pacific, *Ae. albopictus*, also known as the Asian tiger mosquito, soon became a worldwide threat to public health, native biodiversity and a major socioeconomic burden by being an efficient vector of disease transmission, as rapidly colonized new territories throughout the world (KNUDSEN, 1995; TATEM ET AL., 2006; BENEDICT ET AL., 2007; PAUPY ET AL., 2009; KRAEMER ET AL., 2015). Potent to transmit several emerging arboviruses including Zika- (ZIKV), dengue- (DENV) and chikungunya virus (CHIKV), and nematodes like *Dirofilaria immitis* and *D. repens* (KNUDSEN 1995; CANCRINI ET AL., 2003a, CANCRINI ET AL., 2003b, TATEM ET AL., 2006; PAUPY ET AL., 2009, MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013; SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2013b; KRAEMER ET AL., 2015), it poses a major risk to human and animal health. Its adaptability and ecological plasticity elevated this species into the top hundred worst invasive species' list, its status being the most invasive mosquito species in the world (Global Invasive Species Database, http://www.iucngisd.org/gisd/100_worst.php) (LOWE ET AL., 2000; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013).

Since its first report in Albania in 1979 (ADHAMI AND REITER, 1998), it has colonized over 25 European countries, and it is continuously expanding its territory (ECDC, 2022). Due to its aggressive daytime-biting behaviour and by being a highly anthropogenic species, *Ae. albopictus* has adapted well to urban environments. As a consequence, it acts as a bridge vector for zoonotic pathogens (KNUDSEN, 1995; PAUPY ET AL., 2009; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013), furthermore it is a primary vector for arboviruses like chikungunya-, causing serious outbreaks throughout Europe, but mainly in the Mediterranean region. For instance, in Italy it was involved in two major chikungunya outbreaks (2007 and 2017) (ANGELINI ET AL., 2007; REZZA ET AL., 2007; VENTURI ET AL., 2017), but also in France (2010, 2014, 2017) (GRANDADAM ET AL., 2011; DELISLE ET AL., 2015; VENTURI ET AL., 2017). Autochthonous dengue transmission linked to *Ae. albopictus* were reported in France (2010, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2018, 2019) (LA RUCHE ET AL., 2010; MARCHAND ET AL., 2013; SUCCO ET AL., 2016; ECDC 2018, ECDC 2019), as well as in Croatia (2010) (GJENERO-MARGAN ET AL., 2011), in Portugal (2012) (ALVES ET AL., 2013), in Spain (2018, 2019) (ECDC, 2018; ECDC, 2019a), and in Italy (2020) (LAZZARINI ET AL., 2020). Furthermore, recently autochthonous ZIKV cases were reported from France (GIRON ET AL., 2019). The first detection of *Ae. albopictus* in Romania dates back to 2012, when a general survey conducted in Bucharest and its surrounding areas led to the discovery of adult and immature stages of the species (PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015). Since the first report it has become established in 19 counties throughout the country with permanent breeding populations (FĂLCUȚĂ ET AL., 2020; current study). Its rapid dissemination raises a major public health concern, as previously several imported cases of Zika (FLORESCU ET AL., 2017) and dengue (DINU ET AL., 2015a) have been detected in Romania. Hence very few mosquito species that are native to Europe are susceptible to transmit chikungunya-, dengue-, or Zika viruses (PRUDHOMME ET AL., 2019), the dissemination and the establishment of *Ae. albopictus* makes Europe - and continental climate countries like Romania - vulnerable to arbovirus infestations and to future outbreaks. Not only its vector competence, but also its susceptibility to insecticide resistance raise awareness of the species importance. The growing populations of *Ae. albopictus* in Romania could lead to the manifestation of new phenotypes and the increase of mutated allele frequencies, which can facilitate their resistance to insecticides and to further grow their vector capacity. In Romania Pyrethroids are the most widely used insecticides, however it is known that their intensive use increases the risk for triggering insecticide resistance among mosquito populations (HEMINGWAY AND RANSON, 2000; HEMINGWAY ET AL., 2016; BALABANIDOU ET AL., 2018). In a previous study several populations of *Ae. albopictus* from Romania were screened for two types of *kdr* mutation of the voltage gated sodium channel, F1534C and

V1016G; both mutations have been found in Bucharest (PITCHLER ET AL., 2022; VALADAS ET AL., in prep). Understanding this species' genetic diversity and population structure could lead us to decipher their origin and invasion biology, and would give us a tool for designing efficient mosquito control strategies, but also to identify epidemiological risks and to reduce pathogen transmission. In order to evaluate the genetic relationships between *Ae. albopictus* populations in Romania, and to learn about the introduction events that led to this species establishment, we conducted a study based on 12 polymorphic microsatellite markers previously used in similar studies (MANNI ET AL., 2015; MANNI ET AL., 2017). Furthermore, to improve the accuracy of our data, we have analysed the mitochondrial *cox1* gene together with microsatellite data.

2.2.1.2. Materials and methods

Mosquito sampling

Collecting samples had been conducted in two consecutive years with two trapping methods. Between 8th and 15th of September 2019, during an entomological survey in Port Constanța-Agigea, Constanța county, 20 ovitraps were placed alongside a road between shipping docs, from which 9 traps were found positive with *Ae. albopictus* eggs and larvae. The traps were standard ovitraps (1L) with small pieces of polystyrene (5 cm × 5 cm × 2 cm) as oviposition substrate. The eggs were hatched at the University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Cluj-Napoca's insectary, adults were identified based on morphological key by BECKER ET AL., (2010). A few adult specimens were stored in 70% ethanol, and stored at 4°C. Furthermore, an entomological survey was conducted for three months (between 28th of July and 18th of September 2020) at multiple cities in Romania (Agigea, Satu Mare, Caracal, Ploșoru, Drobeta Turnu Severin, Bucharest, Giurgiu, Pitești, Timișoara, Arad, Oradea), to detect the presence of invasive *Aedes* species. For that purpose, we have searched for biting adults in cemeteries using human landing collection (HLC) technique to collect mosquitoes. In each site we have selected multiple sampling points where we have been collecting adult mosquitoes for 5-10 minutes. The sampling sites were selected by the following criteria: suitable habitat for mosquitoes (the presence of the vegetation, permanent or semi-permanent water bodies- river streams near the cemeteries, flower vases filled with water etc.;;) along transport routes. The cemeteries were chosen based on the Google maps satellite images, where these conditions were given. Among the sampling sites were suburban, urban and rural areas. The collected specimens were stored at -20°C till further analysis.

Mosquito identification

Adult mosquitoes were identified based on morphological criteria by using a key for invasive mosquitoes by ECDC (2012). In total 495 adult mosquitoes were collected: 232 males and 263 females, from which we selected 180 specimens from 6 localities: Satu Mare, Oradea, Timișoara, Ploșoru, Bucharest and Constanța (30 each- 15 females and 15 males).

DNA extraction

Total DNA was extracted from whole individual mosquitoes with two different methods: the CTAB method adapted from WEEKS ET AL. (2000) and by using the DNeasy blood and tissue kit ("Purification of Total DNA from Animal Tissues" as found in DNeasy Blood & Tissue Handbook, Qiagen, Valencia, CA; July 2006). The samples that initially were stored in ethanol were dried previously to these procedures, by placing the mosquitoes on a filter paper till the ethanol has evaporated (approximately 10 min). For the CTAB 2% Buffer 1M Tris HCL (pH 8.0) together with 0.5M EDTA (pH 8.0), NaCl (1.4 mM final concentration), 2% CTAB (Cetyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide) and sterile distilled water were used. Steps were followed as written in protocol (WEEKS ET AL., 2000). The DNA was eluted in 200µl of distilled water, and samples were stored at -20°C. Additionally 30µl of aliquots were prepared in 0.5mL tubes for further analysis and stored at 4°C. In total 120 samples were extracted with this method. For the remaining samples we used the commercially available DNA isolation kit (Qiagen DNeasy) following the manufacturer's recommendations. Samples were incubated at 56°C for tissue lysis with 20 µl proteinase K and 180 µl ATL lysis buffer (from the DNeasy kit) for 3 hours. After the spin-column purification the samples were eluted in 200 µl Buffer AE (from the kit), each tube was labelled with a unique code and stored at -20°C. Additionally 30µl of aliquots were prepared in 0.5mL tubes.

Amplification of mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) and sequence analysis

Amplification of mitochondrial COI was carried out by using universal primers LCO1490 and HCO2198 for the polymerase chain reaction adapted from protocols by Folmer ET AL., (1994) for a total of 180 samples from Bucharest, Satu Mare, Constanța, Oradea, Timișoara and Ploșoru localities (30 each). For the PCR reaction we used 1x GoTaq Buffer, 1.5 mM MgCl₂, 0.2 mM dNTPs, 0.3 µM of each primer (forward and reverse) with 0.04U/µl of GoTaq DNA polymerase and 1µl of DNA template. The reaction's final volume was 25µl. The PCR programme consisted of the initial denaturation on 94°C for 1 min, followed by 40 cycles of 94°C - 1 min denaturation, 50°C - 1 min 30 s of annealing and 72°C - 1 min 30 s of extension,

with 72°C – 10 min of final extension. The PCR products were visualized in a 2% agarose gel. For the sequencing PCR the same mixture was prepared with both forward and reverse primers. The PCR products were purified using the Grisp Exo/SAP Go kit and sent to Stab Vida Lda (Portugal) for sequencing together with primers. Alignments were created in BioEdit (7.2.5 version, HALL, 1999). Multiple sequence alignments and phylogenetic analysis were performed using partial COI gene sequences of the mosquito isolates obtained from Romanian samples in Mega-X software (version 10.2.2; Arizona State University, Tempe, AZ, USA) (KUMAR ET AL., 2018).

All data is available upon request from the author (Additional file 2: Dataset S1).

Microsatellite PCR analysis and genetic diversity analysis

Genetic polymorphism was assessed at twelve microsatellite loci: Aealbm1c2, Aealbm1c3, Aealbm1c4, Aealbm1c5, Aealbm1c6, Aealbm1c7, Aealbm1c8, Aealbm1c9, Aealbm1c10, Aealbm1c11, Aealbm1c12 and Aealbm1c13 (Additional file 3: Table S2) which are part of larger groups of loci that have previously been described for genetic typing of *Ae. albopictus* (BEEBE ET AL., 2013; MANNI ET AL., 2015; MANNI ET AL., 2017).

PCR was prepared in 96 well plates, DNA was amplified in 1900µl reaction mixes (mix per well: 20µl) containing 400µl of 1x GoTaq buffer, 1.5 mM MgCl₂, 300µl of 2 mM dNTP, 40µl of each primer, 20µl of 0.05 U/µl GoTaq DNA polymerase and 980µl deionized water. The end of each forward primer was labelled with a fluorescent dye (FAM, HEX or NED) (Sigma, USA). Cycling conditions were as follows: 3 min at 94°C, followed by 30 cycles of 94°C for 30 s, annealing temperature 57-60°C (each primer has a specific annealing temperature- Additional file 3: Table S2) for 30 s, 72°C for 30 s, with a final extension at 72°C for 10 min. For the sequencing another two 96 well plates were prepared with 9 µl of Formamide and 1 µl of each PCR product, to obtain a total volume of 12µl. The plates were sealed and centrifuged, each plate was provided with a specific identification number, then shipped to Yale University for fragment analysis. Microsatellite alleles were scored with GeneMarker software (SoftGenetics, LLC). Results were analysed using GeneMarker software (version 1.85Val, SoftGenetics, LLC), GENEPOP (version 4.7.5, ROUSSET, 2008), F-Stat (version 2.9.4, GOUDET, 2005) and NeEstimator V2 (DO ET AL., 2014). Alleles for each marker were scored manually in the program GeneMarker (HOLLAND AND PARSON, 2011). To test the population genetic variability, we have calculated allelic richness for each population and locus, and the inbreeding coefficient (Fis) by using F-Stat. Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) and linkage disequilibrium (LD) tests were computed using GENEPOP, as well as observed (Ho) and expected (He) heterozygosity. For structure analysis of the samples, pairwise

F_{ST} values with 99% confidence intervals (1000 bootstraps over loci) were calculated between population pairs using F-Stat. In addition, isolation by distance (IBD) was tested using Mantel test in GENEPOP. A Bayesian cluster analysis was performed - based on multilocus genotyping data - using the programme STRUCTURE 2.3.4 (PRITCHARD ET AL., 2000). Parameters were set as follows: admixture model was chosen with a Markov Chain Monte Carlo algorithm set for 100,000 iterations with 100,000 burn-ins, and 10 runs for each value of K (1-10). The optimal K value (estimated number of genetically distinct groups) was calculated with STRUCTURE's online extension STRUCTURE HARVESTER (<http://taylor0.biology.ucla.edu/structureHarvester/>) (EARL AND VONHOLT, 2012) which implements the EVANNO ET AL., (2005) Delta K method. Additionally, the number of f_0 migrants were calculated using GeneClass 2.0 (PIRY ET AL., 2004).

2.2.1.3. Results

Mitochondrial DNA and phylogenetic analysis

Multiple sequence alignments were performed using partial COI sequences of the mosquito isolates in Mega-X software. The gap containing codons were trimmed and homogenous patterns among the groups and uniform rates among the sites were assumed. The sequence alignment showed two haplotypes with only one variation (A/G) in Ploșoru population. The polymorphism occurred in two samples from the same population (samples ROPL09 and ROPL23). The phylogenetic analysis was carried out for COI sequences, in addition the obtained sequences were compared with *Ae. albopictus* COI isolates previously updated to GenBank; a phylogenetic tree was constructed by using the Neighbor-Joining method using the Tamura 3-parameter of Mega-X software. The robustness of each node was estimated using 1000 bootstrap replications under the Neighbor-Joining statistical method (Additional file 4: Figure 1). The phylogenetic analysis showed that the Romanian samples are closely related to each other and to *Ae. albopictus* populations from Italy (KX383916, KX383921, KX383923, KX383929, KX383933, JX679374, JX679376, JX679378), Brazil (MK575475), Greece (KX383932), Albania (KX383930, KX383931), China (KR068634, KX383934), Portugal (MN513355) and the Philippines (KX809761- KX809764).

Microsatellites

Genotypes at 12 microsatellite loci were assessed in a total of 120 *Ae. albopictus* mosquitoes collected from six different localities (Bucharest, Ploșoru, Timișoara, Oradea, Satu Mare, Constanța) from Romania. Allelic frequencies for each locus were computed using GENEPOP, expected numbers of homozygotes or heterozygotes were computed using Levene's correction, F_{is} computed as in WEIR AND

COCKERHAM (1984); also as in ROBERTSON AND HILL (1984). HWE tests conducted for each locus in each population showed H_e greater than H_o in 70,14% of the conducted tests (Table 2). In locus MIC4, MIC5, MIC7, MIC10, MIC11, MIC12 and MIC13 the H_e was always higher than H_o , in the case of MIC6 and MIC8 the H_o was significantly higher. In the case of MIC2, MIC3, MIC9 there was no difference. In all the populations the H_e was always higher than the H_o . The HW probability test showed significant values in all loci except MIC7, in Bucharest population in the case of MIC2, MIC5, MIC6, MIC9, MIC12; in Constanța for MIC3, MIC4, MIC5, MIC9, MIC10, MIC12 and MIC13; in the case of Oradea significant differences were found in the case of MIC3, MIC4, MIC5, MIC9, MIC11, MIC12 and MIC13; in Ploșoru population MIC5, MIC8, MIC9 and MIC12; for Satu Mare MIC2, MIC4, MIC12, MIC13 and for Timișoara MIC6, MIC10, MIC12 and MIC13 (Table 2). None of the loci showed significant deviation from HWE following Bonferroni correction.

Table 2.

Number of alleles, allele richness (Rs), observed (Ho) and expected heterozygosity (He), inbreeding coefficient (FIS), estimated frequency of null alleles (r), HWE P-value calculated per locus and per populations, and '-' missing values shown.

Population		MIC2	MIC3	MIC4	MIC5	MIC6	MIC7	MIC8	MIC9	MIC10	MIC11	MIC12	MIC13
ROBU	No allele	4	8	1	5	3	2	4	6	2	4	9	1
	Rs	1.666	1.686	1.000	1.738	1.398	1.500	1.821	1.761	1.333	1.867	1.813	1.000
	Ho	0.333	0.500	0.000	0.233	0.100	0.033	0.667	0.333	0.033	0.067	0.533	0.333
	He	0.622	0.640	0.000	0.320	0.199	0.333	0.110	0.482	0.333	0.087	0.732	0.459
	Fis	0.468	0.222	-	0.279	0.506	0.000	0.429	0.314	0.000	0.273	0.275	-
	r	0.161	0.058	-	0.094	0.165	0.000	0.131	0.126	0.816	0.000	0.143	-
	P value	0.984	0.913	-	0.954	0.978	-	0.971	0.989	-	0.933	1.000	-
ROCO	No allele	3	7	7	6	6	7	8	7	2	5	6	4
	Rs	1.459	1.745	1.761	1.758	1.599	1.773	1.820	1.706	1.271	1.742	1.770	1.430
	Ho	0.333	0.933	0.333	0.500	0.567	0.867	0.833	0.800	0.000	0.567	0.467	0.200
	He	0.459	0.720	0.634	0.657	0.500	0.744	0.820	0.682	0.117	0.692	0.693	0.387
	Fis	0.278	-0.303	0.479	0.242	-0.138	-0.163	-0.016	-0.176	1.000	0.184	0.331	0.489
	r	0.078	0.000	0.532	0.083	0.004	0.053	0.030	0.000	0.919	0.082	0.143	0.307
	P value	0.954	0.000	1.000	0.955	0.206	0.519	0.601	0.073	1.000	0.979	1.000	1.000
RODE	No allele	4	10	7	11	7	7	7	6	2	5	11	3
	Rs	1.601	1.790	1.782	1.866	1.645	1.754	1.822	1.731	1.328	1.677	1.850	1.298
	Ho	0.600	1.000	0.500	0.800	0.733	0.600	0.833	0.967	0.133	0.400	0.467	0.067
	He	0.601	0.790	0.756	0.866	0.623	0.729	0.794	0.731	0.219	0.677	0.850	0.179
	Fis	0.001	-0.271	0.343	0.078	-0.180	0.180	-0.050	-0.330	0.397	0.414	0.100	0.634
	r	0.000	0.000	0.173	0.034	0.000	0.051	0.000	0.000	0.836	0.181	0.057	0.242
	P value	0.427	0.000	1.000	0.792	0.055	0.897	0.186	0.000	0.992	0.989	0.992	1.000
ROPL	No allele	3	5	6	7	5	4	8	4	1	5	7	1
	Rs	1.568	1.669	1.879	1.825	1.605	1.475	1.825	1.651	1.000	1.822	1.762	1.000
	Ho	0.667	0.600	0.167	0.300	0.633	0.267	0.267	0.400	-	0.100	0.533	-
	He	0.530	0.647	0.205	0.495	0.484	0.348	0.357	0.586	-	0.137	0.762	-
	Fis	-0.263	0.074	0.200	0.401	-0.318	0.238	0.262	0.321	0.397	0.294	0.303	-
	r	0.000	0.015	0.061	0.170	0.000	0.086	0.142	0.113	-	0.085	0.114	-
	P value	0.061	0.741	0.936	0.998	0.013	0.970	0.968	0.966	-	0.972	0.983	-
ROSM	No allele	3	8	6	6	8	6	8	6	4	4	9	5
	Rs	1.538	1.800	1.769	1.512	1.782	1.717	1.767	1.695	1.554	1.685	1.804	1.747
	Ho	0.733	0.700	0.533	0.633	0.967	0.667	0.900	0.500	0.500	0.533	0.733	0.167
	He	0.538	0.774	0.769	0.512	0.782	0.693	0.742	0.641	0.554	0.663	0.804	0.548
	Fis	-0.371	0.097	0.310	-0.242	-0.240	0.039	-0.218	0.233	0.099	0.198	0.089	0.701
	r	0.000	0.233	0.134	0.000	0.000	0.003	0.000	0.079	0.322	0.070	0.063	0.381
	P value	0.010	0.796	1.000	0.019	0.005	0.703	0.010	0.949	0.963	0.941	0.986	1.000
ROTI	No allele	3	11	9	9	7	5	7	6	3	8	10	5
	Rs	1.606	1.780	1.834	1.881	1.631	1.462	1.781	1.779	1.552	1.803	1.892	1.712
	Ho	0.667	0.900	0.733	0.667	0.500	0.467	0.800	0.800	0.300	0.500	0.500	0.100
	He	0.585	0.780	0.750	0.763	0.610	0.447	0.729	0.753	0.423	0.643	0.863	0.332
	Fis	-0.142	-0.157	0.023	0.129	0.183	-0.045	-0.099	-0.064	0.295	0.226	0.425	0.707
	r	0.000	0.005	0.245	0.062	0.079	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.617	0.114	0.200	0.387
	P value	0.185	0.861	0.741	0.988	0.923	0.488	0.088	0.261	0.993	1.000	1.000	1.000

The estimation of heterozygote deficit (Hd) in each population was the following: Bucharest- MIC2, MIC5, MIC6, MIC9 and MIC12 showed significant values, in the case of Constanța MIC5, MIC10, MIC11, MIC12, MIC13, for Oradea MIC4, MIC11, MIC12 and MIC13, for Ploșoru MIC5, MIC7, MIC9 and MIC12, for Satu Mare MIC4, MIC9, MIC12, and for Timișoara MIC5 and MIC10. The Hd in case of loci was the following: MIC5, MIC9 and MIC12 had the most significant values among loci (Additional file 5: Table S3).

There are several loci constantly under pairwise linkage disequilibrium: MIC2 with MIC8, MIC6 with MIC8, MIC5 with MIC11 and MIC11 with MIC13 (Additional file 6: Table S4).

These loci pairs were found in LD in the following populations: MIC2 & MIC8 in Constanța (P-value 0.026850) and Timișoara (P-value 0.031460); MIC6 & MIC8 none; MIC5 & MIC11 in Timișoara (P-value 0.001470); MIC11 & MIC13 in Satu Mare (P-value 0.024200). Among the 396 total tests of HWE 18 pairs significantly departed from HWE (P-value > 0.05) (Additional file 7: Table S5).

The allele number of each locus ranged from 1 to 11, with a mean of 5,68 alleles per locus. (Table 2). Allelic richness per locus per population ranged from 1 to 1.892 (Table 3), with a low average varying from 1.366 to 1.821. Largest allelic richness per population was detected in Timișoara with an average Rs of 1.726.

Table 3.

Allelic Richness per locus and population with mean values.

Loci	Mean						
MIC2	1.666	1.459	1.601	1.568 1.575	1.538	1.606	1.589
MIC3	1.686	1.745	1.79	1.669 1.751	1.8	1.78	1.788
MIC4	1	1.761	1.782	1.879 1.701	1.769	1.834	1.885
MIC5	1.738	1.758	1.866	1.825 1.783	1.512	1.881	1.9
MIC6	1.398	1.599	1.645	1.605 1.617	1.782	1.631	1.661
MIC7	1.5	1.773	1.754	1.475 1.625	1.717	1.462	1.692
MIC8	1.821	1.82	1.822	1.825 1.808	1.767	1.781	1.821
MIC9	1.761	1.706	1.731	1.651 1.742	1.695	1.779	1.869
MIC10	1.333	1.271	1.328	1 1.366	1.554	1.552	1.527

MIC11	1.867	1.742	1.677	1.822 1.769	1.685	1.803	1.787
MIC12	1.813	1.77	1.85	1.762 1.821	1.804	1.892	1.857
MIC13	1	1.43	1.298	1 1.404	1.747	1.712	1.641

The average inbreeding coefficient (FIS) value of the majority of loci were positive, ranging from 0.068 to 0.293 supporting a high rate of inbreeding (Table 2), meanwhile pairwise F_{ST} values between populations ranged from 0.048 to 0.163. The low F_{ST} values indicate that the populations are closely related to each other (Table 4).

Table 4.

Pairwise F_{ST} estimates for all loci

	ROBU	ROCO	RODE	ROPL	ROSM	ROTI
ROBU	-					
ROCO	0.106	-				
RODE	0.088	0.048	-			
ROPL	0.081	0.129	0.119	-		
ROSM	0.080	0.163	0.146	0.112	-	
ROTI	0.071	0.050	0.049	0.089	0.130	-

Geographic distances IBD (Table 5). The results suggest that geographic distance does not significantly contribute to the genetic differentiation observed in *Ae. albopictus* populations in Romania.

Table 5.

Below the diagonal: Genetic distance (F_{ST}/(1-F_{ST})) for all 6 populations of *Aedes albopictus* from Romania. Above the diagonal: geographic distances between populations ln (distance).

	ROBU	ROCO	RODE	ROPL	ROSM	ROTI
ROBU	-	12.266	12.670	12.481	12.964	12.015
ROCO	0.134	-	12.714	11.459	12.926	12.280
RODE	0.107	0.053	-	12.521	11.617	11.950
ROPL	0.085	0.174	0.156	-	12.724	12.198
ROSM	0.095	0.242	0.205	0.144	-	12.475
ROTI	0.082	0.055	0.054	0.107	0.175	-

A Bayesian clustering approach was applied using the programme STRUCTURE, the number of appropriate genetic clusters was determined using the Evanno method, ΔK supported 2 clusters for the 6 analysed populations, ROCO, RODE & ROTI being separated from the others (Figure 6), possibly reflecting distinct introduction events with different geographic origins.

Figure 6: STRUCTURE analysis bar plot. This program assigns unique genetic variation a colour code. Populations with one solid colour that is not shared by another group are genetically distinct. Populations that share colours are more similar. Note dominant colours in sampled populations are Red (Bucharest, Ploşoru, Satu mare) and Green (Constanţa, Oradea, Timişoara).

The number of f_0 migrants were calculated using GeneClass 2.0 (PIRY ET AL., 2004), where 3 individuals were identified as having migrant ancestry, with a probability below 0.01 (two individuals from Oradea and 1 from Timișoara). There is a correlation between populations from Oradea and Timișoara, as well as between populations from Oradea and Constanța (Additional file 8: Figure 2).

2.2.1.4 Discussion

Constant monitoring of the mosquito populations is essential, as early detection of new species and potential vectors can prevent serious epidemics if control measures are implemented. Assessments can be done as simple faunistic monitoring or active coordinated surveillance in suitable habitats and sites at risk for introduction and spread, such as trade routes, highways, airports, harbours, cemeteries, or highly frequented tourist destinations (SCHOLTE AND SCHAFFNER, 2007; BONIZZONI ET AL., 2013; COLLANTES ET AL., 2015). Understanding the patterns of gene flow and the population genetic structure of invasive vectors like *Ae. albopictus* is important for designing and interpreting the outcome of area-wide elimination strategies. After only 8 years from its first finding in Bucharest (PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015), *Aedes albopictus* has become established in 17 counties in Romania at present moment (current study). These new findings highlight the need that control measures should be implemented in the affected areas and further surveillance should be carried out, as it could prevent further invasion and the spread of insecticide resistance since Romania does not have an active mosquito surveillance program; hence, all the data originate from research-related sampling. Among the numerous molecular markers available in population genetics, microsatellites are one of the most powerful tools developed in recent years to study genetic variation among populations; combined with mitochondrial *coxI* gene analysis it provides reliable information regarding population structure. The inbreeding coefficients (FIS) of the majority of loci were positive, and the observed heterozygosity was less than expected heterozygosity in most cases, indicating an excess of homozygote genotypes at most loci and deviations from the HWE. Combined with the STRUCTURE bar plot analysis, the Bayesian clustering analysis showed that all the *Ae. albopictus* populations were allocated to two clades, and the best K value, as determined via the ΔK method of EVANNO ET AL., (2005), was also equal to two. However, the statistical approach to identify the most likely number of potential clusters allowed the conclusion that the sampled populations are most likely structured in two clusters. The bar plot analysis- and IBD analysis combined with the analysis of f_0 migrants shows that *Ae. albopictus* populations from Oradea and Timișoara likely originate from the same introduction event, but are separated from

the other populations. This heterogeneous picture is probably the result of a combination of multiple introductions and inbreeding within these small populations; Further analysis is needed to clarify the relationship between these populations.

2.3.1. Geographic distribution of the V1016G knockdown resistance mutation in *Aedes albopictus*: a warning bell for Europe

2.3.1.1. Introduction

In the last few decades, mosquito-borne arboviruses (i.e. arthropod-borne viruses, such as dengue and chikungunya) have undergone an extraordinary spread as a consequence of the colonization of large tropical and temperate regions by invasive *Aedes* mosquito species (WEAVER AND REISEN, 2010; WHO, 2014). In particular, in less than 40 years, *Aedes albopictus* has invaded all continents except Antarctica—thanks to the capacity of its eggs to sustain both desiccation and low temperatures—and has become an increasing public health concern also in temperate regions. In fact, several autochthonous outbreaks of dengue (dengue virus [DENV] in Croatia, France, Spain and Italy (GJENERO-MARGAN ET AL., 2011; SUCCO ET AL., 2016; LAZZARINI ET AL., 2020)) and two major chikungunya (chikungunya virus [CHIKV]) outbreaks in Italy (REZZA ET AL., 2007; VENTURI ET AL., 2017) have been reported since the species' appearance in Europe. Since no specific medical treatment exists for these diseases, integrated vector management is the only available strategy to limit the public health burden (BELLINI ET AL., 2020).

To reduce mosquito nuisance and the risk of disease outbreaks, European guidelines for the surveillance of invasive mosquitoes (ECDC, 2012) recommend larval source reduction and larvicide applications. In contrast, pyrethroid-based adulticidal interventions are recommended only in the cases of ongoing—or high risk of—virus transmission, when a fast and effective abatement of adult mosquitoes is necessary. Pyrethroids, which are the only insecticide class for mosquito adulticide spraying registered in Europe (EU, 2018a, 2018b), interact with the voltage-sensitive sodium channel (VSSC) and interfere with the transmission of nervous signals, resulting in fast knockdown and eventually death of the mosquito (SODERLUND, 2012). However, their effectiveness is increasingly compromised by the rise of insecticide resistance. This is observed in all major mosquito vector species, including *Aedes aegypti* and Afrotropical malaria vectors, and has been recently reported in *Ae. albopictus* populations from both the native (CHUAYCHAROENSUK ET AL., 2011;

LEE ET AL., 2014; THANISPONG ET AL., 2015; ISHAK ET AL., 2015; CHEN ET AL., 2016; GAO ET AL., 2018; SU ET AL., 2019; LIU ET AL., 2020) and the invasive ranges (KAMGANG ET AL., 2011; KUSHWAH ET AL., 2015; SIVAN ET AL., 2015; NGOAGOUNI ET AL., 2016; ARSLAN ET AL., 2016; RICHARDS ET AL., 2018), including populations in Italy and Spain (BENGOA ET AL., 2017; PICHLER ET AL., 2018; PICHLER ET AL., 2019a).

Target site mutations in the *vssc* gene, conferring knockdown resistance (*kdr*), are among the best-characterized mechanisms contributing to pyrethroid resistance across all major mosquito vector species. These *kdr* mutations weaken the binding of the pyrethroid insecticide to the sodium channel, thereby reducing the knockdown effect (SODERLUND, 2012). Studies on *Ae. aegypti* have identified several point mutations (reviewed by MOYES ET AL., 2017) in the S6 transmembrane segments of domain II and III of the VSSC protein that constitute the pyrethroid binding site (O'REILLY ET AL., 2006). Among these, V410L, S989P, I1011M, V1016G and F1534C show the strongest association with resistance phenotypes (MOYES ET AL., 2017). Moreover, several mutations act synergistically, resulting in enhanced levels of resistance. In particular, functional assays showed that, compared to the wild type, the co-occurrence of the three mutations S989P, V1016G and F1534C decreases the susceptibility to permethrin and deltamethrin by 1100- and 90-fold, respectively (HIRATA ET AL., 2014).

Despite studies having so far mostly focused on major vector species, in the last decade a few mutations within the *vssc* gene have also been identified in *Ae. albopictus*, in particular in positions 1534 (F1534C/S/L/W/R; (KASAI ET AL., 2011; CHEN ET AL., 2016; ZHOU ET AL., 2019; TANCREDI ET AL., 2020; CHEN ET AL., 2021)), 1016 (V1016G/I (ZHOU ET AL., 2019; KASAI ET AL., 2019; TANCREDI ET AL., 2020)) and 1532 (I1532T (XU ET AL., 2016)). Among these, the only alleles confirmed to be associated with strong pyrethroid resistance phenotypes are 1534C (KASAI ET AL., 2019), 1534S (GAO ET AL., 2018; ZHOU ET AL., 2019; KASAI ET AL., 2019; YAN ET AL., 2020) and 1016G (PICHLER ET AL., 2019a; KASAI ET AL., 2019). The latter has been shown to confer the highest levels of resistance to different Pyrethroids (HIRATA ET AL., 2014; KASAI ET AL., 2019) and has been reported from the species native range (ZHOU ET AL., 2019; KASAI ET AL., 2019; TANCREDI ET AL., 2020), as well as from Reunion Island in the Indian Ocean (TANCREDI ET AL., 2020). In the European region, it has only been detected in Italy, where it is widespread and reaches alarming frequencies of up to 45% in some coastal sites (PICHLER ET AL., 2019a; PICHLER ET AL., 2021).

Genotyping pyrethroid resistance-associated mutations in mosquito samples from natural populations represents a powerful approach to detect early signs of resistance without the need of carrying out phenotypic bioassays that require

availability of live mosquitoes, dedicated facilities and appropriate expertise (DUSFOUR ET AL., 2019). Indeed, PCR-based approaches have proved to be instrumental in monitoring the onset and spread of *kdr* alleles and in raising awareness of insecticide resistance in *Ae. aegypti* and major malaria vectors (DUSFOUR ET AL., 2019).

The aim of this work was to map the presence and frequency of the V1016G mutation in *Ae. albopictus* populations across Europe.

2.3.1.2 Materials and methods

European *Ae. albopictus* specimens were sampled between 2015 and 2020 within the framework of AIM-COST Action (<http://www.aedescost.eu>) and of the ARBOMONITOR projects. Mosquitoes were collected by either ovitraps, larval sampling or adult trapping methods (see Additional file 9: Table S5). Larvae collected in the field or hatched from ovitrap-collected eggs were reared to adults under standard insectary conditions.

The DNA was extracted from single legs or whole individual mosquito carcasses using the DNAzol® (RIDER ET AL., 2012) or CTAB (WEEKS ET AL., 2000) methods. The allele-specific PCR (AS-PCR) assay for V1016G genotyping was performed either on DNA extracted from single specimens or on pooled DNA extracted from three specimens (PICHLER ET AL., 2021). In the case of detection of the 1016G allele in one of the pools, genotyping by PCR of each of the three specimens was performed separately.

For a subset of specimens, a fragment of domain II of the *vssc* gene was sequenced following the protocol described by KASAI ET AL. (2019). This comprised all specimens identified as either homozygotes or heterozygotes for the mutated 1016G allele by AS-PCR, as well as a subset of randomly chosen homozygotes for the susceptible 1016V allele from each country. PCR products were purified using the SureClean Kit (Bioline; Meridian Bioscience, Cincinnati, OH, USA), and the amplicons were sequenced either at BMR Genomics s.r.l. (Padua, Italy) or at STAB Vida (Oeiras, Portugal). Results from sequencing and AS-PCR genotyping were compared and the accuracy of the AS-PCR was estimated as the number of correct assessments divided by the total number of observations, taking the DNA sequencing results as the gold standard. Genotyping results were deposited in VectorBase.org (Project ID: VBP0000793). An interactive map reporting frequencies of the V1016G mutation per site (including also reports from previous publications; (PICHLER ET AL., 2019a; PICHLER ET AL., 2021)) was created using the Leaflet package for R (<https://rstudio.github.io/leaflet/>) in R studio version 2019. The database was better visualized by exploiting “*tydiverse*” and “*ddply*.” Finally, the “*classInt*”

package was used to obtain the scales of frequency of V1016G. The interactive map code and the data are available at:

https://randomxsk8.github.io/MedEnt_Sapienza/resist_map.html.

2.3.1.3. Results

Here we report for the first time the presence of the V1016G mutation in European *Ae. albopictus* populations outside Italy. Overall, 2530 specimens from 69 sampling sites in 19 European countries were PCR-genotyped (Additional file 9: Table S5). For a subsample of 265 specimens, a fragment of domain II of the *vssc* gene, including position 1016, was also sequenced to validate the PCR results. Consistently with the results reported by PICHLER ET AL. (2021), the AS-PCR assay accuracy was 94%. All mismatches (N = 16) between AS-PCR and sequencing were due to specimens homozygous for the 1016V susceptible allele and PCR-genotyped as heterozygotes (Table 6). This result confirms the previously reported slight overestimation of mutant allele detection by AS-PCR (PICHLER ET AL., 2021) and highlights the relevance of confirming PCR results by sequencing individuals carrying the resistant 1016G allele, particularly when the allele is detected for the first time in a region. Sequence analysis of the 16 incorrectly PCR-genotyped specimens did not reveal mutations in primer binding sites. Since 12 out of the 16 specimens came from only three sampling sites (i.e. Burgas in Bulgaria, Bucharest in Romania and Basauri in Spain), it is possible to hypothesize that low-quality DNA may have biased the PCR reaction.

Table 6.

Comparison of genotyping results obtained by sequencing the V1016G knockdown resistance mutation of the *vssc* gene in *Aedes albopictus* and by allele-specific-PCR assay

Genotyping results by AS-PCR assay	Genotyping results by sequencing			Total
	VV	VG	GG	
VV	203	-	-	203
VG	16	45	-	61
GG	-	-	1	2
Total	219	45	1	265

Noteworthy, the amino acid valine at position 1016 of the VSSC protein was encoded by the GTG codon instead of the wild-type GTA codon in five specimens, including two heterozygote GTA/GTG specimens, one homozygote GTG/GTG specimen from Greece and two heterozygote GTA/GTG specimens from Serbia. This synonymous substitution has already been observed in Italian specimens (PICHLER ET AL., 2021) and shown to have no impact on AS-PCR results. Moreover, as already described by

ZHOU ET AL. (2019) and PICHLER ET AL. (2021), the amplicon lengths varied by about 10 bp. This variation is due to insertions present in the intron 20 of the *vssc* gene, abutting codon position 1016. However, this does not interfere with the correct identification of the 1016V and 1016G alleles.

The combined AS-PCR and sequencing results reveal the presence of the 1016G allele at 12 sites from nine countries, at frequencies ranging from 1 to 8% per sampling site (Figure 7; Table 7; Additional file 9: Table S5). However, the sample size for some of the sites are low (Additional file 9: Table S5), and no detection of the 1016G mutation in these samples may imply low frequencies rather than absence in the whole population. Despite this limitation, we observed a spatial trend with the resistant allele being mostly detected in two clusters. The first cluster, hereafter called the “Western Cluster,” includes mainly Mediterranean coastal sites from Italy (Rome and Bari), France (Nice and Perpignan) and Malta (Luqa) but also sites in Spain (Basauri) and Switzerland (Basel). The second cluster, hereafter called the “Eastern cluster,” includes the easternmost sites on both sides of the Black sea from Bulgaria (Burgas), Turkey (Istanbul and Igneada) and Georgia (Batumi) as well as one site from Romania (Bucharest). Whether the observed clusters correspond to independent mutation or introduction events or reflect dispersal through migration and gene flow from the same source populations remains to be understood. Intriguingly, population genomic studies tracking the invasion history of *Ae. albopictus* in Europe revealed a pattern consistent with that of the 1016G *kdr* allele distribution. These studies showed high connectivity and close genetic relationship among Western European populations and identify Italian populations as possible bridgeheads for the invasion of other Western European countries (KOTSAKIOZI ET AL., 2018; SHERPA ET AL., 2019; PICHLER ET AL., 2019b). In line with the present results, the same studies suggest that the populations from Eastern Europe originated from a different source population and that a major barrier to gene flow exists between Western European and Balkan clusters.

Figure 7. Distribution of the V1016V knockdown locus (*kdr*) in the gene encoding the voltage-sensitive sodium channel (*vssc*) in *Aedes albopictus* across Europe. Each dot represents a sampling site, while the size corresponds to the number of specimens that were PCR-genotyped for the V1016V *kdr* locus from that site. Details on the sampling sites and the 1016G allele frequencies per site are given in Additional file 9: Table S5. Green dots represent samples with wild-type 1016V allele only; blue dots represent samples where the *kdr* 1016G allele was detected. The georeferenced map was produced using the leaflet package (<https://rstudio.github.io/leaflet/>) in RStudio 4.1.2 with map data from OpenStreetMap contributor

Table 7. Genotype and allele frequencies across European countries for wild-type (1016V) and mutated (1016G) alleles at position 1016 of the *vssc* gene in *Aedes albopictus* field populations sampled across Europe. G Mutated 1016G allele, V wild-type 1016V allele

Country	N sites	N specimens	Genotype frequency			1016G frequency
			VV	VG	GG	
Abkhazia (Georgia)	2	47	1.00	–	–	–
Albania	3	96	1.00	–	–	–
Bulgaria	2	107	0.935	0.065	–	0.033
Croatia	3	103	1.00	–	–	–
France	5	130	0.985	0.015	–	0.008
Georgia	1	49	0.980	0.020	–	0.010
Greece	5	283	1.00	–	–	–
Italy	2	71	0.845	0.155	–	0.077
Malta	1	50	0.960	0.040	–	0.020
Montenegro	3	126	1.00	–	–	–
Portugal	2	76	1.00	–	–	–
Romania	4	391	0.969	0.028	0.003	0.017
Russia	4	50	1.00	–	–	–
Serbia	7	274	1.00	–	–	–
Slovenia	1	40	1.00	–	–	–
Spain	14	384	0.995	0.005	–	0.003

Switzerland	6	65	0.954	0.046	-	0.023
Turkey	4	188	0.963	0.037	-	0.019
Total	69	2530	0.981	0.018	-	0.010

2.3.1.4 Discussion

In this study, we focused on the detection of the 1016G mutation. However, other *kdr* mutations conferring pyrethroid resistance could contribute to a reduction in the susceptibility to Pyrethroids and might even co-occur with the 1016G variant. In *Aedes aegypti*, a combination of the 1016G and 1534C alleles was found to have a strong synergistic effect, conferring increased resistance to Pyrethroids in individuals carrying both mutations (HIRATA ET AL., 2014; DUSFOUR ET AL., 2015). In *Ae. albopictus*, specimens carrying both alleles have not been reported yet, despite both mutations in positions 1016 and 1534 circulate in populations from the native range in Vietnam (KASAI ET AL., 2019) and China (ZHOU ET AL., 2019; TANCREDI ET AL., 2020). Therefore, it would not come as a surprise to find co-occurrence of the two alleles also in Eastern Europe since the 1016G allele is found in countries neighbouring Greece and mutation F1534C has been reported from Greece at frequencies up to 68% (BALASKA ET AL., 2020). Moreover, the F1534C allele could likely be introduced into Italy by passive dispersal of *Ae. albopictus* specimens across the sea between Italy and Greece through extensive maritime traffic. Therefore, we highly recommend extending the insecticide resistance monitoring to include additional PCR diagnostics for alternative *kdr* alleles, including F1534C (ZHU ET AL., 2019), and assessing the phenotype of possibly found multi-locus resistant populations.

2.3.1.5 Conclusions

Genotyping of *kdr* mutations in major mosquito vector species such as *Ae. aegypti* and Afrotropical malaria vectors species has proven to be instrumental to trigger pyrethroid resistance management plans to slow down or reverse resistance spreading (SHERPA ET AL., 2019). The present study represents the first effort to map the V1016G *kdr* mutation in *Ae. albopictus* on a continental scale in Europe.

On the one hand, results show that the very high frequencies previously reported from Italy are unparalleled in other European countries, consistently with a more extensive and/or protracted pyrethroid selective pressure in Italy. On the other hand, the presence of the 1016G allele in European populations both west and east of Italy represents a wake-up call for mosquito surveillance programs and highlights the need to include the monitoring of pyrethroid resistance in their activities. PCR genotyping of *kdr*-alleles represents a cost-effective and sensible tool to do this and, in case of detection of a sharp increase in frequencies, would allow timely

implementation of policies to counteract inappropriate pyrethroid spraying for nuisance reduction and/or impose rotation of different pyrethroid-based adulticides for mosquito control. Notably, since insecticide use against agricultural pests is also known to represent an additional source of selective pressure for pyrethroid resistance in mosquitoes, rotation of different insecticidal compounds or enhanced integrated control measures in agriculture should also be considered (MICHAELAKIS ET AL., 2021). This would prevent the risk of a reduced efficacy of emergency spraying in the case of an arbovirus outbreak.

Finally, the interactive map made available in this study includes all data so far available on 1016G allele distribution in Europe and will be updated with results from future genotyping studies on this and other *kdr* alleles. The map represents an easy tool for public health officers and private companies involved in mosquito control to assess the risk of pyrethroid resistance spreading in their regions in the early phases (i.e. when the frequency of V1016G or other *kdr* alleles is still low), thus opening the possibility to activate monitoring and management activities, instead of simply increasing pyrethroid concentrations, with inevitable harm to the environment and non-target species.

3. Conclusions and general recommendations

- Suburban environments like cemeteries usually show large populations of *Aedes albopictus*, because flower vases serve as optimal breeding spots for this container breeding species.
- Since its first discovery in Romania, *Ae. albopictus* has several well established populations in the lowland and western parts of the country, it shows a rapid and aggressive expansion.
- The new records of *Ae. albopictus* and *Ae. japonicus* show a continuous spreading tendency, which highlights the need to further assess these species' distribution and abundance, also to evaluate the risk of pathogen transmission related to these vector species.
- New sampling sites should be kept under observation throughout the country in order to monitor the invasion of *Ae. japonicus* to assess the species' status in Romania.
- Our findings draw attention to the dissemination of invasive mosquito species, which, together with increased global travel and trade, as well as the ongoing climate crisis, presents a significant risk to the public health system and the economy.
- Invasive species expand their geographic range steadily, increasing the circulation of vector-borne diseases globally.
- We recommend that future investigations should be carried out in Romania and elsewhere to assess the distribution of invasive mosquito species and make local authorities aware of the situation so they can carry out regular surveillance and mosquito control in the affected areas.
- Genotyping of *kdr* mutations in *Ae. albopictus* and other invasive mosquito species has proven to be efficient in designing mosquito control campaigns in order to slow down the spread of the pyrethroid resistance.
- Presence of V1016G and F1534C *kdr* mutations in Romanian *Ae. albopictus* populations represents a wake-up call for authorities to design mosquito surveillance programs and appropriate mosquito control strategies to assess the further spread of the insecticide resistance genes in the invasive mosquito populations.
- Inappropriate pyrethroid spraying for nuisance reduction of mosquito populations will favour the spread of *kdr* genes, therefore we recommend a rotation of different pyrethroid-based adulticides for mosquito control, this would help to prevent the risk of a reduced efficacy of emergency spraying in the case of an arbovirus outbreak.

- Future *kdr* genotyping studies of the invasive mosquito populations in Romania are needed, as well as the need for a design of an early risk monitoring system which would allow public health officers and private companies involved in mosquito control to assess the risk of pyrethroid resistance spreading in time and would help them to operate management activities in early phases, preventing them to harm non-target species.
- Among the numerous molecular markers available in population genetics, microsatellites are one of the most powerful tools developed in recent years to study genetic variation among populations; combined with mitochondrial *coxI* gene analysis it provides reliable information regarding population structure.
- Understanding the patterns of gene flow and the population genetic structure of invasive vectors like *Ae. albopictus* is important for designing and interpreting the outcome of area-wide elimination strategies.
- The statistical approach to identify the most likely number of potential clusters allowed the conclusion that the sampled *Ae. albopictus* populations from Romania are most likely structured in two clusters. This heterogeneous picture is probably the result of a combination of multiple introductions and inbreeding within these small populations; Further analysis is needed to clarify the relationship between these populations.

4. Originality

Chapter 2.1.1. "The invasive Asian tiger mosquito *Aedes albopictus* in Romania: towards a country-wide colonization?" is the first comprehensive study in Romania that focuses on the distribution of the invasive *Ae. albopictus* and covers a large area. The study presents an updated distribution data, which shows that the lowland southeast and western regions of the country host several established populations of *Ae. albopictus*, as well as we reported this species for the first time inside the Carpathian Mountain's arch.

Chapter 2.1.2. "Emergence of the invasive Asian bush mosquito, *Aedes (Finlaya) japonicus japonicus*, in an urban area, Romania" is the first detailed investigation in Romania that aimed to monitor the presence of *Aedes* invasive mosquitoes based on a Pan-European coordinated surveillance plan. Here we are reporting for the first time the presence of *Ae. japonicus* in Romania.

Chapter 2.2.1. "Genotyping of various microsatellite loci shows multiple introduction events of *Aedes albopictus* (Diptera: *Culicidae*) in Romania" is the first comprehensive study conducted with the help of microsatellite markers aimed to assess the genetic diversity and genetic relationships among *Ae. albopictus* populations in Romania. In this study we evaluate for the first time introduction events of the Romanian *Ae. albopictus* populations based on microsatellite data.

Chapter 2.3.1. "Geographic distribution of the V1016G knockdown resistance mutation in *Aedes albopictus*: a warning bell for Europe" is the first comprehensive study to assess the presence of *kdr* mutations in *Ae. albopictus* populations in Romania. Our findings confirm the presence of the V1016G *kdr* mutation in one of the analyzed populations, in Bucharest, which was the first introduction point of the species in Romania, and possible the oldest known population in the country.

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ANNEX

Ethical statement

All the activities were performed according to ethical permits and national legislation.

Like in all vector biology studies, volunteers may get in contact with infectious agents during field activities, therefore the human landing collection of the mosquitoes were performed with the consent of the volunteers; during the procedure preventive measures were taken granting the safety of participants, who wore protective clothing at the time of field collection, to minimize vector contact with the exposed skin.

Supplementary material

Chapter 2.1.1. All data presented in the article are included in the article and its supplementary files;

Additional file 1: Table S1. MS Excel table including all trapping data (date, trapping sites, coordinates, captured specimens, trap types used) (XLSX 20 kb);

The supplementary material related to this study is available online at:

https://static-content.springer.com/esm/art%3A10.1007%2Fs00436-020-06620-8/MediaObjects/436_2020_6620_MOESM1_ESM.xlsx

Chapter 2.1.2. All data presented in the article are included in the article; 30 April 2021: A Correction to this paper has been published:

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04730-5>

Chapter 2.1.3. All data presented in the manuscript are included in the manuscript and supplementary material related to this study is available by request from the author;

Additional file 2: Dataset S1. Summarizing CSV file with all available data;

Additional file 3: Table S2. List of the twelve microsatellite loci. Primers were designed by BEEBE ET AL., 2013; MANNI ET AL., 2015; and MANNI ET AL., 2017;

Additional file 4: Figure 1. Phylogenetic tree constructed with Tamura 3-parameter of Mega-X software. The robustness of each node was estimated using 1000 bootstrap replications under the Neighbor-Joining statistical method;

Additional file 5: Table S3. Estimation of exact P-Values by the Markov chain method, heterozygote deficit results by population *After correction for multiple tests using a simple Bonferroni correction ($\alpha' = \alpha/n$; $\alpha' = 0.05/66$; $\alpha' = 0.000758$);

Additional file 6: Table S4. P-value for each locus pair across all populations (Fisher's method);

Additional file 7: Table S5. Estimation of exact P-Values by the Markov chain method, results by locus;

Additional file 8: Figure 2. f0 migrants shown in red with a probability below 0.01, in green the most likely population is shown;

Chapter 2.3.1. All data presented in the article are included in the article and its supplementary files; genotyping/sequencing data have been submitted to VectorBase.org (Project ID: VBP0000793);

Additional file 9: Table S5. Detailed genotyping results and samples collections/processing information per sampling site;

The supplementary material related to this study is available online at:

https://static-content.springer.com/esm/art%3A10.1186%2Fs13071-022-05407-3/MediaObjects/13071_2022_5407_MOESM1_ESM.xlsx

Ph.D. THESIS

Biology and ecology of the invasive mosquito species in Romania: distribution and molecular analysis of *Aedes albopictus* and *Aedes japonicus*

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ABSTRACT

Mosquitoes are the most medically and veterinary important arthropods, widely dispersed except in places that are permanently frozen (BECKER ET AL., 2010). Up to date there are approximately 3,614 species worldwide (<http://mosquito-taxonomic-inventory.info>), from which more than 100 species can be found throughout Europe.

The ongoing climate crisis, the increasing globalisation, the extended circulation of humans and of goods are continuously facilitating the dissemination of invasive mosquitoes towards new habitats. Thanks to their ecological plasticity and resistance, they are likely to adapt fast to new environments and changing climate (BECKER ET AL., 2010; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). One key of their success lays in their ability to produce freeze- and desiccation resistant eggs, that can travel long distances (BECKER ET AL., 2010).

Currently, in Europe there are five invasive *Aedes* mosquito species, *Aedes aegypti*, *Ae. albopictus*, *Ae. atropalpus*, *Ae. japonicus* and *Ae. koreicus* (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2013a). Newly introduced or established invasive mosquitoes have a great impact on local ecosystems, economy and on the public health systems as they are highly competitive with native mosquitoes, exploiting habitats and food resources, and can transmit numerous pathogens (LOUNIBOS, 2002; JULIANO AND LOUNIBOS, 2005; PAUPY ET AL., 2009; ANDREADIS AND WOLFE, 2010). Since there are very few native mosquito species in Europe that are capable to transmit chikungunya-, dengue-, or Zika virus (PRUDHOMME ET AL., 2019), the presence of these vectors is associated with exotic pathogens, making Europe vulnerable to arbovirus transmission and outbreaks.

In Romania out of the listed five invasive species in Europe, two are present, *Ae. albopictus* and *Ae. japonicus*.

Ae. albopictus was first introduced in 2012 in Romania (PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015) and it shows an aggressive and rapid expansion throughout the country. It is known to be a competent vector for several arboviruses (chikungunya-, dengue-, Zika-, La Crosse-, Eastern equine encephalitis-, Japanese encephalitis-, Venezuelan equine encephalitis-, West Nile virus) and to transmit filariae (*Dirofilaria immitis* and *D. repens*) (PAUPY ET AL., 2009; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). Several arbovirus outbreaks have been recorded throughout Europe, where *Ae. albopictus* played an important role in virus transmission (ANGELINI ET AL., 2007, BONILAURI ET AL., 2008; DELATTE ET AL., 2010; GRANDADAM ET AL., 2011; MARCHAND ET AL., 2013; DELISLE ET AL., 2015; SUCCO ET AL., 2016; GOSSNER ET AL., 2018).

Ae. japonicus first record dates back a few years, to 2020 (HORVÁTH ET AL., 2021) when the species was found during a coordinated Pan-European surveillance program (<https://www.aedescost.eu/aimsurv>) to detect the presence of invasive mosquitoes in Cluj-Napoca.

However, *Ae. japonicus* is not considered to be an important vector, it is known to be able to transmit Zika-, dengue-, chikungunya-, Japanese encephalitis-, La Crosse-, Eastern equine encephalitis-, St. Louis encephalitis-, Rift Valley fever- and West Nile virus (TAKASHIMA AND ROSEN, 1989; ANDREADIS ET AL., 2001; SARDELIS ET AL., 2002a; SARDELIS ET AL., 2002b; SARDELIS ET AL., 2003; SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2011; TURELL ET AL., 2013; ABBO ET AL., 2020) and susceptible to both *Dirofilaria repens* and *D. immitis* (SILAGHI ET AL., 2017).

Romania is a hotspot for West Nile encephalitis, each year having significant number of human cases, with the highest numbers in 2018 (ECDC, 2019b). Several imported cases of dengue (DINU ET AL., 2015), Zika (FLORESCU ET AL., 2017), yellow fever (ECDC, 2018) and chikungunya (JAVELLE ET AL., 2019) have been recently reported in Romania, which raises concern about the presence of invasive mosquito species, as Romania has no active mosquito surveillance system, nor coordinated vector control, making the country vulnerable to future outbreaks.

The ecology of invasive mosquito species has become a hot topic in the past decades, as their expansion and the medical and veterinary importance they have has raised awareness in European countries. Several studies focus on distribution and abundance of the species', as well as on the molecular approach to investigate their vector potential, phylogenetic relationships and latest the insecticide resistance. In Romania there are few studies focusing on alien mosquito species, and they are mostly targeting abundance and distribution of the mosquitoes. We lack important information regarding the species seasonal activity, vector potential, impact on local mosquito populations, further expansion trends based on climatic data, insecticide resistance and phylogenetic relationships. Through our research we aimed to fill some of these scientific gaps, as follows:

- to assess the distribution and abundance of invasive mosquito species in Romania, with an emphasis on range expansion in urban- and peri-urban areas;
- to launch an active coordinated surveillance program to detect invasive mosquito species, and to introduce citizen science methods as a part of an active surveillance system;
- to draw attention of the importance of constant monitoring of invasive species and to strengthen the relationship among experts, public health officers and stakeholders in the hope to build and

implement an active surveillance system, and an early alert system with appropriate and in-time measures which follow European guidelines to tackle the risk that invasive mosquitoes pose on the economy and public health;

- to evaluate the phylogenetic relationships based on microsatellite data in Romanian *Ae. albopictus* populations, and to compare to other European populations;
- to assess the presence of insecticide resistance genes in *Ae. albopictus* populations in Romania

The first part of the thesis (Chapter 1. Introduction) focuses on the current knowledge of the biology and ecology of mosquitoes in general, basics of mosquito taxonomy, a short presentation of the invasive mosquito species occurring in Europe and their medical importance based on literature data. The second part (Chapter 2. Original research) presents four original manuscripts, divided in two parts. The first part consists of two studies regarding the distribution data of invasive mosquito species in Romania, while the second part consists of two manuscripts that covers molecular approaches to identify genetic relationships based on microsatellite markers and knockdown resistance mutation in Romanian *Ae. albopictus* populations. The last part of the thesis consists of a summary of our conclusions and recommendations, as well as we listed the references in alphabetical order from the introduction part and the presented studies.

In the first part of the second chapter (2.1.1) we aimed to collect information regarding the distribution of *Ae. albopictus* in urban-, and peri-urban sites in Romania. In the last decade, urbanization process showed a growing tendency in the country which has been facilitating the dispersal of invasive species. *Ae. albopictus* is highly anthropogenic compared to other native mosquitoes, feeds on a large range of hosts, but predominantly on humans in urban areas. The last study evaluating the distribution of *Ae. albopictus* dates back to 2015 (PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015) and only focuses on Bucharest and its close surroundings, summarizing data from three consecutive years of sampling. In order to update the knowledge of the distribution of the species we conducted a study investigating potential breeding sites (we placed ovitraps along busy transport routes and inspected vases in cemeteries) in 53 localities in 13 counties. As an outcome of this study we confirmed the presence of *Ae. albopictus* in 7 counties, and we reported its presence for the first time inside the historical region of Transylvania (Sibiu). According to our findings, *Ae. albopictus* has several established populations in the lowland in the southern-, as well as in the north-western

part of the country, highlighting the rapid expansion of the species, and the need for further investigations.

The second study of the second chapter (2.1.2) is focusing on the implementation of a Pan-European surveillance program of invasive mosquitoes, an initiative coordinated by the Aedes Invasive Mosquitoes COST Action (www.aedescost.eu/aimsurv). To the beginning of the study no activity of invasive mosquitoes was detected in Cluj-Napoca, therefore we considered to place the traps in the airport apron area, as it represents an important entry point for the tourists and goods, therefore to invasive species too. The study was carried out for three consecutive months, from the end of June to the end of September 2020, aiming to cover the peak activity of invasive mosquito species. During one of the regular check-ups one ovitrap was found to contain several eggs of *Ae. japonicus*. This is the first report of the species in Romania. Further surveillance should be carried out to establish the species status in Romania, as given the country's climatic and environmental conditions there is a great probability that this new species will become established, creating nuisance and increasing public health concern.

The second part of the second chapter (2.2.1) consists of two studies based on molecular data, from which the first one presents data on the molecular phylogeny of different *Ae. albopictus* populations in Romania. In Europe there are several studies focusing on genetic relationships of different *Ae. albopictus* populations using molecular markers like microsatellites. This study represents the first phylogenetic analysis of *Ae. albopictus* in Romania, based on microsatellite markers and fragments of the mitochondrial COXI gene. In order to assess the genetic structure and diversity of *Ae. albopictus* populations, we chose a set of 12 different polymorphic microsatellite markers previously described by MANNI ET AL. (2015, 2017). Microsatellite typing showed several populations with lower observed than expected heterozygosity and inbreeding within the small populations, which could be influenced further by local admixture events. Data analysis showed a separation of the populations in two clusters, which indicate two distinct introduction events.

The last manuscript of the second chapter (2.3.1) evaluates pyrethroid resistance-associated mutations of the voltage-sensitive sodium channel (*vssc*) distribution and frequency in European *Ae. albopictus* samples. Among the best characterized mechanisms of pyrethroid resistance is the knockdown resistance (*kdr*), which is the result of a target site mutation of

the *vssc* gene. There are several types of *kdr* mutations previously studied on *Ae. aegypti*, our study focusing on the V1016G mutation only, which is highly associated with the insecticide resistant phenotypes (PICHLER ET AL., 2019; KASAI ET AL., 2019). This is the first study in Romania to assess pyrethroid resistance in invasive mosquito species. Our findings confirm the presence of the V1016G *kdr* mutation in one of the analyzed populations, in Bucharest. Genotyping pyrethroid resistance-associated mutations of the *vssc* gene gives us a powerful tool to detect the early signs of insecticide resistance, giving us more time to assemble appropriate mosquito control strategies. In a country like Romania, where we lack of continuous mosquito surveillance programs and coordinated mosquito management, this tool is the most useful when it comes about mosquito control. Monitoring of the spread of *kdr* alleles with the help of this novel PCR-based approach would be essential in the Romanian invasive mosquito populations.

General conclusions and recommendations

The main purpose of this Ph.D. thesis was to evaluate biotic and abiotic factors influencing the dispersal of invasive mosquito species, to give an insight of their current distribution and phylogenetic relationships, to assess genetic diversity and to understand the introduction events that led to the establishment of *Ae. albopictus* in Romania. Moreover, we aimed to investigate genetic factors, such as genotyping pyrethroid resistance-associated gene mutations in *Ae. albopictus* populations, which further explains the species rapid expansion pattern. We concluded that the *Ae. albopictus* populations present in different parts of Romania, are likely to originate from distinct introduction events, which could further influence admixture among populations, increasing their vector capacity and their potential to inherit mutated alleles increasing their frequencies, creating strong pyrethroid resistance phenotypes, which could lead to the spread of multi-locus resistant populations across the country. The presence of mutated *kdr* alleles in Romanian *Ae. albopictus* populations should be a warning bell for the legislative body to take measures accordingly when it comes to mosquito management.

We dedicate our results to local authorities and public health experts, hence all available data regarding invasive mosquitoes originates from studies conducted by universities. The data we obtained during our brief study should help health authorities to evaluate the present situation regarding mosquito control in Romania, the implementation of an active surveillance system with the emphasis on the importance of the appropriate use of insecticides, in order to effectively eliminate nuisance and risks caused by invasive mosquito species.

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Teză de doctorat

Biologia și ecologia speciilor de țânțari invazivi în România: distribuția și analiza moleculară a speciilor *Aedes albopictus* și *Aedes japonicus*

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REZUMAT

Având o distribuție globală, cu excepția locurilor care sunt permanent înghețate, țânțarii sunt cele mai importante artropode din punct de vedere medical-veterinar (BECKER ET AL., 2010). În prezent există aproximativ 3614 de specii pe mapamond (<http://mosquito-taxonomic-inventory.info>), dintre care peste 100 de specii pot fi găsite în Europa. Încălzirea globală, globalizarea, transportul oamenilor și al mărfurilor facilitează încontinuu diseminarea țânțarilor invazivi către habitate noi. Datorită plasticității și rezistenței lor ecologice, țânțarii se adaptează rapid la medii noi și la schimbările climatice (BECKER ET AL., 2010; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). Succesul lor evolutiv constă în capacitatea de a produce ouă rezistente la îngheț și secetă, care pot călători pe distanțe lungi (BECKER ET AL., 2010). În prezent, în Europa există cinci specii invazive de țânțari *Aedes*, *Aedes aegypti*, *Ae. albopictus*, *Ae. atropalpus*, *Ae. japonicus* și *Ae. koreicus* (SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2013a). Țânțarii invazivi nou introduși/stabiliți au un impact mare asupra ecosistemelor locale, economiei și sistemelor de sănătate publică, deoarece sunt foarte competitivi cu țânțarii nativi, având capacitatea de a exploata habitatele și resursele alimentare și de a transmite numeroși agenți patogeni (LOUNIBOS, 2002; JULIANO AND LOUNIBOS, 2005; PAUPY ET AL., 2009; ANDREADIS AND WOLFE, 2010). Deoarece există foarte puține specii native de țânțari în Europa care sunt capabile să transmită virusuri ca Chikungunya, Dengue sau Zika (PRUDHOMME ET AL., 2019), prezența acestor vectori este asociată cu agenți patogeni exotici, care face Europa vulnerabilă la transmiterea arboviruselor. În România, dintre cele cinci specii invazive enumerate sunt prezente două, respectiv *Ae. albopictus* și *Ae. japonicus*.

Ae. albopictus a fost semnalat pentru prima dată în 2012 în România (PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015) și prezintă o expansiune agresivă și rapidă în toată țara. Este un vector competent pentru mai multe arbovirusuri (chikungunya-, dengue-, Zika-, La Crosse-, encefalita ecvină de est-, encefalita japoneză-, encefalita ecvină venezueleană-, virusul West Nile) și transmite filarii (*Dirofilaria immitis* și *D. repens*) (PAUPY ET AL., 2009; MEDLOCK ET AL., 2012). Au fost înregistrate mai multe focare de arboviroze în toată Europa, unde *Ae. albopictus* a avut un rol important în transmiterea virusurilor (ANGELINI ET AL., 2007, BONILAUDI ET AL., 2008; DELATTE ET AL., 2010; GRANDADAM ET AL., 2011; MARCHAND ET AL., 2013; DELISLE ET AL., 2015; ; SUCCO ET AL., 2016; GOSSNER ET AL., 2018).

Ae. japonicus a fost prima dată semnalat în România în 2020 (HORVÁTH ET AL., 2021), când specia a fost găsită în cadrul unui program de supraveghere

paneuropeană (<https://www.aedescost.eu/aimsurv>) pentru detectarea prezenței speciilor invazive de țânțari în Cluj-Napoca. *Ae. japonicus* nu este considerat a fi un vector important, deși este demonstrat că este susceptibil să transmită Zika-, Dengue-, Chikungunya-, encefalita japoneză, La Crosse, encefalita ecvină estică, encefalita St. Louis, febra Rift Valley, și virusul West Nile (TAKASHIMA AND ROSEN, 1989; ANDREADIS ET AL., 2001; SARDELIS ET AL., 2002a; SARDELIS ET AL., 2002b; SARDELIS ET AL., 2003; SCHAFFNER ET AL., 2011; TURELL ET AL., 2013; ABBO ET AL., 2020), cât și *Dirofilaria repens* și *D. immitis* (SILAGHI ET AL., 2017). România este un hotspot pentru encefalita West Nile, în fiecare an fiind raportat un număr semnificativ de cazuri umane, cel mai mare număr de semnalări fiind înregistrat în 2018 (ECDC, 2019b). În România au fost raportate recent mai multe cazuri importate de Dengue (DINU ET AL., 2015), Zika (FLORESCU ET AL., 2017), febră galbenă (ECDC, 2018) și Chikungunya (JAVELLE ET AL., 2019), ceea ce cauzează îngrijorări față de prezența speciilor invazive de țânțari, întrucât România nu are un sistem activ de supraveghere, nici control coordonat al vectorilor. Ecologia speciilor de țânțari invazivi a devenit un subiect popular în ultimele decenii, deoarece extinderea lor, importanța medicală și veterinară au crescut gradul de conștientizare în țările europene. Mai multe cercetări se concentrează asupra distribuției și abundenței acestor specii, precum și asupra studiilor moleculare pentru a investiga potențialul lor vectorial, relațiile filogenetice și mai recent, rezistența la anumite insecticide. În România există puține studii care se axează pe speciile invazive, iar acestea vizează mai ales abundența și distribuția țânțarilor. Ne lipsesc informații importante cu privire la activitatea sezonieră a speciilor, potențialul vectorial, impactul lor asupra populațiilor locale, tendințele de extindere ulterioare bazate pe date climatice, rezistența la insecticide și relațiile filogenetice între populații. Prin cercetarea de față ne-am propus să acoperim unele dintre aceste lacune științifice, astfel că obiectivele acestei lucrări au fost următoarele:

- Evaluarea distribuției și abundenței speciilor de țânțari invazivi în România, cu accent pe extinderea ariei în zonele urbane și periurbane;
- Lansarea unui program de supraveghere coordonată pentru a detecta specii invazive de țânțari și introducerea metodelor de “citizen-science” ca parte a unui sistem activ de supraveghere;
- Să atragem atenția asupra importanței monitorizării constante a speciilor invazive și să fortificăm relația dintre experți, ofițerii de sănătate publică și guvern în speranța de a construi și de a implementa un sistem activ de supraveghere și un sistem de alertă timpurie cu măsuri adecvate care urmează tendințe europene

pentru a aborda riscul pe care țânțarii invazivi îl prezintă asupra economiei și sănătății publice;

- Evaluarea relațiilor filogenetice pe baza analizei microsateleților în *Ae. albopictus* din România comparativ cu alte populații din Europa;
- Evaluarea prezenței genelor de rezistență la insecticide în populațiile *Ae. albopictus* din România;

Prima parte a tezei (Capitolul 1. Introducere) se concentrează pe cunoștințele actuale despre biologia și ecologia țânțarilor în general, elementele de bază ale taxonomiei țânțarilor, o scurtă prezentare a speciilor invazive de țânțari care apar în Europa și importanța lor medicală bazată pe date din literatură. A doua parte (Capitolul 2. Cercetare originală) prezintă patru manuscrise originale, împărțite în două părți. Prima parte constă în două studii privind datele de distribuție a speciilor de țânțari invazivi în România, în timp ce a doua parte constă în două manuscrise care acoperă analize moleculare pentru identificarea relațiilor genetice bazate pe markeri microsateleți și investigarea prezenței mutației knockdown în *Ae. albopictus*. Ultima parte a tezei constă într-un rezumat al concluziilor și recomandărilor autorilor, precum și lista referințelor în ordine alfabetică din studiile prezentate în cele două capitole.

În prima parte a celui de-al doilea capitol (2.1.1) ne-am propus să colectăm informații privind distribuția speciei *Ae. albopictus* în siturile urbane și periurbane din România. În ultimul deceniu în România, procesul de urbanizare arată o tendință de creștere, ceea ce a facilitat răspândirea speciilor invazive. *Ae. albopictus* este mult mai antropocentric în comparație cu alte specii native, se hrănește pe o gamă largă de gazde, predominant pe oameni, mai ales în zonele urbane. Ultimul studiu de evaluare a distribuției *Ae. albopictus* datează în 2015 (PRIOTEASA ET AL., 2015) și se focusează doar pe zona București și împrejurimi, rezumând datele de eșantionare din trei ani consecutivi. Pentru a actualiza cunoștințele despre distribuția speciei am realizat un studiu care investighează potențiale locuri de reproducere (am amplasat ovitraps de-a lungul rutelor de transport și am inspectat vase în cimitire) în 53 de localități din 13 județe. Ca rezultat al acestui studiu am confirmat prezența lui *Ae. albopictus* în 7 județe și am semnalat prezența sa pentru prima dată în interiorul regiunii istorice a Transilvaniei (Sibiu). Conform constatărilor noastre, *Ae. albopictus* are mai multe populații stabilite în zonele joase din sudul, precum și în partea de nord-vest a țării, evidențiind expansiunea rapidă a speciei și necesitatea unor investigații suplimentare.

Al doilea studiu din prima parte a capitolului II (2.1.2) se concentrează pe implementarea unui program paneuropean de supraveghere a țânțarilor invazivi, o inițiativă coordonată de Aedes Invasive Mosquitoes COST Action (www.aedescost.eu/aimsurv). Până la începerea studiului nu a fost depistată nicio activitate de țânțari invazivi în Cluj-Napoca. Prin urmare am avut în vedere amplasarea capcanelor în zona platformei aeroportului (Aeroportul Internațional Avram Iancu), deoarece acesta reprezintă un punct de intrare important pentru turiști și mărfuri, așadar și pentru speciile invazive. Studiul a fost realizat timp de trei luni consecutive, de la sfârșitul lunii Iunie până la sfârșitul lunii septembrie 2020, cu scopul de a acoperi activitatea de vârf a speciilor de țânțari. În timpul unuia dintre controalele regulate, s-a descoperit că un ovitrap conține mai multe ouă de *Ae. japonicus*. Acesta este primul raport al speciei în România. Ar trebui efectuată o supraveghere ulterioară pentru a stabili starea speciei în România, deoarece având în vedere condițiile climatice și de mediu ale țării, există o mare probabilitate ca această nouă specie să se stabilizeze, creând neplăceri și sporind îngrijorarea sănătății publice.

A doua parte a celui de-al doilea capitol (2.2.1) constă în două studii bazate pe date moleculare, dintre care primul prezintă date despre filogeneza moleculară a diferitelor populații de *Ae. albopictus* din România. În Europa există mai multe studii care se concentrează pe relațiile genetice ale diferitelor populații de *Ae. albopictus* folosind markeri moleculari precum microsateliții. Acest studiu reprezintă prima analiză filogenetică a *Ae. albopictus* în România, bazat pe markeri microsateliți și fragmente ale genei COXI mitocondriale. Pentru a evalua structura genetică și diversitatea genică a *Ae. albopictus*, am ales un set de 12 markeri microsateliți polimorfi descriși anterior de MANNI ET AL. (2015, 2017). Tiparea microsateliților a arătat mai multe populații cu heterozigoți observate mai puțin decât cele așteptate și consangvinizare în cadrul populațiilor mici, care ar putea fi influențate în continuare de evenimentele locale de amestecare. Analiza datelor a arătat o separare a populațiilor în două grupuri, care indică două evenimente de introducere distincte.

Ultimul studiu al celui de-al doilea capitol (2.3.1) evaluează mutațiile canalului de sodiu sensibil la tensiune (vssc) asociate cu rezistența la piretroizi în probe de *Ae. albopictus* din diferite părți ale Europei. Printre cele mai bine caracterizate mecanisme de rezistență la piretroizi se numără rezistența knockdown (kdr), care este rezultatul unei mutații în genei vssc. Există mai multe tipuri de mutații kdr studiate anterior pe *Ae. aegypti*, studiul nostru concentrându-se doar pe mutația V1016G, care este asociată

cu fenotipurile rezistente la insecticide (PICHLER ET AL., 2019; KASAI ET AL., 2019). Acesta este primul studiu din România care evaluează rezistența la piretroizi în speciile invazive de țânțari. Descoperirile noastre confirmă prezența mutației V1016G la una dintre populațiile analizate, în București. Genotiparea mutațiilor asociate rezistenței piretroidelor ne oferă un instrument puternic pentru a detecta semnele timpurii ale rezistenței la insecticide, oferindu-ne mai mult timp pentru a asambla strategii adecvate de control al țânțarilor. Într-o țară precum România, unde ne lipsesc programele de supraveghere și gestionarea coordonată a țânțarilor, acest instrument este cel mai util atunci când vine vorba de controlul țânțarilor. Monitorizarea răspândirii alelelor kdr cu ajutorul acestei noi abordări bazate pe PCR ar fi esențială în populațiile de țânțari invazivi în România.

Concluzii generale și recomandări

Scopul principal al acestei teze a fost de a evalua factorii biotici și abiotici care influențează răspândirea speciilor de țânțari invazivi, pentru a oferi o perspectivă asupra distribuția lor actuale și a relațiilor filogenetice și pentru a evalua diversitatea genetică și a înțelege evenimentele de introducere care au condus la stabilirea lui *Ae. albopictus* în România. Mai mult, ne-am propus să investigăm factorii genetici, cum ar fi genotiparea mutațiilor genetice asociate cu rezistența la piretroizi în *Ae. albopictus*, ceea ce explică modul de expansiune rapidă a speciei. Am ajuns la concluzia că *Ae. albopictus*, prezent în diferite părți ale României, provine cel mai probabil din mai multe introduceri distincte care ar putea influența și mai mult amestecul dintre populații, crescând capacitatea vectorială a acestora și potențialul lor de a moșteni alele mutante, creând astfel fenotipuri puternice de rezistență la piretroide, fapt care ar putea duce la răspândirea populațiilor rezistente în toată țara. Prezența alelelor kdr mutante în populații de *Ae. albopictus* în România ar trebui să fie o avertizare pentru autoritățile competente pentru a lua măsuri în consecință atunci când vine vorba de gestionarea țânțarilor. Dedicăm rezultatele noastre autorităților locale și experților în sănătate publică, prin urmare toate datele disponibile referitoare la țânțarii invazivi provin din studii efectuate de universități. Datele pe care le-am obținut în cadrul studiului nostru ar trebui să ajute autoritățile sanitare să evalueze situația actuală privind combaterea țânțarilor din România, implementarea unui sistem de supraveghere activă, cu accent pe importanța utilizării adecvate a insecticidelor, pentru a elimina în mod eficient neplăcerile și riscuri cauzate de speciile invazive de țânțari.

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